

Semantic-Aware Structure Preserving Image Filtering Techniques

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by

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*Dedicated to the scientific community
and to my family*

Abstract

Image filtering techniques play a crucial role in enhancing the quality of images. Digital images acquired by sensors often suffer from geometric, radiometric, and sensor-related distortions and noises. These imperfections can degrade image quality substantially. In turn, the effectiveness of image processing and analysis methods is closely tied to the quality of input images. Consequently, image filtering has become an essential and indispensable step in many image processing and image analysis applications.

There exist two approaches: spatial and frequency domain image filtering. Spatial domain filtering is inherently intuitive as it directly operates on image pixels, whereas frequency domain filtering works on signals derived from digital images. The spatial domain offers a practical advantage in image processing by enabling direct pixel-based operations, which preserve structures and enhance specific regions without the artifacts that can arise from frequency domain transformations. This approach is computationally simpler, supporting real-time applications that require fast processing. Additionally, it allows for flexible integration of semantic information, such as edges and textures, which are critical for tasks like object detection, segmentation, and classification, where maintaining spatial details is essential. Overall, the spatial domain is ideal for applications where clarity, precision, and efficiency are prioritized. Spatial domain image filtering techniques have evolved from basic linear filters to advanced non-linear ones, including edge-preserving filters, adaptive filters, region-based structure-preserving filters, and morphological filters. Over the past two decades, there has been a shift from gradient-based edge-preserving filtering to adaptive window-based edge preserva-

tion and region statistics-based structure preservation. These structure-preserving filtering techniques aim not only to preserve individual edges but also to retain meaningful structures while eliminating insignificant ones.

The gradual developments of pixel-based filtering methods primarily rely on region-based directional gradients (horizontal and vertical) and statistical measures, such as total variation (TV), relative total variance (RTV), and region covariance, as descriptors of structures and textures. These methods often struggle to effectively preserve the edges of objects and perform poor smoothing for varying scale textures/noises. Also, achieving optimal results with these approaches requires meticulous parameter tuning, involving the selection of appropriate neighbor window, region window, or kernel functions.

In recent times, the concept of semantic-aware structure-preserving filtering has emerged. Defining semantically meaningful structures within an image is one of the most challenging aspects of developing such filtering techniques. To address these challenges, in this thesis, we have proposed and developed a few robust semantic-aware structure-preserving filtering techniques. The basic approach of these techniques begins by generating a semantic-aware edge map that leverages the semantic information from the input image. Using this edge map, an edge-aware adaptive filtering technique is then developed.

As a first contribution of this thesis, a novel semantic-aware adaptive median morpho-filtering technique is proposed. First, it generates an edge-map by using semantic information extracted from the global and local morphological gradient histograms obtained from the input image. Then, using the generated edge-map a novel adaptive median morpho-filtering technique is proposed by defining a dynamic window that avoids overlapping of textural and structural contents of the image. Although the proposed technique provides satisfactory results for wide varieties of input images, the size of the window taken for considering semantic information is a critical parameter of this technique. The filtering result is significantly dependent on this parameter.

In order to reduce the limitation of the above filtering technique, in the second

contribution, a completely different approach is proposed to generate the semantic edge-map of the input image. We exploit Jensen-Shannon Divergence (JSD) to incorporate semantic information into edge-map generation. Here, we present two approaches for generating semantic edge-maps using JSD. In the first approach, JSD is directly used to distinguish between structural edge pixels and non-edge pixels. Where as in the second approach, a set of novel features are proposed to represent the pixels of the input image. These features are defined by exploiting Jensen-Shannon (JS) divergence in such a way that it incorporates semantic information of the pixel for determining whether it is a structural edge pixel or not. Then, projecting all the pixels into the feature space, a semantic-aware edge-map of the input image is generated by applying k-means clustering. Once the edge-map is obtained, the edge-aware adaptive recursive median filter proposed in the first contribution is used to generate the filtered image. Compared to the existing state-of-the-art methods, the proposed method outperforms for a wide variety of images with the minimal fine tuning of its parameters within a few discrete options.

The third contribution of this thesis introduces a parameter-efficient filtering technique that builds on the semantic information developed in the first and second contributions. This novel approach generates a semantic edge map of the input image by leveraging the morphological gradient distribution from the first contribution and the Jensen-Shannon divergence introduced in the second. Once the edge map is constructed, the edge-aware adaptive recursive median filter, also presented in the first contribution, is applied to produce the filtered image. Notably, this technique requires only one parameter, manually defined within four discrete options, making it efficient and straightforward to use. The effectiveness of the proposed method has been validated across a wide range of input images.

While image filtering techniques are widely employed in various computer graphics applications, they are rarely leveraged to incorporate spatial information for image classification tasks. The fourth key contribution of this thesis addresses this gap by demonstrating the effectiveness of our proposed filtering techniques

in enhancing hyperspectral image (HSI) classification through spatial information incorporation. Our filtering techniques are designed to preserve object structures effectively while reducing noise and texture, thus enabling the filtered images to retain valuable spatial information.

In this contribution, we first apply one of our proposed filtering techniques to generate multiple filtered versions of the HSI, creating a filtered profile. This profile provides spectral-spatial features for each pixel, which are then used as input to a classifier for HSI classification. The effectiveness of our approach is validated by comparing it to several leading spectral-spatial HSI classification methods.

Finally, we draw conclusions and discuss potential future advancements to extend this work further.

Keywords: Image filtering, edge-aware filtering, structure-preserving filtering, texture filtering, structure texture decomposition, semantic-aware image filtering, semantic image filtering

Declaration

I hereby certify that

- The work presented in this dissertation is my own original work, conducted under the general supervision of my advisor.
- This work has not been submitted to any other institution for any degree or diploma.
- I have adhered to the guidelines provided by Tezpur University in writing this thesis.
- I have followed the norms and guidelines outlined in the Ethical Code of Conduct of the university.
- Whenever I have used materials (data, theoretical analysis, and text) from other sources, I have properly cited them within the text of the dissertation and included their details in the references.

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Certificate of Supervisor

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “ **Semantic-Aware Structure Preserving Image Filtering Techniques** ” submitted to Tezpur University in the Department of Computer Science and Engineering under the School of Engineering, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Computer Science and Engineering, is a record of research work carried out by **Kunal Pradhan** under my supervision and guidance.

All assistance received from various sources has been duly acknowledged. No part of this thesis has been submitted elsewhere for the award of any other degree.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Swarnajyoti Patra'.

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Certificate

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The Committee recommends the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy.

Signature of Principal Supervisor

Signature of External Examiner

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" আমাদের যাত্রা হলো শুরু, এখন ওগো কর্ণধার তোমারে করি নমস্কার "

“ Our journey has begun, and now, O Captain, we bow to thou in reverence ”

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" দ্বিধা দ্বন্ধের দিন ঘোচার স্বপ্নে "

“ In the dream of a day when doubts and conflicts fade away ”

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“ Go deeper and go even deeper ”

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“This is the golden hour, the finest time to dare and dream ”

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" ফিরে এসো, ফিরে এসো, চাকা, রথ হয়ে, জয় হয়ে, চিরন্তন কাব্য হয়ে এসো । আমরা বিশ্বদ্ব
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Date:- 18/12/2024

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Glossary of Terms

BF	Bilateral Filtering
Reg-Cov	Region Covariance
BTF	Bilateral Texture Filtering
SATF	Structure Aware Texture Filtering
SATV	Structure Adaptive Total Variation
FABF	Fast Adaptive Bilateral Filter
RILS	Real-Time Iterative Least Square
GISF	Generalized Image Smoothing Framework
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
PSNR	Peak Signal to Noise Ratio
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index Measure
MSSIM	Multi-scale Structural Similarity Index Measure
PIQE	Perception-based Image Quality Evaluator
MI	Mutual Information
D_{KL}	Kullback-Leibler (KL) Divergence
JSD	Jensen Shannon Divergence
MGD	Morphological Gradient Distribution
SGI	Semantic Gradient Image
EPI	Edge Preservation Index
NGD	Normalized Gradient Deviation
FI	Fragmentation Index
NMI	Normalized Mutual Information

Symbols and Notations

δ	morphological dilation
ϵ	morphological erosion
$\delta(\epsilon)$	morphological opening
$\epsilon(\delta)$	morphological closing
$\epsilon(\delta)$	morphological closing
$\delta - \epsilon$	morphological gradient
$(\delta(\epsilon) + \epsilon(\delta))/2$	morphological texture filtering

Chapter 1

Introduction

There is a Chinese proverb that ‘a picture is worth a thousand words’. A digital image is a representation of visual information in a form that can be processed and manipulated by electronic systems, such as computers. It is composed of a grid of picture elements, commonly known as pixels. Each pixel contains information about color and brightness, and when combined, they create the overall visual representation of an image. Digital images can take various forms, including photographs, graphics, illustrations, and more. They can be created using digital cameras, scanners, or generated through computer graphics software. The most common formats for digital images include JPEG, PNG, GIF, and TIFF. Digital images can be edited, resized, and manipulated using image editing software, enabling a wide range of creative possibilities. They are widely used in various fields, such as photography, graphic design, web design, medical imaging, remote sensing images, text images, and scientific research. The ability to store, share, and transmit digital images has greatly facilitated communication and information exchange in the modern digital age.

Image processing encompasses the manipulation and analysis of digital images through various algorithms and techniques. This field involves enhancing, transforming, and extracting information from images to either improve their quality or derive significant insights. Image processing finds applications in numerous

areas such as computer vision, medical imaging, remote sensing, and multimedia. This is a multidisciplinary field that combines aspects of computer science, mathematics, and engineering. It plays a crucial role in various applications, from medical diagnostics and satellite imagery analysis to facial recognition and entertainment industry graphics.

Image analysis is a broader term that encompasses the extraction of meaningful information or knowledge from digital images through computational methods. It involves the application of various techniques and algorithms to analyze and interpret visual data. Image analysis can be used in a wide range of fields, including medicine, biology, astronomy, geology, remote sensing, and computer vision. Image analysis often involves a combination of image processing techniques, machine learning, and statistical methods to derive meaningful insights from visual data. It plays a crucial role in automating tasks that would be challenging or time-consuming for humans to perform manually and contributes to advancements in various scientific and technological fields.

Image filtering is a fundamental step in image processing and analysis, often serving as a crucial pre- or post-processing stage. It is essential across all image processing and analysis applications, laying the groundwork for enhancing image quality, reducing noise, and preparing images for further analysis. The effectiveness of image processing and analysis is heavily dependent on the quality of the output image. High-quality images provide a clear foundation for accurate feature detection and interpretation, enabling tasks like object detection, segmentation, and pattern recognition to perform effectively. Clear processing ensures essential features such as edges and textures are preserved, while reducing noise and artifacts minimizes misinterpretation and false results. Additionally, high-quality images improve analysis efficiency by reducing the need for complex corrective algorithms. Overall, well-processed images are critical for achieving accurate, reliable, and efficient outcomes in image analysis.

1.1 Image filtering

Image filtering techniques serve the crucial purpose of enhancing the quality of images. The presence of geometric, radiometric, and sensor-related effects in digital images captured by sensors often introduces noise and distortion. The effectiveness of various image processing and analysis methods significantly relies on the quality of the input and output images. Consequently, image filtering becomes a necessary and integral step in the majority of image processing and analysis applications.

Two primary approaches to image filtering techniques are spatial and frequency domain filtering. Spatial domain filtering is more intuitive as it directly operates on image pixels, while frequency domain filtering works on signals transformed from digital images. Spatial domain image filtering techniques have evolved from simple linear filters to advanced non-linear ones, including edge-preserving filters, adaptive filters, region-based structure preserving filters, and morphological filters. In recent years, developments have shifted from gradient-based edge-preserving filtering to adaptive window-based edge preserving and region statistics-based structure preserving filtering. These structure preserving filtering techniques aim not only to protect individual edges or lines but also to safeguard meaningful structures while eliminating insignificant ones. In contemporary times, semantic-aware structure preserving filtering has emerged as a concept. Defining the semantically meaningful structures within an image remains one of the most challenging aspects of developing such filtering techniques.

The limitations of recent gradient-based filtering methods are that they often rely on directional (horizontal and vertical) image gradients and certain region based statistical measures of them for structure/texture descriptors. This approach frequently fails to effectively preserve the corner portions of objects. Also, the measures of gradients are taken within a fixed-size neighbor window. That is why, to achieve optimal results with these methods, a substantial amount

Figure 1-1: Evolution of image filtering

of empirical study is needed to select appropriate neighbor window sizes, region window sizes, or kernel function parameters.

In contrast, morphological filters have the ability to preserve the structure of objects without relying on complex statistical measures. However, their effectiveness is heavily dependent on the size and shape of the structuring element. Connected component filtering, an advanced form of morphological filtering, can also be applied to preserve object structures in images. Nevertheless, it relies on component ordering and threshold values, making it less robust for preserving meaningful image structures.

Figure 1-1 is showing the evolution of all these different conventional spatial and range domain filtering techniques towards more sophisticated and meaningful semantic-aware image filtering approaches.

1.1.1 Weighted average filtering

Image filtering started its journey with simple weighted average filtering. Weighted average filtering [58, 106, 130] in spatial domain mainly takes the information of predefined neighbor pixels to update the centre pixel. As it averages the pixel values, it smooths the images and removes the small noises effectively, but as it

1.1. Image filtering

operates uniformly throughout the whole image, it can destroy the weak edges and weaken the sharp edges. Weighted average filtering is employed to enhance or denoise images by assigning different weights to neighboring pixels during the filtering process. The basic concept behind weighted average filtering is to replace the intensity value of a pixel with a weighted average of its neighboring pixels. The weights are typically determined by a predefined kernel or filter mask.

A brief step-by-step explanation of the weighted average filtering process is as follows:

- Selection of a kernel/filter mask: A kernel, or filter mask, is a small matrix that defines the weights assigned to neighboring pixels. Commonly used filter masks include the box filter, where all neighboring pixels have equal weights, and the Gaussian filter, which uses a Gaussian distribution over its distance from the central pixel to assign weights.
- Centering on a pixel: The filter mask is centered on each pixel in the image, and the weights are applied to the corresponding neighboring pixels.
- Weighted sum calculation: Multiply the intensity values of each neighboring pixel by its corresponding weight. Sum up the weighted values to get the weighted sum.
- Normalization: Divide the weighted sum by the sum of the weights in the filter mask to normalize the result.
- Replacement of pixel value: Replace the original intensity value of the central pixel with the normalized weighted sum.

The weighted average filtering process effectively reduces noise in the image by smoothing out variations caused by random fluctuations. The choice of the filter mask and its size directly impact the filtering results. Smaller filter sizes preserve finer details but may not eliminate as much noise, while larger filter

sizes provide stronger noise reduction but may blur important features. Also, the weight's spatial distribution determines the filtering effects. If the distribution is uniform or flat spatially, then it smooths more, otherwise if the distribution has a sharp peak, then smooth less.

Despite its effectiveness in noise reduction, weighted average filtering has limitations. It can not perform well in scenarios where there are both sharp and weak edges or boundaries in the image, as it treats both edges equally. Therefore, it is crucial to choose the parameters, like the appropriate filter mask and size, based on the characteristics of the image and the desired outcome.

1.1.2 Edge-aware/ Edge preserving filtering

Initial developments in edge preserving image filtering techniques [106, 130] were mainly developed on the assumptions that prominent edges are with comparatively high gradients than noises/textures. They employed the range/intensity difference or gradient information into weight designing function. This made the filtering edge or high gradient aware. Also these methods were applied a uniform operation with fixed parameter (like filtering window/mask size, kernel parameter) throughout the whole images. But images having insignificant textures/noises with high gradient values can not be smoothed out with such uniform operation. So most of the gradient based uniform edge preserving image filtering techniques fails for such kind of images. Therefore in later development adaptive window based edge preserving image filtering techniques were proposed in the later developments. But only the gradient based features are not sufficient for developing robust filtering technique for different types of images and for different types of applications also. That is why, instead of several good edge/structure preserving filtering techniques exist in the literature, still there is a scope to develop semantically significant feature extraction to develop semantic filtering techniques. In many applications, such as medical or satellite image analysis, edges are crucial features that must be

1.1. Image filtering

preserved sharply and without distortion during smoothing or denoising processes.

Initial edge-preserving filters are designed to automatically limit smoothing at structural edges, which are identified by high gradient magnitudes. A weighted average based premier non-linear technique is bilateral filter [130], that is initially designed for edge-preserving and noise reducing smoothing. It defines the weights by combining Gaussian distributions of both spatial and spectral variations such that the weights are inversely proportional to both the spatial distance and spectral difference (i.e the range difference or color difference or depth distance). This key idea take the crucial role in preserving sharp edges. The basic formulation of the bilateral filter is follows:

$$J_p = \frac{1}{W_p} \sum_{q \in \Omega_p} G_{\sigma_s}(\|q - p\|) G_{\sigma_r}(\|I_q - I_p\|) I_q. \quad (1.1)$$

Where I is the original and J is the corresponding filtered image, G_{σ_s} is the standard Gaussian function over spatial domain with standard deviation σ_s and G_{σ_r} is over range domain of σ_r respectively. It is a non-linear combination of spatial and range filters, where the spatial part smooths the images and the range part used to detect the edges not to be smoothed. In bilateral filtering smoothing and preserving edges is totally depends on the parameter σ_s and σ_r , respectively. Thus, a huge amount of empirical study is needed for different types of images to find the possible values of σ_s and σ_r to get best filtered results.

Anisotropic diffusion is also a premier technique used in image processing and computer vision for smoothing images while preserving and enhancing important structures, such as edges. Unlike isotropic diffusion, which smooths uniformly in all directions, anisotropic diffusion adapts the diffusion process based on local image characteristics. Based on the gradient magnitude of the image the diffusion coefficient is modulated in anisotropic diffusion. The basic idea is to allow diffusion to occur more along regions with weaker intensity gradients (smoother areas

) while limiting diffusion across regions with stronger intensity gradients (edges or boundaries). The preservation of edges and fine details in an image is elevated by this adaptive behavior.

Perona-Malik diffusion is another popular term used for anisotropic diffusion by its developer names, is become a widely utilised approach for noise removing while preserving significant image contents. It works similarly through the process of scale space creation, by generating a family of smoothed images based on a isotropic diffusion process with a increasing set parameters. Isotropic diffusion basically operates like a convolution of the image with a 2D isotropic Gaussian filter with a increasing width depending on the parameter. This transform the original image by a space-variant linear diffusion, which smooths uniformly in all directions. Anisotropic diffusion adapts the smoothing process based on the local image structure by controlling the diffusion process with a gradient-based function. Consequently, it become a space-variant non-linear transformation of the original image.

The original formulation in [106], is also termed as shape-adapted smoothing or coherence-enhancing diffusion. It simply generalized the usual diffusion equation, in which the constant scalar diffusion coefficient replaced with a function of pixels position. This is designed by a partial differential equations (PDEs) to estimate pixel-wise spatially varying diffusivities. It reduce smoothing at image edges so that preserve important image structures while smoothing out noise or textures. The image is iteratively updated according to the partial differential equation, which governs the diffusion process. The PDE is designed to reduce diffusion in regions with high gradient magnitudes (i.e., at edges) and allow more diffusion in relatively uniform areas. The result is an image with reduced noise and preserved edges, making anisotropic diffusion particularly useful for tasks such as edge detection, image segmentation, and feature extraction. The equation is designed as follows:

1.1. Image filtering

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial t} = \operatorname{div}(c(x, y, t)\nabla I) = \nabla c \cdot \nabla I + c(x, y, t)\Delta I \quad (1.2)$$

In this context, $\operatorname{div}(\)$ stands for the divergence operator, Δ is the *Laplacian*, ∇ for the *gradient*, and $c(x, y, t)$ represents the diffusion coefficient, which regulates the diffusion rate. Typically, this coefficient is taken as a function of the image gradient to maintain edge integrity in the image. In Perona and Malik [106] two functions are proposed as the diffusion coefficient:

$$c(\|\nabla I\|) = e^{-(\|\nabla I\|/K)^2} \text{ and}$$

$$c(\|\nabla I\|) = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{\|\nabla I\|}{K}\right)^2} \text{ The constant } K \text{ determines the sensitivity to}$$

edges and is typically selected either through experimentation or depending on the level of the noise in the image.

1.1.3 Mathematical morphology

Mathematical Morphology (MM) [122] proposes a theoretical framework and a set of methodologies for analyzing and manipulating geometric structures. It initially incorporates principles from set theory then lattice theory, topology and random functions. Although MM is primarily used for digital images, it is also applicable to the other spatial structures like surface meshes, solids, and graphs. MM introduces geometrical and topological concepts in both continuous and discrete spaces, including shape, size, geodesic distance, connectivity, and convexity. These concepts are essential to morphological image processing, that uses a series of operators to transform images based on these characteristics.

The basic morphological operators in digital image processing are— dilation, erosion, opening, and closing—play a pivotal role. In contrast to weighted

average filtering, morphological operator does not introduce new pixel values during the filtering process. Morphological operators integrate image objects with their background/foreground, determined by structuring elements. Notably, it excels in preserving the fundamental shape of image objects while eliminating spurious or extended edges.

Initially designed for binary images, MM has further evolved to operate on grayscale images or functions. The theoretical foundation of MM is now established by the generalization of it to complete lattices. Morphological filters are notable for preserving object structures without depending on statistical measures, making MM a valuable tool in many applications of image analysis and processing. However, the structuring element's size and shape highly determines the effectiveness of MM.

1.1.3.1 Morphological filter

Morphological filters are image processing techniques that operate on the structure, or morphology, of an image. Computer vision and image processing widely use it to enhance or suppress certain features of an image. These filters are based on mathematical morphology, which deals with the shape and structure of objects. Dilation and erosion are two fundamental operations in morphological filtering. In an image, expansion of the objects boundaries is accomplished through dilation, while erosion involves shrinking them. These operations are performed using a structuring element, which is a small, predefined pattern or shape to determine the neighbor window. The structuring element is moved through each pixel of the image, and the designed interaction determines the result of the morphological operation.

The operational foundation of mathematical morphology relies on the rank-ordering principle. The fundamental operations, dilation and erosion, filter an image by substituting the center pixel of a predefined neighboring region known

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as the structuring element (SE) with the local maximum and minimum values, respectively. Additional operations like opening and closing are constructed by sequentially applying alternating dilation and erosion. These operations intuitively eliminate impulse noises smaller than the structural element without distorting the fundamental shape of the objects. In essence, mathematical morphology utilizes rank-based comparisons within the structuring element to modify and analyze the structure of objects in an image.

Dilation (δ) : Dilation is designed to expand the brighter objects in an image. It is achieved by simply placing the structuring element at each pixel and setting the considered pixel value in the filtered image to the maximum pixel value within the structuring element. This operation is useful for tasks such as joining broken parts of an object, filling in gaps, and making objects more prominent.

Erosion (ε): Erosion, on the other hand, is used to shrink the brighter objects. It involves placing the structuring element at each pixel and setting the considered pixel in the filtered image to the minimum pixel value within the structuring element. Erosion is helpful in tasks like separating objects that are close to each other, removing small details, and smoothing and sharpening object boundaries.

Opening and closing are two other basic compound operations that combine dilation and erosion.

Opening ($\delta(\varepsilon)$): It perform an erosion operation following to a dilation. This helps in removing small objects and fine details.

Closing ($\varepsilon(\delta)$): It involves applying an erosion operation prior to a dilation. Closing is effective in closing small gaps and connecting nearby objects.

Morphological filters are utilized in a variety of image processing tasks, including noise reduction, edge detection, feature extraction and image segmentation. These are particularly useful in scenarios where the object shapes and sizes

in the image are critical for analysis.

It's worth noting that the selection of the structuring element is crucial for the effectiveness of morphological filtering. The structuring element's size and shape need to be selected by analysing the attributes of the objects in the input image and the desired outcome of the filtering operation.

Morphological gradient ($\delta - \varepsilon$): Morphological gradient is a morphological operation used in image processing to highlight the boundaries or edges of objects within an image. It is particularly useful for emphasizing transitions between regions of different intensity or texture. The morphological gradient is obtained by computing the difference of the dilation to erosion of an image. It is a powerful tool in image processing, and its application can contribute to various tasks, including image analysis, computer vision, and pattern recognition. It provides a way to enhance and emphasize the edges or transitions in an image, making it valuable for feature extraction and subsequent processing steps.

Morphological texture filtering ($\delta(\varepsilon) + \varepsilon(\delta)$)/2: Morphological texture filtering is a technique used in image processing to analyze and enhance texture information within an image using morphological operations. Morphological operations involve the manipulation of image structures based on the shape and gray scale characteristic of the elements in the image. The opening operator can remove the darker noises/textures and the closing operator can remove the brighter noises and textures. Hence, the combination of these two reduces the sharp oscillation of noises and textures while structural edges remain as they are. The average of opening and closing is thus useful as an initial texture structure discriminator.

In this research work, morphological filters are exploited to improve the discrimination between structural edges and textural regions of the image for further semantic texture structure decomposition.

1.1.4 Median filter

A median filter [7, 60, 64] in signal processing and digital image processing is a non-linear filtering technique applied to reduce noise and remove outliers. Unlike linear filters, such as mean or Gaussian filters, that compute the average or weighted average of pixel values of neighbor pixels, in median filter the median value of the neighbor pixels is computed and replace the centre pixel by it. The median filter operates by sliding a window (also known as a kernel or mask) over the image, and for each position, the pixel value at that position is replaced by the median value of the pixels within the window. The size of the window determines the neighboring pixels considered for computing the median. The key advantage of the median filter is its ability to effectively reduce impulse noise, also known as salt-and-pepper noise, which are the random white and black pixels occur in an image. Also median filter is particularly effective in scenarios where preserving edges and fine details is crucial because it does not compute a weighted average that can blur these features. However, it may not be as effective in reducing certain types of noise, such as Gaussian noise. Unlike weighted average filtering neighbor window size is the only key parameter of it.

It is a popular rank order filter that takes the median value of the defined neighbouring pixels and replaces it to considered centre pixel. As the median value always divides the distribution into equal two parts in the same number of counts, it is naturally not sensitive to the impulse noise/outliers. Unlike the weighted average filters, median filter always takes a pixel value as a substitute, from the existing values within the window if the pixel numbers in the window is odd. If the neighbour pixels follow a positively skewed histogram then the median will be less than the mean. On the other hand, for a negatively skewed histogram the median will be greater than the mean. For a symmetric/near-symmetric histogram (i.e., skewness is near to zero) the median will be equal to or closer to the mean value.

In summary, the median filter is an invaluable tool in digital image processing, known for its ability to effectively reduce impulse noise while preserving the integrity of edges and fine details. This makes it indispensable for applications where maintaining image quality through noise reduction is critical. It merges the high intensity textures to its low intensity background if the local distribution is positively skewed and the low intensity texture to its high intensity foreground if the distribution is negatively skewed. But taking traditional fixed size square window can face the similar problem that in average filtering, that it depend on the window size. Hence, an approach of adaptive window (in size or shape or both) consideration can made median filtering best for edge preserving filtering. In our research work, this intuitive property of the adaptive median filter is exploited to develop a robust semantic edge preserving smoothing technique. Where the adaptive (in size and shape both) windows are considered differently for different pixels (edge and non edge pixels) such that edges are preserved semantically while removing noises and textures.

1.1.5 Non-Local approaches in image filtering

Non-local approaches to image filtering, such as Non-Local Means (NLM), patch-based filtering, and dictionary-based methods, have gained significant attention due to their effectiveness in preserving structural and textural image content. These methods rely on the self-similarity property in images, leveraging repeated patterns and textures for more accurate noise suppression. Non-local means (NLM) introduced by Buades, Coll, and Morel [21], exploits the idea that pixels with similar neighborhoods (patches) within an image likely have similar intensities. NLM calculates the weighted average of similar patches found across the entire image, providing an effective noise reduction while preserving fine details. This method is particularly beneficial for natural images with repetitive textures and structures. Variants of NLM include adaptive patch sizes and faster

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implementations to reduce computational complexity, as presented by Mahmoudi and Sapiro [97] and Kervrann and Boulanger [74]. These enhancements improve performance, making NLM viable for high-resolution images.

Patch based filtering: Patch-based filtering methods, like BM3D (Block-Matching and 3D filtering), introduced by Dabov [34], extend the NLM concept by grouping similar patches and processing them in a 3D transform domain. BM3D’s collaborative filtering leverages the self-similarity of patches within an image to achieve state-of-the-art denoising performance, particularly effective for both Gaussian and other types of noise. BM3D has proven especially useful in preserving textures, as it groups similar patches into 3D arrays and applies a joint filter, which averages the noise across the patches. This technique is widely adopted for its robustness in maintaining both fine textures and large-scale structures in the image.

Dictionary based sparse representation methods: Dictionary-based denoising methods aim to represent image patches as sparse linear combinations of basis elements (atoms) in a dictionary, effectively separating noise from signal. Aharon [1] introduced the K-SVD (K-means Singular Value Decomposition) algorithm, which trains dictionaries specific to image patches. By encoding patches sparsely, this method removes noise while retaining essential structures. Dictionary learning has become particularly influential for applications requiring fine detail preservation, such as medical and microscopic imaging [43]. Further advancements include adaptive dictionaries that are tuned for specific types of noise and structures in images, leading to superior denoising outcomes.

Non-local means with deep learning: Recent advances integrate non-local methods with deep learning, where CNNs enhance patch similarity matching. For example, [156] used deep residual learning to improve upon dictionary-based methods by training models on large datasets, achieving noise reduction while retaining non-local structural information. Applications in Complex Noise: These

hybrid approaches address limitations in complex noise scenarios where traditional patch-based methods might struggle, making them well-suited for applications like low-light photography and hyperspectral imaging.

Non-local approaches such as NLM, BM3D, and dictionary-based filtering have become cornerstones in image denoising literature due to their capability to preserve textures and structural details. By leveraging self-similarity, these methods offer robust noise reduction while retaining critical image features, proving essential for both natural and medical imaging applications.

1.1.6 Structure preserving filtering

Over the past two decades, advancements have progressed from gradient-based edge-preserving filtering and swift to adaptive window-based edge-preserving filtering and structure preserving filtering based on region statistics. The objective of structure preserving filtering extends beyond the preservation of individual edges or lines; it aims to preserve meaningful structures while eliminating insignificant textures. Notably, anisotropic diffusion [106] and bilateral filters [130] solely rely on directional (horizontal and vertical) image gradients to depict edges or textures. But in later developments for structure preserving filtering, various patch-based statistical metrics, including region covariance, total variation, relative total variation (RTV), modified RTV, and context features based on local max-min, are employed as texture descriptors, utilizing measures of directional gradients of the first and second order. In equation 1.3, showing that in place of direct gradient in equation 1.1, similarity or dissimilarity measure of region features (like the covariance C_p and C_q) of the predefined region around center pixel p and neighboring pixels q , respectively adopted as the edge or texture descriptor between p and q . However, these methods are also contingent on three parameters: variance σ of kernel function, region patch size, and neighbor filtering window size.

$$J_p = \frac{1}{W_p} \sum_{q \in \Omega_p} G_\sigma(\|C_q - C_p\|) I_q. \quad (1.3)$$

1.1.7 Applications

Image filtering plays a fundamental role in improving visual quality, enhancing features, and reducing noise, which are essential for various applications across image denoising, enhancement, tone mapping, and hyperspectral image classification. By selecting and applying the appropriate filters, these processes can meet unique requirements and improve accuracy, visual clarity, and interpretability of images.

1.1.7.1 Image denoising

Image denoising is essential for reducing noise in images due to environmental factors or sensor limitations, with applications spanning medical imaging, astrophotography, and remote sensing. Key aspects of image filtering in denoising. Filters are selected based on the type of noise present. Gaussian filters are commonly used for images affected by Gaussian noise, while median filters are preferred for impulse noise, as they preserve edges while removing outliers [67].

Edge preserving filtering is a set of techniques in image processing that smooths or reduces noise in an image while preserving important edges. These filters are widely used in computer vision tasks like denoising, tone mapping, and non-photorealistic rendering. Filters like Bilateral filter, Anisotropic diffusion and non-local means based filters reduce noise while maintaining structural details, crucial for medical images where clear boundaries are essential [19]. Frequency-based filters are a class of image processing techniques that operate in the frequency domain. These filters analyze and manipulate the frequency components

of an image, rather than directly working on the pixel intensities in the spatial domain. The frequency domain is obtained by transforming an image using a Fourier Transform, which decomposes the image into sinusoidal components of varying frequencies. Techniques like wavelet-based denoising filter images based on frequency content, efficiently separate noise from details and make it suitable for spatially varying noise types in satellite imaging [29].

Image denoising is essential for restoring clean images affected by various noise types, such as additive Gaussian noise, multiplicative speckle noise, or signal-dependent Poisson noise. Traditional approaches like mean and Gaussian filters [19], wavelet-based denoising [117], and adaptive filters like Lee and Frost [50] for multiplicative noise have shown effectiveness. For impulse noise, median and adaptive median filters are commonly used [18]. Advanced techniques such as Total Variation (TV) denoising [116], anisotropic diffusion [106], and Fourier domain filtering for periodic noise [58] enhance edge preservation. Signal-dependent noise like Poisson is handled using variance-stabilizing transforms [98] and hybrid methods [98]. Recently, deep learning approaches, including CNNs like DnCNN [157] and [81], have outperformed traditional methods in adaptability and performance, making them suitable for complex noise patterns. Hybrid methods combining spatial and frequency-domain techniques [108] further improve denoising results, reflecting a shift towards more adaptive and learning-based solutions.

1.1.7.2 Image enhancement and tone mapping

Image enhancement improves the perceptibility of features in images, making it easier for observers to analyze details. Applications include digital photography, medical imaging, and surveillance. Image filtering aspects for enhancement include several approaches. Contrast enhancement filters like histogram equalization redistribute intensity values by improving contrast. They are widely used in satellite and medical imaging for enhanced visibility of critical features [58]. Edge enhanc-

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ing filters like Unsharp masking and high-pass filters enhance edges by amplifying high-frequency details, which is especially useful in facial recognition and surveillance imaging [2]. Adaptive filters modify their parameters based on local image characteristics, providing context-sensitive enhancement and preserving significant details, which is useful in medical imaging to improve visibility of tissue structures [120].

Tone mapping adapts high dynamic range (HDR) images for standard displays, balancing brightness levels while preserving details across shadows and highlights. This is vital in computer graphics, photography, and HDR visualization. Key aspects of filtering in tone mapping include global tone mapping filters those apply a uniform adjustment across the entire image, ideal for scenes with even lighting but often lacking in detailed balance for scenes with wide dynamic range [113]. Local tone mapping filters use local operators adjust tones based on local neighborhood characteristics, preserving spatial details across brightness variations, essential in HDR photography where shadow and highlight details are both important [38]. Gradient domain filters applied in the gradient domain enhance detail consistency and reduce halos around high-contrast edges, providing high-quality visual results in professional photography and CGI [48].

1.1.7.3 Classification of hyperspectral images

Hyperspectral imaging captures extensive spectral data, enabling detailed classification of materials and objects in fields like agriculture, environmental monitoring, and mineral exploration. Filtering aspects important in hyperspectral classification include spatial filters for noise reduction which is a widely used technique for denoising hyperspectral images (HSI) by leveraging spatial information from neighboring pixels to suppress noise while preserving essential details. Since HSI data is rich in spectral and spatial information, effective denoising is crucial to improve the accuracy of subsequent analyses, such as classification, segmentation,

and target detection. Spectral filters are also applied in noise reduction in hyperspectral images which often suffer from noise due to atmospheric interference. Filters like spectral smoothing and matched filtering are used to enhance signal quality and extract relevant spectral features [153]. Spatial spectral convolutional filters are recently developed using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) that combine spatial and spectral filtering have enhanced hyperspectral classification accuracy, particularly useful in agricultural mapping and geological surveys [152].

1.1.7.4 Semantic segmentation of natural images

Semantic segmentation [6, 11, 26, 68, 73, 77, 100, 151] is a pivotal computer vision task that assigns class labels to each pixel in an image, enabling applications like autonomous driving, medical imaging, and satellite analysis. One of its key challenges is achieving precise boundary delineation and reducing noise in segmentation maps. Filtering techniques, particularly edge-aware filters such as bilateral and guided filters, play a critical role in addressing these issues. These filters are used both in preprocessing, where they smooth noisy inputs while preserving edges, and in postprocessing, where they refine segmentation outputs to align boundaries with actual object edges. Additionally, advanced methods like Conditional Random Fields (CRFs) and edge-preserving neural architectures integrate filtering principles to enhance segmentation accuracy. By ensuring noise suppression, boundary precision, and feature enhancement, filtering significantly elevates the reliability and quality of semantic segmentation in complex real-world scenarios.

1.2 Challenges

Despite significant advancements towards structure preserving filtering techniques, many of them grapple with the challenge of blurring the original image, leading

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to information loss and weakening the edges, as they are unable to consider semantic information while smoothing.

Blurring and information losses: Image filtering is all about to update the pixel values from the neighbour information to remove the insignificant details or noises. To do so filtering process blur the overall image and causes information losses. So one of the primary challenge to develop an effective filtering technique is to preserve the significant objects properly. The ultimate aim of image filtering is to remove noises while preserving significant objects with minimal information loss. The recent researches focus on this by incorporating 1) textural features, 2) structural edge features or 3) both textural and structural semantic feature.

Semantically detect significant structures: One of the most challenging tasks in image filtering is to differentiate between significant objects/structures to be preserved and noises/textures to be removed. Most of the existing approaches directly rely on gradient or range difference information for this task. Only gradient information can not differentiate texture and structure. But incorporating semantic information, or semantically defining significant objects is the most crucial and challenging task. In this research some novel semantic features have been proposed to develop semantic-aware structure preserving filtering techniques.

Parameter sensitivity: Another important problem of most of the existing filtering techniques is their parameters dependency or sensitivity. The existing techniques have several parameters that need to be wisely set manually within a predefined continuous interval to get the best results for different images. This parameters dependency make them inappropriate for applying in different applications such as classification, segmentation, denoising, etc. This research has focused on this issue and developed some effective filtering techniques which are less parameters sensitive in a way such that only need to select parameters values from few discrete options.

1.2.1 Preservation of significant structures

Due to wide varieties of images used for different applications, preservation of significant structures/edges during image filtering is become very challenging. The term significant structure is vague in sense. For different images used in different type of applications it may differ in sense. Significant object/structure may be in the sense of human visual perception or in the purpose of some particular applications perspective. So, the filtering technique has to define generalized robust features for preservation of significant structures.

1.2.1.1 Semantic features for preserving significant structures

There are several techniques developed for structure/edge preserving image filtering. Most of them either considered intensity difference or image gradients or some statistical measure for structure/edge detection during smoothing process. But there are many cases in which only image gradient or gradient based features can not differentiate significant structures/edges and insignificant textures/noises. Here the term significant can be in some semantical sense of human visual perception or some scientific image analysis and applications perspective. During filtering for different types of images, semantically recognise the significant structures/edges to be preserved and insignificant textures/noises to be removed is a challenging and much needed work. Consideration of appropriate semantic features in filtering process can significantly improve the quality of the filtered image.

1.2.1.2 Semantic-aware filtering

Edge-preserving image filtering aims to smooth an image while maintaining its edges. Recently, several techniques have been developed to differentiate between structures and textures at varying scales. These techniques typically use a user-

selected scale measurement to control texture smoothing. However, natural images often contain objects of varying sizes, making it difficult to describe them with a single scale measurement. Additionally, edge and contour detection, which is closely related to edge-preserving filtering, has seen significant advancements. Despite this progress, many state-of-the-art filtering techniques rely heavily on image gradients for edge detection and are dependent on multiple parameters. This limitation has led us to propose the use of semantic-aware edge features to better distinguish between textural and structural edges.

In this research work we have developed some efficient semantic-aware structure preserving image filtering techniques and tested those in realm of few applications of computer graphics like image denoising, image enhancement, tone mapping as well as in image classification.

1.3 Evolution and developments of image filtering techniques

Linear filters are the oldest image filtering techniques implemented with the help of a convolution mask. Due to their simplicity and low computational cost, traditional linear filtering techniques like mean filtering, box filtering, Gaussian filtering [58, 67] are still relevant for many image processing applications. One of the primary disadvantages of linear filters is that during filtering they destroyed lines, edges, and other fine details of the image. To reduce this, last three decade a variety of non-linear filters have been developed [27, 32, 42, 55, 61, 65, 82]. The main aim of all these developments is to preserve the image details and local geometries in much better way, while removing the undesired textures from the images.

In early 1990's an important concept anisotropic diffusion is introduced for non-linear filtering [106]. It exploits Partial Differential Equations (PDE) to estimate pixel wise spatially varying diffusivity from image gradients. These

diffusivity prevent excessive smoothing at image edges, thereby preserving important image structures while effectively reducing noise. The other popular edge preserving filtering techniques based on PDE that proposed in the literature are non-linear isotropic (spatial) diffusion [137], anisotropic (directional) diffusion [17], level set methods [99], total variation methods ([24, 115]) *etc.*

Although the above PDE based filtering methods show their robustness to preserve edges, they are implemented through an iterative process, which can often be slow and may pose challenges related to stability and efficiency. As an alternative bilateral filter was first introduced by [130] based on the works [8, 124], and later it improved in [42]. Bilateral filter (BF) is a simple nonlinear filtering approach, that combines domain and range considerations for filtering. The spatial domain and the range function controls the smoothing and edge preserving effects, respectively. Because of its simplicity and effectiveness, bilateral filtering has garnered significant attention from researchers and has been successfully applied to various computational photography applications. In the image processing literature, several modifications of it has also been developed to handle the drawbacks of the existing methods.

Although bilateral filters are non-iterative in nature, their brute force (direct) implementation is very slow. The computational complexity of such brute-force implementation is $O(Nr^2)$ (N is pixel numbers in the image), which is eventually become high when the radius r of kernel is large. Therefore, several adaptive techniques [27, 28, 49, 55, 104, 107, 134, 146, 154] have been developed to make computationally faster the bilateral filters using different kernel implementation techniques and data structures. However, achieving fast or real-time implementation remains a challenging problem. To address this challenge, a new filtering approach called guided filtering ([63]) was introduced. This method effectively preserves edges while denoising by taking into account the content of a guidance image. One advantage of the guided filter compared to the bilateral

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filter is its $O(N)$ time complexity, ensuring efficient implementation without being dependent on the kernel radius r . A filtering method that used self-similarity and non-locality characteristics of images is proposed in [19]. A few extension of this non-local filtering are presented in [33], [96]. Manifold learning based filtering for high dimensional image and video processing are found in [53–55] which make the BF implementation faster.

One of the limitation of the above different approaches of BF techniques is that they directly rely on image gradient for describing edge/structure, which is prone to fail to preserve the different type of edges properly or create false edges. To address this issue, local statistical measure based adaptive and iterative filtering models draw more attention in the last decade. These filtering techniques introduced the concept of texture-structure decomposition. Structure-preserving texture filtering is an area of ongoing development with diverse applications in computational photography and image analysis. This operation decomposes an image into its prominent structures and fine-scale details, facilitating various image manipulations such as tone mapping, detail enhancement, visual abstraction, scene understanding, and more. The large number of filtering methods proposed in the literature are mainly divided into four categories: average based [63, 145], optimization based [22, 135, 138, 139], rank order based [10, 94] and patch based [32, 72, 129]. The filtering methods in the first two are particularly effective for removing noise and fine-scale geometric details. For example, bilateral filter [5, 130], weighted least square filter [47, 91, 135], L0 smoothing [128, 138], and the methods using anisotropic diffusion [103, 106, 143] are successfully used to filter low-contrast noise but failed to smooth high-contrast noises or textures. Rank order based filtering techniques are capable of filtering high-contrast noises or textures using a local histogram where the color/intensity of each pixel is replaced by some order ranked value (like the maximum, minimum, median, etc) of the neighbouring pixels. Thus, they preserve the original contrast in the filtered image. Texture filtering [89, 127, 158] is all about removing the insignificant regular or irregular

patterns (textures) from the filtered image while preserving the significant structures or objects of the image. Since the measure of the visual patterns of regular or irregular textures is not considered by the filtering methods of the first three categories, they are not that effective in texture filtering. Whereas, patch based filters are capable of considering the measurements of visual patterns. Thus, more suitable for texture filtering. Generally, visual patterns are measured with axis-aligned patches or by computing the patch based statistical measures. There are patch based techniques presented in [15, 20] performed filtering by applying some non-local measurements, but the textural measurements are not taken into consideration. As a result, these methods are less effective for texture filtering. The spatial relationship, frequency, and symmetry/asymmetry of the textural pattern of regular or near-regular shapes are taken into consideration for texture identification and filtering is presented in [62, 93]. However, for developing a robust texture filtering technique, filtering out arbitrary textures of both regular or irregular shapes/patterns is important. Though, finding out the insignificant irregular textures and removing them in a semantic sense is always a challenging task. In this regard, Rudin et al. [115] have effectively enforced total variation (TV) regularization constraints to preserve large-scale edges. In order to further improve the texture-structure separation based on TV, Xu et al. [139] introduced relative total variation (RTV). Both the methods are developed based on the concept of the aggregation of signed gradient values within a local window/patch often produces a larger absolute value for structural edges than its textural counterpart. As the texture regions usually produce inconsistent gradients within a local window, the gradient measure is used to differentiate textural and structural edges. However, such a measure may misidentify small structural edges as textures. Moreover, the use of larger neighbouring windows overlapping different regions may result in very similar RTV values for neighbouring pixels of different regions. As a result, these methods are prone to produce over-smooth structural edges. In [72], Karacan et al. introduced the region co-variance descriptor as a textural measurement that

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uses second-order statistics extracted from the fixed size patches. Although this descriptor performs better separation between texture and structure, it fails to avoid the over-blur effect at the structural edges, as the overlap patches near an edge always share almost similar region co-variances.

To mitigate this problem, some later techniques have tried to optimize the position of patches [32] or the size of patches [150]. For computing the textural measure, Cho et al. [32] assumed that a pixel may not be always well represented by the patch centered on it. Finding out the nearby patch which is least likely to contain structural edges can resolve the patch overlapping issue. Thus, they have proposed a patch shifting technique to avoid the neighboring window overlapping problem, which has improved the effectiveness of the textural measures. The main challenge in this technique is to choose an effective patch size and its position. To address this issue [140] introduced a concept of edge aware dynamic shape and size based filtering approach. In [69] a scale aware structure preserving filtering mechanism is proposed by using directional Relative Total Variation (dRTV) measure. Some graph based minimum spanning tree/shortest path filtering concept was presented in [10, 37, 101]. There is another kind of filtering techniques exist in the literature based on mathematical morphology. Some developments of adaptive structure preserving morphological filtering was proposed by several researchers [59, 80, 82, 83]. They introduced the concept of adaptive morphological filtering and morphological amoebas, which dynamically define structuring elements size and shape for each pixel. [4] proposed a morphological bilateral filtering approach by defining a spatially-variant bilateral structuring function, where the adaptive structuring elements are obtained by taking thresholds on the bilateral functions. Connected component filtering, an advanced version of morphological filtering found in [16, 23, 35, 39, 119, 142] applied for hyper-spectral image denoising. The semantic edge-aware structure preserving filtering concept was introduced in [84, 145, 149]. In [145] a learning-based edge-preserving filtering technique is presented. In [87], to avoid over-blurring smaller structural edges, a

smaller patch (shrink version of the original patch) is considered for the pixels located at the nearby structural edges, while a larger patch (original patch) is used for the pixels representing the texture regions. Since the technique is only able to shrink the original patches and is unable to expand them, it prevents the original patches from being as large as needed. Thus, filtering large-scale textures is not efficiently done by this method. For multiple scaled texture smoothing, a scale-aware method is presented in [69]. Depending on the patch-based statistics, this method finds an optimal per-pixel adaptive smoothing scale for texture filtering. It used RTV based statistics for the textural measure. Because of the over-blurring issue with RTV, this method may fail to estimate the scales of textures properly. As a result, large-scale texture filtering may not be efficiently performed by this method. As the scale of the textures is related to the gradients, Lee et al. [79] proposed an adaptive gradient smoothing method by introducing the interval gradient measure. An adaptive relative total variation filter (ARTVF) is proposed in [149]. Since the estimation of the scales of textures depends on the statistics of gradients, the method is effective when the scales of the textures are similar. The textures with large, varying texels are not properly handled by this method, as the statistics of gradients also change drastically. So, the main challenge for developing a robust structure preserving filtering technique lies in handling varying scales of textural patterns.

To address this, some recent developments have proposed dynamic shape adaptive window generation by taking into consideration the linear characteristics of the structural edges [88, 94, 140]. They approximate the linearity of the structural edges by local gradient directions. As the structural edges are not always axis-aligned, approximating the linearity of the edges locally is not an easy task. There are some studies directed towards the development of edge-aware filters [25, 54, 145, 149, 155, 160]. Some of these methods define an edge-aware adaptive window for filtering depending on a prior edge-map generated by introducing modified edge features or using existing edge detection techniques. As the gener-

ation of a proper edge-map is a challenging and developing task, semantic-aware filtering has undergone more exploration in recent research.

Thus more recent studies are focusing on the development of semantic edge-aware filtering techniques [25, 76, 90, 95, 109, 111, 145, 147, 149, 159, 160]. These techniques proposed structural-edge feature or edge-aware textural features. [54] proposed edge-aware filtering by reducing the dimension of the RGB image. Edge detection techniques are used for developing learning-based edge-aware filtering in [145, 149]. An artificial neural network (ANN) is trained for edge-aware smoothing in [95, 159] and [75, 76] used a convolution neural network (CNN) based framework to exploit deep variational prior for the same task. An edge-aware filtering by combining bilateral filter and weighted least square is presented in [90]. [25] proposed an optimization framework for filtering by combining edge detection and L_0 gradient minimization recursively. [147] proposed a novel soft clustering algorithm using a restricted Gaussian mixture model for the same. Although, these edge-aware filtering techniques provided satisfactory results even for varying scale irregular textures, they have multiple parameters and the filtering result is very much dependent on the values of these parameters set manually. In this research, we proposed a novel edge-aware filtering method that provides better filtering results for a wide variety of images with minimum fine-tune of its parameters. The aim of the present work is to develop some semantic edge-aware structure preserving filtering techniques which explore semantic information that has not been exploited earlier.

1.4 Methodologies/approaches

Recent developments in bilateral filtering techniques have successfully used regional statistical features to describe regular or irregular textures in the image. Although the statistical features are robust to distinguish different structures present on the image, they cannot exploit the geometric features of the structures. As a

Figure 1-2: Proposed framework

result these features are very much parameter sensitive. On the other hand, morphological filters intuitively preserve the different shapes of the structures (objects). But the filtering results are dependent on the considered structure element or threshold value. Moreover, in the literature it is found that median filter provides excellent results when the size of the dynamic window of the median filter are chosen properly. Thus, developing filtering technique by exploiting both, patch-based region statistics and morphological filters to define adaptive window of the median filter could solve some critical issues present in filtering techniques. Unfortunately, such a filtering technique is seldom presented in the image processing literature. In this thesis, our main objective is to develop few robust structure preserving filtering techniques that exploit semantic information of the image by using region-based statistics and/or morphological filters for defining the adaptive

dynamic window of the median filter with minimal fine tune of the parameters. The major steps of this approach are as follows:

Propose semantic features for texture-structure decomposition- In recent research, there has been an introduction of a concept termed semantic-aware structure preserving filtering. While the definition of semantic-aware structure preserving filtering remains somewhat ambiguous due to the vagueness of the term “ semantic-aware ”, its essence lies in the identification of significant objects. Unlike traditional methods that primarily detect individual edges based on sharp intensity differences, semantic-aware filtering focuses on recognizing structures in a meaningful manner, whether to preserve or remove them. The challenge lies in defining what constitutes semantically meaningful structures within an image. In our work, we have proposed few novel semantic features for addressing this challenge. First, we have employed morphological gradient distribution to define semantic feature. Second, we have utilized the Jensen-Shannon divergence (JSD) for the same. Third both, morphological gradient distribution and JSD are exploited to define robust semantic features for texture-structure decomposition. Moreover, to generate such semantic features our aim is to define less number of parameters which required minimal fine tune.

Semantic-aware edge-map generation- Once the semantic features of the pixels are obtained, a semantic-aware edge-map of the input image is generated by using these features. Depending on the semantic features different algorithms are proposed to generate the edge-map of the input image. The main focus of these algorithm is to preserve the edges of the significant objects and remove the edges of the insignificant objects or textures.

Adaptive dynamic window for median filter- After generation of semantic edge-map of the input image, a novel technique needs to be proposed to define the dynamic window of the median filter with help of the generated semantic edge-map. To develop such technique care should be taken so that the proposed

algorithm either define its parameters automatically or less sensitive to its parameters. Figure 1-2 shows the framework of our approaches.

1.5 Experimental validation

To evaluate the effectiveness of our developed filtering techniques the common approach is to compare the filtered image and its zoomed parts of different structural and textural areas by human visual perception. As well as the quality of the filtered image can be assessed by some standard image quality measurement index (IQA). For image classification problem, the classification results is used to validate the effectiveness of our filtering technique.

Visual perception:- The common way of assessing filtered image quality subjectively is human visual perception based. Specially for structure preserving image filtering techniques need to check how well the filtered images preserving significant objects' structure while removing textural fine scale details. As the term significant is depends on manual observation or some specific applications aspect, visual perception is a useful way to validate it.

IQA:- IQA stands for Image Quality Assessment, which is a field of study and a set of techniques used to measure and evaluate the perceived quality of images. The goal of IQA is to develop metrics that can objectively quantify the degree of distortion or degradation in an image compared to a reference or original image. This is particularly essential in numerous applications such as image compression, transmission, and processing, where maintaining high visual quality is crucial. Common metrics used in IQA include Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), among others are the reference based measure, i.e it measure the filtered image quality with respect the the original input image. IQA techniques play a significant role in optimizing and validating image processing algorithms

1.5. Experimental validation

and systems. There are other IQAs like perceptual based image quality evaluator (PIQE) or naturalness image quality evaluator (NIQE) which are non-reference based.

HSI classification:- Hyperspectral Image (HSI) classification is the process of categorizing different materials or land cover types within an image captured by a hyperspectral sensor. Unlike traditional images that have three bands (RGB), hyperspectral images have numerous bands, each capturing information across a specific wavelength range. HSI classification entails assigning each pixel in the image to a specific class or category based on its spectral and spatial characteristics. The classifiers such as Neural network, K-nearest neighbours, support vector machine (SVM) and random forest (RF) are widely used for HSI classification. Evaluations of the performance of the classification was done by using validation data that was not used during training. Common metrics include overall accuracy (OA), average accuracy (AA), kappa coefficient (κ) obtained from confusion matrix are used to measure the classification performance. In this thesis the effectiveness of the proposed filtering techniques for incorporating better spatial information are assessed by using such metrics.

1.5.1 Performance measure

To assess the effectiveness of our developed filtering techniques in this thesis, the quality of the filtered image is assessed by visual perception as well as with the help of some standard image quality measurement index. The conventional Image Quality Assessment (IQA) measures such as Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) and Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) are not useful for assessing the quality of the filter images produced by the structure preserving filtering techniques [140]. We used three subjective reference IQA metrics: Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) [136], Multi-scale SSIM (MSSIM), and Mutual Information (MI) [131] and one subjective no-reference metric: Perception Image Quality Evaluator (PIQE)

[132] for quantitative comparisons.

SSIM:- Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), is a metric used to quantify the similarity of two images. It is commonly employed in the field of image processing and computer vision to assess the perceived quality of an image. The SSIM index is designed to capture changes in structural information, luminance, and contrast that are perceptible to the human visual system. The SSIM value of two images x and y is computed as follow:

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + C_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + C_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2)}, \quad (1.4)$$

where μ_x , σ_x^2 and σ_{xy} represent the mean, variance of x and covariance of x, y , respectively. C_1 and C_2 are constants added to prevent instability when the denominators approach to zero. The SSIM index ranges from -1 to 1, with 1 signifying perfect similarity between the two images. A higher SSIM value implies a closer resemblance.

MSSIM:- Multi-Scale Structural Similarity Index (MSSIM) is an extension of the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) that takes into account information at multiple scales. It addresses limitations in SSIM, particularly its sensitivity to changes in scale and orientation. The MSSIM metric is designed to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of image quality across various resolutions. The formula for MSSIM involves averaging the SSIM values obtained at different scales as follow:

$$MSSIM(x, y) = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{i=1}^L SSIM_i(x, y) \quad (1.5)$$

MSSIM provides a more robust assessment of image quality because it considers structural similarities across a range of spatial frequencies. This is particularly

1.5. Experimental validation

useful when evaluating the impact of distortions or compression artifacts that may affect different scales differently. MSSIM is widely used in image quality assessment tasks, and it has become a standard metric in evaluating the performance of image and video compression algorithms. It offers a more nuanced and informative evaluation compared to traditional single-scale similarity metrics.

MI:- Mutual Information (MI) can serve as a metric for evaluating the quality of filtered images, especially in the context of computer vision and image processing. The basic idea is to measure the amount of information shared between the original and filtered images, where higher mutual information indicates better quality or similarity. In the case of filtered image quality assessment, the MI computed between the original image (X) and the filtered image (Y) can be computed as follows:

$$I(X, Y) = \sum_{x \in X} \sum_{y \in Y} P(x, y) \log\left(\frac{P(x, y)}{P(x)P(y)}\right) \quad (1.6)$$

Where the joint probability mass function of intensity values in the original and filtered images is $P(x, y)$. The marginal probability mass functions of intensity values in the original and filtered images, respectively are $P(x)$ and $P(y)$. The above formula essentially quantifies how well the intensity values in the original and filtered images are related. Higher mutual information suggests that the filtered image retains more information from the original image, indicating better quality. The computation of mutual information involves discretizing the intensity values, especially when dealing with continuous images. Additionally, the joint and marginal probabilities need to be estimated from the pixel intensity distributions. In practical terms, mutual information for filtered image with original image can serve the purpose of evaluating the effectiveness of different image filtering techniques, such as denoising filters or edge-preserving filters. It provides a quantitative measure of how well the filtered image preserves information with

respect to the original image.

PIQE:- PIQE stands for Perceptual Image Quality Evaluator. It is a metric used to assess the perceptual quality of images, aiming to mimic human perception of image quality. PIQE is designed to provide a numerical score that correlates with the perceived quality of an image. This metric is commonly used in the field of image and video processing for quality assessment. The PIQE algorithm is based on modeling the human visual system's sensitivity to various image distortions. It takes into account factors such as luminance, contrast, color, and spatial details. The goal is to evaluate the overall visual quality by considering multiple aspects that contribute to human perception. The output of PIQE is typically a single score that represents the quality of the image. A higher PIQE score generally corresponds to better perceptual quality. Conversely, lower scores indicate lower perceived quality or the presence of image distortions. The application of PIQE is relevant in scenarios where it's crucial to objectively measure the quality of processed or compressed images. This can include assessing the impact of compression algorithms, evaluating image enhancement techniques, or monitoring the quality of images in various imaging systems. It's worth noting that there are different versions or implementations of perceptual quality metrics, and the specific details of the PIQE metric may vary depending on the version being used. We have used the Matlab 21 inbuilt function.

1.5.2 Data sets

In this thesis we have proposed few semantic-aware structure preserving image filtering techniques. In order to establish the effectiveness of our developed filtering techniques several images are used which are made publicly available in different publications cited in the thesis and few internet sources like <http://www.cse.cuhk.edu.hk/~leojia/projects/texturesep/index.html>, <http://cg.postech.ac.kr/publications> and <https://eod-grss-ieee.com/dataset>.

1.6 Objectives

Developing an effective structure-preserving image filtering technique requires addressing three primary challenges: (i) minimizing image blurring and information loss, (ii) incorporating suitable semantic information for accurate texture-structure decomposition, and (iii) reducing dependency on adjustable parameters. Existing techniques in the literature rarely meet all three challenges simultaneously. This research aims to design robust structure-preserving image filtering techniques that overcome these challenges. To achieve this goal, four key objectives have been accomplished, marking significant advancements in the field of image filtering.

1. *To develop a semantic edge-aware median morpho-filtering technique:* According to the recent developments, the most challenging task of texture filtering is to filter out the irregular and varying scale texture while preserving the structural contents with minimum distortion. For better handling varying scale irregular textural patterns, in this objective we propose a novel semantic-aware structure preserving filtering technique. The technique, first, generates a semantic edge-map of the input image by analysing the skewness of global and local histograms of the morphological gradient image obtained from the input image. Then, with help of the generated semantic edge-map, a novel method is proposed to define edge-aware adaptive dynamic window of the median filter for filtering each pixel of the input image by excluding its neighbor pixels belonging to different textural or structural regions. Finally, the proposed median filter and a morphological filter iteratively applied to generate the filter image.

Although, the filtering technique proposed in the first objective produced satisfactory results for a wide varieties of input images, it has one critical parameter. To incorporate semantic information of a pixel for determining whether it is an edge or non-edge pixel, the skewness of the local histogram of gradient image constructed by considering a fixed size window is computed.

So, the semantic edge-map generated by the proposed technique is highly sensitive to the size of this window, which is varied from image to image. In the next two objectives our aim is to develop more parameter efficient semantic-aware filtering techniques.

2. *To develop a reduced parameter sensitive semantic edge-aware image filtering technique:* The effectiveness of edge-aware structure preserving filtering techniques is dependent on their ability to identify right structural edges. Since in most of the images structural and textural edges are confused with each other, only tonal and sharpness dissimilarity are inadequate to discriminate them. In this objective by exploiting Jensen-Shannon (JS) divergence, a set of novel semantic features are proposed to depict the pixels of the input image. These features are defined in such a way that incorporate semantic information of the pixel for determining whether it is a structural edge pixel or not. Projecting all the pixels into the feature space, the technique applied k-means clustering to generate a semantic-aware edge-map of the input image. Once the edge-map is obtained, an edge-aware adaptive median filter which is proposed in first objective is used to generate the filter image. The developed method outperforms for a wide variety of images with the minimal fine tune of its parameters.
3. *To develop another parameter efficient semantic edge-aware image filtering technique:* The aim of this objective to propose another parameter efficient semantic image filtering technique by exploiting both the semantic features proposed in objectives one and two. It generates an edge-map of the input image by exploiting semantic information in two phases. In the first phase, two novel features: i) the semantic gradient, and ii) the semantic skewness gradient, are utilised to generate the semantic gradient image (SGI) of considered input image. In the second phase, with the help of the generated SGI, the window size associated to each pixel of the input image is automatically defined to determine whether it is a structural edge or non-edge pixel

by exploiting JS divergence. Once the semantic edge-map is generated, an edge-aware adaptive median filter which is proposed in first objective is used to generate the filter image. Although the proposed technique required to define multiple windows, the sizes and shapes of most of these windows are either automatically defined or kept fixed, irrespective of the consider input images.

4. *To incorporate spatial information by exploiting proposed filtering techniques for hyperspectral image classification and semantic segmentation of natural images:* Structure preserving image filtering techniques differentiate structures and textures in the image by identifying textural and structural edges. The fundamental goal of such techniques is to eliminate noise and smooth the textures while causing the least amount of distortion to the structures of the objects on the image. The development of semantic-aware structure preserving filtering techniques, which leverage semantic information in the image to differentiate structures from textures, has been the subject of recent research. Even if the filter images produced by such sophisticated approaches provide richer spatial information, they are seldom used for HSI classification. The last objective of this thesis is to exploits our proposed filtering techniques to incorporate spatial information for spectral-spatial HSI classification and semantic segmentation of natural images.

1.7 Organization of the thesis

The thesis presents few novel semantic-aware structure preserving image filtering techniques and their applications. The structure of this thesis is as follows:

Chapter 1: It gives brief introduction of the thesis. Several image filtering techniques and their usefulness are discussed. The evolution of image filtering techniques with the challenges and setbacks are also presented here. The purpose

of thesis and the methodologies followed to developed different semantic-aware filtering techniques are presented. Finally, it lays down the objectives of the thesis.

Chapter 2: Presents a novel semantic-aware structure preserving median morpho-filtering technique for better handling varying scale irregular textural patterns. The technique, first, generates a semantic edge-map of the input image by analysing the skewness of global and local histograms of the morphological gradient image obtained from the input image. Then, with help of the generated semantic edge-map, a novel method is proposed to define edge-aware adaptive dynamic window of the median filter for filtering each pixel of the input image.

Chapter 3: Presents a parameter efficient novel semantic-aware structure preserving filtering technique. It exploits JS divergence to represent the pixels of the input image by a set of semantic features. Projecting all the pixels into the feature space, the technique applied k-means clustering to generate a semantic-aware edge-map of the input image.

Chapter 4: Presents another parameter efficient novel semantic-aware structure preserving filtering technique by exploiting both the semantic features proposed in Chapter 2 and Chapter 3.

Chapter 5: Describes a method that incorporate spatial information by exploiting one of the semantic-aware structure preserving filtering technique proposed in the above chapters for hyperspectral image classification and semantic segmentation of natural images.

Chapter 6: Drawn the concluding remarks of the thesis by summarizing the works done and also point out the lists of the possible further research in this area.

Chapter 2

Semantic-aware structure preserving median morpho-filtering

2.1 Introduction

Natural images typically contain meaningful or significant (structure), as well as irrelevant or insignificant (texture) visual information. Structure preserving image filtering is a key operation to derive the meaningful (semantic) information from the images, which have a variety of applications in different fields like medical imaging, document analysis, remote sensing image analysis, etc [13, 70, 85]. Recent research focuses on the development of techniques which identify semantically significant objects from regular or irregular textural patterns for filtering. In the literature such techniques that incorporate semantic information for automatic structure-texture separation is termed as semantic-aware filtering [25, 133, 141, 145, 149]. In the current chapter, we have proposed a robust semantic-aware structure preserving filtering technique. Our technique defines a novel method to obtain an edge-aware adaptive window of dynamic shape for filtering each pixel of the image by excluding its neighbour pixels belonging to different textural or structural regions. Fig:2-1 illustrates the importance of the

uses of adaptive dynamic shape windows in comparison to fixed shape windows for filtering. As shown in Fig:2-1(b), the small fixed shape window does not work well to filter out the large-scale textures. On the contrary, large window does not preserve edges properly (blur the edges) as illustrated in Fig:2-1(c) and Fig:2-1(f). Since larger windows are useful to identify large-scale textures and smaller ones are effective for both detection and preservation of smaller structural edges. Defining an appropriate dynamic window for filtering varying size textures or structures is very much important. In the proposed work this issue is addressed by defining edge-aware adaptive dynamic shape windows as depicted in Fig:2-1(g) and Fig:2-1(h). In our technique, first, a novel method is proposed to generate the semantic edge-map by computing the skewness of global and local morphological gradient histograms. Then, using the generated edge-map an edge-aware structure preserving adaptive median morpho-filter is designed. The edge-map generation followed by median morpho-filtering iteratively runs to generate the final filter image. Note that morphological filters generally preserve the larger structural shapes while removing the smaller irregular shapes. In contrast, median filter converges the pixel values into the background pixels with greater counts. Thus, the proposed median morpho-filter merges the narrow texture to its original background as well as preserves the significant structures. The experimental results demonstrate, unlike many current techniques, our filtering method successfully balances multiple conflicting objectives. It identifies and removes texture, preserves structural edges, protects subtle features such as corners, and avoids introducing artifacts and distortions from over-sharpening or over-blurring. The key participation of this work are:

- Proposes a texture-structure decomposition technique by analysing the morphological gradient histogram of the image.
- Proposes a semantic-aware median morpho-filter for texture smoothing while preserving the significant structures.

Figure 2-1: (a) Original image with simple structure. (b)(c) The filtered images obtained using smaller and larger static box windows. (d) Original image with complex structure. The filtered images and their zoomed portion obtained using (e)(f) static box window and (g)(h) proposed dynamic window.

The next part of this chapter is presented as details: Section 2.2 introduces briefly to morphological and median filters. The proposed technique is detailed in Section 2.3. Experimental findings are analyzed in Section 2.4, and finally, the conclusion of this work is presented in Section 2.5.

2.2 Morphological and median filters

Figure 2-2: (a) Original 1-dimensional signal and the corresponding filtered signal obtained by applying (b) Opening, (c) Closing, (d) $(\text{Opening} + \text{Closing})/2$, and (e) Median operations with a fixed SE of size 3 unit.

Our filtering technique exploits the properties of morphological and median filters [60, 121]. This section presents a concise overview of the two filtering techniques.

2.2.1 Morphological filter

It works on the rank ordering principle. The basic two operations dilation (δ) and erosion (ε) filter the image by replacing the center pixel of the predefined neighbour called structuring element (SE) with the local maximum and minimum value, respectively. The other operations such as opening ($\delta(\varepsilon)$) and closing ($\varepsilon(\delta)$) are designed by applying successive alternative operations of dilation and erosion. The very basic nature of these operations intuitively removes the impulse noises smaller in size than the neighbouring window (i.e SE) without affecting the basic shape of objects. Figure 2-2 displays the filtering outcomes obtained on a 1-dimensional signal by applying different morphological operations with a fixed SE of size 3 unit. In the proposed technique morphological filter is exploited to improve the discrimination between structural edges and textural regions of the image.

2.2.2 Median filter

It's a widely used rank order filter that substitutes each pixel with the median value of the defined neighbouring pixels. As the median value always divides the distribution into equal two parts in the same number of counts, it is naturally not sensitive to the impulse noise/outliers. Unlike the weighted average filters, a median filter always replaces the pixel value with a value that already exists within the window containing odd number of pixels. If the neighbour pixels follow a positively skewed distribution then the median will be less than the mean. On the other hand, for a negatively skewed distribution the median will be greater than the mean. For a symmetric/near-symmetric distribution (i.e., skewness is near to zero) the median will be equal to or closer to the mean value. Figure 2-2 (e) shows the filtering result obtained from Figure 2-2 (a) by applying median operation with a fixed window of size 3 unit. The median filter merges the high

2.3. Proposed technique [111]

intensity textures with its low intensity background if the local distribution is positively skewed and the low intensity texture with its high intensity foreground if the distribution is negatively skewed. In our proposed method, this intuitive property of the median filter is exploited to develop a robust edge preserving smoothing technique.

Figure 2-3: (a) Original image, its magnified part enclosed with yellow rectangle and the intensity values of the pixels on the red line. The filtering results obtained by applying (b) Opening, (c) Closing, and (d) $(\text{Opening} + \text{Closing}) / 2$.

2.3 Proposed technique [111]

The proposed filtering technique has two main tasks. First, it generates a binary edge-map by analysing the morphological gradient histogram of the image. Then, based on the generated edge-map, a semantic edge-aware median morpho-filtering technique is designed to generate the filtered image. The subsequent subsections provide a detailed explanation of the proposed filtering technique:

2.3.1 Image gradients for edge detection

In image processing, a traditional gradient represents the directional change in intensity or color within an image. Including the morphological gradient, there are several other traditional ways to generate gradients in images:

Sobel gradient: The Sobel operator uses convolution with specific filters to detect edges by emphasizing horizontal and vertical gradients. It's commonly used to highlight edges in both x (horizontal) and y (vertical) directions.

Prewitt gradient: Similar to Sobel but with slightly different kernel values, the Prewitt operator is also used for edge detection. It's simpler than Sobel but less sensitive to noise, making it effective for general gradient detection.

Scharr gradient: The Scharr operator is an improved version of the Sobel operator, especially for detecting edges in high-noise images. It emphasizes edges more strongly by using a different kernel, which can produce sharper gradients.

Laplacian of Gaussian (LoG): The Laplacian of Gaussian first applies Gaussian smoothing to reduce noise, then the Laplacian operator detects the gradient. LoG is beneficial for finding fine details and edges in complex images.

Roberts cross gradient: The Roberts Cross operator detects edges by calculating gradients diagonally (at 45-degree angles). It's particularly useful for simple edge detection in noiseless images.

Canny edge detector: The Canny detector is an advanced edge detection method that involves Gaussian smoothing, finding intensity gradients, and applying non-maximum suppression and edge tracking. While more complex, it's highly effective for identifying strong and weak edges, making it suitable for detecting image boundaries.

Isotropic gradient: This involves computing the gradient magnitude

2.3. Proposed technique [111]

and direction using isotropic (rotation-invariant) kernels. The gradient vector's magnitude and direction provide detailed information about the intensity changes.

Each of these methods has its own unique characteristics and application suitability, depending on image quality, noise levels, and the specific purpose (e.g., edge detection, feature extraction, or enhancing contrast). In addition to these, all the above-mentioned techniques are particularly applicable to the single band/channel or gray-scale images. For multi band/channel or RGB image these methods can be applied after converting/reducing to single band/channel or gray scale image. There are techniques that can directly applied to the RGB or multi band/channel images directly for gradient generation.

Marginal Ordering: This approach involves applying morphological operations independently on each color channel (e.g., R, G, B in an RGB image). While straightforward, it can ignore the interactions between channels, potentially resulting in inconsistencies when combining channels back together.

Vectorial Ordering: This strategy considers the multichannel image as a vector field, treating each pixel as a vector of values across channels (e.g., [R,G,B]). Morphological operations are then defined based on the vector magnitude or another vector ordering scheme. This approach better preserves inter-channel relationships, making it particularly relevant for tasks requiring nuanced color interpretation, such as hyperspectral imaging.

In the proposed techniques we have used morphological gradient from the corresponding gray scale image, as because this makes simple both in concept and computationally also. Morphological gradients offer significant advantages over other traditional gradient methods, particularly in their robustness to noise, preservation of shape integrity, and resilience to illumination changes. By leveraging the difference between dilation and erosion, they produce precise and well-defined object boundaries while minimizing false positives in complex scenes.

Their adaptability through customizable structuring elements allows them to excel in diverse applications such as medical imaging, satellite-based remote sensing, industrial inspection, and document analysis. Additionally, their seamless integration with other morphological operations makes them a powerful tool for advanced image analysis tasks.

2.3.2 Generation of gradient image

Our filtering method works on both gray scale as well as colour images. If the input is a colour image, then its corresponding gray scale image is used to generate the morphological gradient image. In many cases, the images may have high gradient textural contents which could be misinterpreted as the structural edges. To optimize the discrimination between textural and structural contents of the image, in this work, we proposed a pre-processing step that performs filtering on the input image by defining a morphological filter combining opening and closing operations. Let I_{gray} represent the grayscale image derived from the input image. The proposed pre-processing step generates a filtered image J from I_{gray} using a (3×3) SE of 8-neighbours as follows:

$$J = (\delta_{SE}(\varepsilon_{SE}(I_{gray}) + \varepsilon_{SE}(\delta_{SE}(I_{gray}))) / 2 \quad (2.1)$$

Figure 2-2(a) shows a 1-dimensional signal with some high textural oscillations having equal or higher gradients than the structural edges. Figure 2-2(d) shows the filtered signal obtained by applying the morphological operation defined in equation (2.1). From this figure, one can see that the average of opening and closing removes the lower textural oscillations and diminishes the higher textural gradient while keeping the higher structural gradients mostly unchanged. Thus, it helps to create a difference between high gradient textural and structural contents in the gradient domain. To better understand the usefulness of the morphological

2.3. Proposed technique [111]

operation defined in equation (2.1), Figure 2-3 displays a real image alongside the filtered images obtained through applying different morphological operations. It also plots the pixels intensity values on the red line (passes through both textural and structural regions) for these images. From Figure 2-3(a) it is showing that in the original image, there are some textural edges whose gradients are as high as the structural edges. From Figures 2-3(b) and 2-3(c) one can see that the individual operation of the opening increases the darker textural gradient and closing increases the brighter textural gradient. But the average of both the operations as defined in equation (2.1) diminishes the textural high gradients (or impulse noises) while keeping structural edges with minimum distortion as shown in Figure 2-3(d). After obtaining the filtered image J , the proposed technique generates morphological gradient image J_{mg} as follows [114]:

$$J_{mg} = (\delta_{SE}(J) - \varepsilon_{SE}(J)) \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2-4: (a) Gradient image without applying pre-processing, (b) Gradient image with applying proposed pre-processing and (c) Its histogram with the best fitted log-normal distribution curve by maximum likelihood estimator. (d) The initial edge-map E_b obtained by applying global threshold t_1 .

Figure 2-4(a) and Figure 2-4(b) is the gradient image obtained without and with applying the pre-processing step, respectively. From these figures, one can see that the proposed pre-processing step diminishes high gradient textures while keeping the structural edges with minimum distortions.

2.3.3 Generation of edge-map

The gradient image J_{mg} obtained from equation (2.2) is applied to produce the edge-map. For an image, a very less number of pixels are associated with significant structural edges as compared to the non-edge pixels. Thus, in the gradient image J_{mg} , higher gradient pixels associated with the structural edges are much less in number than the lower gradient pixels associated with smooth areas. So, the histogram of the gradient image is likely to follow a positively-skewed distribution with a high peak of lower values and a right-tail of higher values, as illustrated in Figure 2-4(c). Note that the domain of the gradient image J_{mg} is associated with non-negative values. So the positively-skewed histogram of the non-negative gradient can be assumed to follow a log-normal distribution [3, 40]:

$$\begin{cases} f(x) = \frac{1}{x\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(\ln(x)-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \\ \mu = \ln\left(\frac{\nu}{\sqrt{1+\frac{\gamma^2}{\nu^2}}}\right) \\ \sigma = \sqrt{\ln\left(1 + \frac{\gamma^2}{\nu^2}\right)} \end{cases} \quad \text{where } x > 0, \sigma > 0 \quad (2.3)$$

The probability density function of a log-normal distribution $f(x)$ for a random variable x is a continuous distribution of positive values as define in equation (2.3), such that the logarithm of x i.e., $\ln(x)$ follow a normal distribution $N(\mu, \sigma)$. Where $\mu = \ln(m)$ is the scale parameter represents mean of $\ln(x)$ and m is the median of the x , σ is the shape parameter represents standard deviation of $\ln(x)$. The standard deviation and mean of x are denoted as γ and ν respectively. Since the gradient image J_{mg} may have zero gradient value we have added a very small positive value η as $J_{mg} = J_{mg} + \eta$ to model J_{mg} as log-normal distribution. In order to generate an accurate edge-map, first, a global threshold t_1 from the gradient image J_{mg} histogram is detected by exploiting the properties of the log-normal distribution. The threshold t_1 roughly differentiates the edge pixels and the non-edge ones in the gradient image. For a log-normal variate x ,

2.3. Proposed technique [111]

the corresponding normal distribution $ln(x)$ contain 66.68% of values within the range $(\mu - \sigma, \mu + \sigma)$, which corresponds to the high peak portion $(e^{\mu-\sigma}, e^{\mu+\sigma})$ of the log-normal distribution. The right-tail portion $(\geq e^{\mu+\sigma})$ of the corresponding log-normal distribution contains less than 33.32% of total values. In this work, we have taken the global threshold $t_1 = e^{\mu+\sigma}$ to roughly differentiate between the edge (high gradient) and the non-edge (low gradient) pixels. After obtaining the threshold t_1 , the initial binary edge-map E_b from the gradient image is generated as follows:

$$E_b(p) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } J_{mg}(p) \geq t_1 \\ 0, & \text{if } J_{mg}(p) < t_1 \end{cases} \quad (2.4)$$

The initial edge-map E_b generated by considering the global threshold t_1 may have textural edges along with structural edges. To further reduces the presence of non-structural edges in the edge-map, a novel technique is proposed to refine it. For each edge pixels p in E_b , the technique constructs a local histogram $H(J_{mg}^w)$ of the gradient image J_{mg} considering a fixed size window $W = (w \times w)$ centering at pixel p . Then to determine whether the pixel p is part of a structural edge or not, it computes the non-parametric skewness value Sk_p from the histogram $H(J_{mg}^w)$ as follows:

$$\begin{cases} Sk_p = \frac{\mu_l - m_l}{\sigma_l} \\ \mu_l = \text{mean of } H(J_{mg}^w) \\ m_l = \text{median of } H(J_{mg}^w) \\ \sigma_l = \text{standard deviation of } H(J_{mg}^w) \end{cases} \quad (2.5)$$

In the proposed technique for each edge pixel p in J_{mg} , if the skewness Sk_p is positive, then the pixel remains an edge pixel. In other cases, it converts into a non-edge pixel. So, the proposed technique generates the refine edge-map

Figure 2-5: (a)(d) Original images, their (b)(e) initial edge-maps E_b , and (c)(f) refined edge-maps E_r produced by the proposed technique.

E_r from the initial edge-map E_b as follows:

$$E_r(p) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } E_b(p) = 1 \text{ and } Sk_p > 0 \\ 0, & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

Table 2.1: The skewness values obtained from local histograms are associated with the different pixels of the gradient image.

<i>Test Pixels (p)</i>	<i>Skewness (Sk_p)</i>	<i>Status</i>
p_1	1.0715	edge
p_2	-0.0083	non-edge
p_3	0.7069	edge
p_4	-0.0467	non-edge
p_5	-0.0733	non-edge

Figure 2-5 show the initial edge-map E_b and the corresponding refined edge-map E_r produced by the proposed technique for two different images. For a deeper insight how the local skewness value of the gradient image helped to find whether a pixel is an edge pixel or not, five edge pixels p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 , and p_5 from

Figure 2-6: (a) Original image I and (b) the corresponding gradient image J_{mg} . (c)(d)(e)(f)(g) The zoomed version of the red windows of center pixels p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 and p_5 are shown in the original image, and (h)(i)(j)(k)(l) their corresponding local histograms obtained from the gradient image.

different portions of the gradient image J_{mg} obtained from the Figure 2-6(a) are chosen. Considering these pixels as center pixels, the corresponding portions in the original image cover by the local windows (red boxes) are shown in Figure 2-6(a). The zoomed version of these windows are depicted in Figures 2-6(c), 2-6(d), 2-6(e), 2-6(f), and 2-6(g). From these figures, one can see that pixels p_1 and p_3 originally belong to the structural-edge regions, whereas pixels p_2, p_4 and p_5 originally belong to the textural or smoother regions. Figure 2-6(h), Figure 2-6(i), Figure 2-6(j), Figure 2-6(k), and Figure 2-6(l) shows the local histogram (considering window W) of the gradient image J_{mg} associated to the center pixel p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 and p_5 respectively. From these figures, it is evident that the gradient distribution of the local histograms corresponding to the pixels p_1 and p_3 which are on the structural-edge regions are positively skewed (i.e., their local

histograms from J_{mg} contain few locally higher gradient pixels those are part of the significant edges). Whereas, the distribution of the local histograms corresponding to the pixels p_2, p_4 and p_5 which belong to the textural or smoother regions are not positively skewed (i.e., their local histograms in J_{mg} contain more locally higher gradient pixels or similar gradient pixels those are part of some textural or smoother regions). Table 2.1 reports the skewness values computed for these five local histograms. Form the table one can see that the pixels having positive skewness values are on the structural-edges, and pixels of negative skewness are on the textural/smooth regions. Note that for the presence of high gradient noises, some pixels in the textural region may possess positive skewness values. In such cases, our method may wrongly identify these pixels as structural-edge pixels. To mitigate this, in the proposed work the edge-map for the next iteration is updated based on the filtered image generated in the current iteration.

2.3.4 Median morpho-filtering

To produce the final filtered image, we propose a novel semantic-aware structure preserving filtering technique by exploiting the generated edge-map E_r . Let I be the original image will be filtered and E_r be the corresponding edge-map generated by the proposed technique. By exploiting the edge-map E_r , our technique follows different approaches to determine the dynamic window of the median filter for filtering the edge pixels and non-edge ones. For filtering the pixels belonging to textural regions (i.e., non-edge pixels), our technique determines the dynamic size square window by looking into the surrounding edge pixels present in E_r . For each non-edge pixel, the algorithm starts with a small square window L_w and then increases its size uniformly until a sufficiently large size square window is obtained or an edge pixel is found. Thus, for filtering non-edge pixels our algorithm determine dynamic size square windows by looking into the edge pixel on the edge-map. The blue boxes in Figure 2-7 depict the windows obtained by

the proposed algorithm for some non-edge pixels. From this figure one can see that the larger size windows are formed for filtering the pixels of textural areas which are far from the structural-edges and smaller size windows are formed for filtering the pixels near to the structural-edges. Thus, the size of the windows defined by the proposed algorithm for filtering non-edge pixels is adaptive in nature. On the other hand, conversely, for filtering the pixels that are part of structural-edges (i.e., edge pixels), our technique determines the shape of the window of the median filter dynamically by identifying the appropriate object in which the edge pixel belongs. Note that edge pixels always belong to either one of the two objects that are responsible for forming the edge. By computing the intensity value of the edge pixel within a fixed-size window, our algorithm tried to find out the appropriate object to which the considered edge pixel belongs and then reshape the window for filtering. The red curves in Figure 2-7 formed the dynamic windows by considering the appropriate edge pixels for filtering some structural-edge pixels. The window sizes defined by the developed algorithm for filtering edge pixels is also adaptive in nature.

In greater detail, let p be an edge pixel and its intensity value in the original image I is I_p . Our algorithm first defines a fixed-size square window W_s by using p as a center pixel. Considering the window W_s , let I_{w_s} and $E_r^{w_s}$ be the sub-image obtained from the input image I and the edge-map image E_r , respectively. Let $I_{w_s}^e$ represent the intensity values of the edge pixels in I_{w_s} . The middle intensity value R_{mid} of the edge pixels within W_s will be $R_{mid} = (\max(I_{w_s}^e) + \min(I_{w_s}^e))/2$. The pixel intensity I_p is larger (or smaller) than R_{mid} implying that the edge pixel p belongs in the higher(or lower) intensity object. Thus, for filtering the pixel p , if I_p is larger than R_{mid} then the pixels in I_{w_s} having higher intensity values than R_{mid} are considered to define the window W_s^u of the median filter. Otherwise, the pixels in I_{w_s} having lower intensity values than R_{mid} are considered to define the window W_s^l of the median filter. In the proposed technique for filtering edge pixels the dynamic size window W_s^a of the median filter within W_s is defined as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} R_{mid} = (\max(I_{w_s}^e) + \min(I_{w_s}^e))/2 \\ W_s^l = \text{pixels in } W_s \text{ for which } (I_{w_s} \leq R_{mid}) \\ W_s^u = \text{pixels in } W_s \text{ for which } (I_{w_s} > R_{mid}) \\ \text{if } (I_p \leq R_{mid}), \text{ then } W_s^a = W_s^l \\ \text{if } (I_p > R_{mid}), \text{ then } W_s^a = W_s^u \end{array} \right. \quad (2.7)$$

Figure 2-7: Adaptive windows for the median filter are designed using the generated edge-map (E_r).

From the above equations, one can see that the dynamic window W_s^u is formed when the center pixel's (I_p) intensity value is higher than R_{mid} , otherwise, it is formed the dynamic window W_s^l for filtering the edge pixel p . The proposed algorithm splits the fixed size window W_s to form an edge adaptive dynamic shape window along the approximate edge alignment. The red curves in Figure 2-7 connected with appropriate edge pixels show the dynamic windows defined by the proposed algorithm for filtering edge pixels. From this figure, one can

Figure 2-8: (a)(f) Original images and the generated edge-maps after (b)(g) iteration 1, (c)(h) iteration 2, (d)(i) iteration 3. (e)(j) Filtered images produced by the proposed technique after 3rd iteration.

Figure 2-9: (a) Original image and some magnified portions of it. Filtered images obtained by the proposed technique after (b) iteration 1, (c) iteration 3, and (d) iteration 5.

Algorithm 1 Proposed semantic-aware structure preserving filtering technique

```

1: Input: Image  $I$ 
2: Output: Filtered Image  $I_f$ 
3:   Obtain grayscale image  $I_{gray}$  from the input image  $I$ 
4:   Generate pre-processed image-  $J = (\delta_{SE}(\varepsilon_{SE}(I_{gray}) + \varepsilon_{SE}(\delta_{SE}(I_{gray}))) / 2$ 
5:   Generate gradient image  $J_{mg} = \delta_{SE}(J) - \varepsilon_{SE}(J)$ 
6: for iteration = 1 to  $n_{itr}$ 
7:   for all pixel  $p \in J_{mg}$ 
8:     if ( $J_{mg}(p) \geq e^{(\mu+\sigma)}$ )
9:        $E_b(p) = 1$ 
10:    else
11:       $E_b(p) = 0$ 
12:    end if
13:  end for
14:  for all pixels  $p \in E_b$ 
15:    if ( $E_b(p) = 1 \ \& \ Sk_p > 0.0$ )
16:       $E_r(p) = 1$ 
17:    else-if ( $E_b(p) = 1 \ \& \ Sk_p \leq 0.0$ )
18:       $E_r(p) = 0$ 
19:    end if
20:  end for
21:  for image band  $c = 1$  to  $C$ 
22:    for all pixels  $p \in I_c$ 
23:      if ( $E_r(p) = 1 \ \& \ I_c(p) \leq R_{mid}$ )
24:        Define window  $W_s^a = W_s^l$  using (2.7)
25:      else-if ( $E_b(p) = 1 \ \& \ I_c(p) > R_{mid}$ )
26:        Define window  $W_s^a = W_s^u$  using (2.7)
27:      else-if ( $E_b(p) = 0$ )
28:        Define window  $W_s^a$  by starting from  $L_w$ 
29:        to a maximal size square window that does
30:        not contain any edge content.
31:      end if
32:      Replace  $I_c(p)$  by the median value from  $I_c$ 
33:      within the window  $W_s^a$ .
34:    end for
35:     $I_f(c) = (\delta_{SE}(\varepsilon_{SE}(I_c) + \varepsilon_{SE}(\delta_{SE}(I_c))) / 2$ 
36:  end for
37:   $I = I_f$ 
38: end for

```

see that windows at the edge are formed according to the edge linearity. Since there is a possibility that the window division for edge pixels may not always be as accurate as the actual edge alignment. In such cases, a small amount of edge distortion may occur after applying the proposed adaptive median filter. In order to refine these distortions, the morphological operation defined in equation (2.1)

2.4. Experimental results and analysis

with a small static window is applied. The adaptive median filtering followed by morphological filtering alternatively suppresses/refines the artifacts/distortions of each other. That is, the edge dilation of median filtering regains its sharpness by the morphological counterpart and the impulse edge shape distortion of morphological filtering is smoothed by median filtering. In this work, we refer to this technique as adaptive median morpho-filtering.

All the steps of the proposed technique need to be repeated multiple times to generate the desired filtered image. Let I_f be the filtered image obtained from the input image I . Then the output image I_f is considered as the input image ($I = I_f$) for the next iteration. Figure 2-8 shows the edge-maps produced by the proposed technique at different iterations and the filtered image obtained after 3rd iteration. Figure 2-9 shows the filter images produced by the proposed technique at different iterations. From these figures, it is evident that the developed technique successfully preserves the structure of the objects. The developed technique is outlined in Algorithm 1.

2.4 Experimental results and analysis

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed filtering technique, it is compared with six widely recognized structure-preserving smoothing techniques considered as state-of-the-art, such as bilateral texture filtering(BTF) [32], Relativity of Gaussian(RoG) [22], scale-aware texture filtering(SATF) [69], structure adaptive total variation(SATV) [125], fast adaptive bilateral filtering(FABF) [55], and real-time iterative least square(RILS) [91]. To achieve an equitable comparison, the parameters of all these state-of-the-art methods are meticulously chosen. Whenever possible, the parameter values are adopted from the respective papers that reported the best results. Otherwise, we manually adjust the parameter values to achieve the best possible results using a trial-

and-error approach. The images analyzed in this study are accessible publicly at <http://www.cse.cuhk.edu.hk/~leojia/projects/texturesep/index.html> and <http://cg.postech.ac.kr/publications>. Detailed comparisons are outlined in the subsequent subsections.

2.4.1 Qualitative comparison

Qualitative comparisons between the developed and the state-of-the-art methods are performed on the basis of how much they are effective to differentiate texture and structure by smoothing out fine details of textures while preserving the significant structures. Figure 2-10 shows the filtering results obtained by the developed as well as the six state-of-the-art methods for the part of the Roman marine life mosaic image. By looking into the zoomed portions of the filter images produced by the different methods, it is evident that our method is outperforming the existing methods in both terms: i) texture smoothing and ii) structure preserving. From the figure, it is observed that BTF [32], SATF [69], FABF [55] are capable of preserving the significant structures but producing poor smoothing results for the varying scale textures. Whereas, the RoG [22] filtering technique is good in texture smoothing but fails to preserve the smaller structures, and the RILS [91] produces blur structural objects. On the contrary, our developed method is equally effective in smoothing varying scales texture as well as preserving the significant structures of different sizes. Unlike the other methods, instead of blurring, the proposed method sharpens the filtered image by preserving the structural edges. Moreover, it is capable to preserve the small structural details like the iris and eyelids of the fishes more prominently than the others. In the experiment performed on a large number of images containing different types of textural patterns the proposed technique always produced satisfactory results.

Figure 2-10: Comparative results for part of the Roman marine life mosaic image in Pompeii (a) Original image and some zoomed portions of it. Filtered images generated by applying (b) BTF, $k = 7, n_{itr} = 5$ [32], (c) SATF $ss = 4, sr = 0.05, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$ [69], (d) RoG, $\lambda = 0.01, \sigma_1 = 2, \sigma_2 = 4, K = 4, dec = 2.0$ [22], (e) SATV, $\lambda = 1.25, n_{itr} = 19$ [125], (f) FABF $\rho_{smooth} = 5, \rho_{sharp} = 5$ [55], (g) RILS, $\lambda = 0.35, \gamma = 50/255, n_{itr} = 25$ [91], and (h) Proposed, $W = 31 \times 31, n_{itr} = 4$

Figure 2-11: Comparative results for part of a roman still life mosaic image: (a) Original image and the filtered images produced by applying (b) BTF, $k = 5, n_{itr} = 3$ [32], (c) SATF $ss = 3, sr = 0.1, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$ [69], (d) RoG, $\lambda = 0.01, \sigma_1 = 1, \sigma_2 = 2, K = 2, dec = 2.0$ [22], (e) SATV, $\lambda = 2.5$ [125], (f) FABF $\rho_{smooth} = 2, \rho_{sharp} = 4$ [55], (g) RILS, $\lambda = 0.5, \gamma = 25/255, n_{itr} = 15$ [91], and (h) Proposed, $W = 17 \times 17, n_{itr} = 3$

The filtering results obtained from a few of such images are shown in Figures 2-11, 2-12, and 2-13. From these figures, one can see that for the input images of smaller textural patterns e.g. part of the Roman still life mosaic image in Figure 2-11(a) as well as the images of larger texels e.g. the brick wall graffiti image in Figure 2-12(a), the proposed method always provides better or as good as the best result produced by the existing state-of-the-art methods. Looking into the filtering results in Figure 2-11 and Figure 2-12, one can see that our method outperforms most of the existing techniques. Figure 2-13 displays the filtering results of the developed technique on a few more popular images containing rich textural variation.

Figure 2-12: Comparative results for a brick wall graffiti image: (a) Original image and the filtered images produced by applying (b) BTF, $k = 9, n_{itr} = 7$ [32], (c) SATF $ss = 7, sr = 0.05, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$ [69], (d) RoG, $\lambda = 0.01, \sigma_1 = 2, \sigma_2 = 4, K = 4, dec = 2.0$ [22], (e) SATV, $\lambda = 0.75$ [125], (f) FABF $\rho_{smooth} = 5, \rho_{sharp} = 5$ [55], (g) RILS, $\lambda = 0.75, \gamma = 50/255, n_{itr} = 25$ [91], and (h) Proposed, $W = 7 \times 7, n_{itr} = 7$

Figure 2-13: (a)(b)(c)(d) Original images, and (e)(f)(g)(h) the filtered images obtained by the proposed technique.

2.4.2 Quantitative comparison

From recent studies, it was found that the classical non-subjective Image Quality Assessment (IQA) metrics like Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR), Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) are not good enough for assessing the quality of the filtered images, particularly when they are generated by structure-preserving or texture filtering techniques [140]. The subjective reference IQA metrics such as Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) [136], Multi-scale SSIM (MSSIM), Mutual Information (MI) [131] and the subjective no-reference metrics like Perception based Image Quality Evaluator (PIQE) [132] and Naturalness Image Quality Evaluator (NIQE) are more closer to human perception. For additional information on these IQA metrics reader may refer to [131, 132, 136, 140]. To evaluate the effectiveness of the developed technique with respect to both texture smoothing and structure preservation, a quantitative comparison is performed with the help of three subjective references IQA metrics SSIM, MSSIM, MI, and a subjective no-reference metric PIQE, where SSIM and MSSIM have a range of $[0, 1]$, while MI ranges from $[0, \log(m \times n)]$, where $m \times n$ denotes the image size, and PIQE ranges from $[0, 100]$. Higher values for SSIM, MSSIM, and MI indicate better performance, whereas a lower value for PIQE signifies better quality. Table 2.2 reports the values provided by those IQA metrics for different filtered images. This table demonstrates that for the natural texture images, the developed technique always provides superior results contrast to all six state-of-the-art methods considered for comparison. For the Lena image with artificial texture and noise, our method yields competitive results to the best literature method. Thus, by analyzing both the quantitative and qualitative results leads us to conclude that the proposed technique surpasses existing state-of-the-art methods in terms of both texture smoothing and structure preservation.

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Table 2.2: The values of the IQA metrics SSIM, MSSIM, MI and PIQE obtained for the filter images generated by the different techniques. The bold font indicates the best values of these IQA metrics.

<i>Images</i>	<i>Metrics</i>	<i>BTF [32]</i>	<i>SATF [69]</i>	<i>RoG [22]</i>	<i>SATV [125]</i>	<i>FABF [55]</i>	<i>RILS [91]</i>	<i>Proposed [111]</i>
Marine life PIQE=20.18	SSIM	0.43	0.41	0.42	0.42	0.44	0.42	0.48
	MSSIM	0.58	0.55	0.50	0.51	0.47	0.58	0.63
	MI	1.74	1.72	1.65	1.69	1.67	1.73	1.80
	PIQE	89.10	89.56	88.64	82.90	90.03	89.34	79.37
Still life PIQE=34.63	SSIM	0.56	0.53	0.56	0.55	0.50	0.57	0.59
	MSSIM	0.76	0.69	0.70	0.70	0.61	0.74	0.77
	MI	2.30	2.27	2.30	2.28	2.26	2.31	2.35
	PIQE	86.86	88.85	86.64	75.28	85.30	86.82	75.10
Graffiti PIQE=27.43	SSIM	0.75	0.72	0.78	0.72	0.74	0.71	0.79
	MSSIM	0.68	0.57	0.71	0.56	0.58	0.62	0.74
	MI	2.03	1.92	2.11	1.90	1.88	1.89	2.27
	PIQE	86.74	92.19	87.70	87.23	87.39	83.05	78.88

2.4.3 Parameters setting and analysis

To incorporate information from neighboring pixels, the proposed technique considers a few windows. The window W used to form the local histogram of the gradient image for computing the local skewness is one such parameter of the proposed technique. The optimum size of this window is dependent on the scale and size of the texels (single textural pattern) present in the input image. In the experiment, the size of W is set manually by looking at the input image. The square windows L_w and W_s of the proposed technique are the spatial parameters supplied as input to the median filter for filtering textural and structural-edge pixels, respectively. Since our technique increases the initial size of L_w in an adaptive manner, the size of the square window L_w should be small (can be taken from 3×3 to 11×11 depending on the size of the small structure to be preserved) and is not a critical parameter to set. In the experiment, the initial size of L_w is set to 3×3 for all the considered images. As for filtering structural-edge pixels, the window W_s is divided into two parts along with the edge alignment. The size of W_s should cover sufficient pixels to form two groups. If we fix the size of W_s

very large, then there is a possibility of overlapping the textural and structural edges. Experimentally we found that the size of W_s between 5×5 to 11×11 provides satisfactory results for a wide variety of images. Keep in mind that the size of the square window W_s is not a critical parameter to set as our technique dynamically reshapes it before filtering. Taking its size smaller preserves more but smoothing needs more iterations. In the experiment the size of W_s is set to 7×7 for all the considered images. For morphological filtering, the proposed technique uses a small SE of size 3×3 . Table 2.3 illustrated the list of parameters of the developed technique and their suggested values. From this table, one can see that the proposed technique has only a critical parameter W . Figure 2-14 shows filter images and their corresponding values of different IQA metrics of the developed technique for different window sizes W .

Table 2.3: List of parameters of the proposed technique and their suggested values.

<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Used for</i>	<i>Suggested range</i>	<i>Taken in experiment</i>
W	Local gradients skewness calculation	5×5 to 41×41	set manually
L_w	Filtering textural pixels	3×3 to 11×11	3×3
W_s	Filtering edge pixels	5×5 to 11×11	7×7
SE	Morphological operations	3×3 or 5×5	3×3
n_{itr}	No of iterations	1 to 10	set manually

Figure 2-14: (a) Original image of a mosaic floor (PIQE=38.97) and some zoomed portions of it. Filtered images obtained by the proposed technique after iteration 3 for (b) $W = 7 \times 7$ (SSIM=0.75, MSSIM=0.76, MI=2.27, PIQE=79.92), (c) $W = 15 \times 15$ (SSIM=0.75, MSSIM=0.77, MI=2.28, PIQE=78.34), and (d) $W = 23 \times 23$ (SSIM=0.76, MSSIM=0.77, MI=2.28, PIQE=78.50).

2.4.4 Applications

Structure-preserving filtering techniques find widespread applications in the realm of image processing and analysis. They prove valuable as both pre-processing and post-processing tools for tasks such as image denoising, enhancement, tone mapping, abstraction, classification, segmentation, and more.

Below are brief descriptions of some specific applications where the proposed filtering technique demonstrates its efficacy.

2.4.4.1 Image denoising

Image denoising involves the removal of unwanted or random variations in pixel values, known as noise, from digital images. Noise often accompanies image ac-

Figure 2-15: (a)(d)(g) Original images, (b)(e)(h) images with Gaussian noise ($\sigma = 0.03$) and their corresponding (c)(f)(i) denoised images obtained by applying the proposed filtering technique.

quisition, transmission, or processing, leading to a degradation in image quality. The objective of denoising is to redevelop the original, clean image by reducing or removing the impact of noise. In Figure 4-9, the presented results display both the noisy and the corresponding denoised images achieved through the proposed filtering technique. The filtered image clearly demonstrates its ability to preserve

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structures effectively while successfully eliminating noise.

2.4.4.2 Detail enhancement

Figure 2-16: (a)(c)(e) Original images and their corresponding (b)(d)(f) enhanced images obtained by the proposed technique.

Image enhancement encompasses the modification of an image to enhance its visual quality, rendering it more suitable for human perception or specific computer vision tasks. These enhancement techniques aim to accentuate particular features, amplify contrast, reduce noise, and overall elevate the image's quality. In Fig. 4-9, the presented images showcase both the original images and their corresponding enhanced versions achieved through the proposed filtering method. The enhancement process begins by decomposing the input image into two layers - one being a smoothed image and the other capturing textural details. The final enhanced image is produced by appending these textural details to the original image. The enhanced images prominently highlight the textural details, showcasing the impact of the developed filtering technique.

2.4.4.3 Tone mapping

Tone mapping is a technique employed in computer graphics and image processing to transform high-dynamic-range (HDR) images into a format suitable for display on devices with lower dynamic ranges (LDR), such as computer monitors, TVs, or printed media. HDR images capture a broader range of luminance values compared to standard images, and tone mapping assists in rendering these images on regular displays while retaining as much visual information as possible. In Figure 4-10(a)(c), two LDR image (RGB) tone-mapped from two HDR images using Farbman's technique [47] is presented. Figure 4-10(b)(d) illustrates the corresponding tone-mapped RGB version generated with the proposed filtering technique. Notably, the proposed filtering technique was seamlessly integrated in place of bilateral filtering (BF) within Durand's method [49] with $\gamma = 0.5$. This replacement demonstrates the impact of the developed technique in the context of tone mapping.

Figure 2-17: (a)(c) Tone mapped images generated by Farbman's method [47] and (b)(d) tone mapped images generated by Durand's method [49] integrating proposed filtering technique.

2.4.4.4 Edge detection

Edge detection is a fundamental step in image processing, impacting applications such as object recognition, segmentation, and feature extraction. Traditional edge detection methods like the Sobel, Prewitt, and Laplacian operators often face challenges in accurately detecting edges in noisy or complex images. The Canny Edge Detector is one of the popular techniques that use sobel operator with Gaussian smoothing. Early edge detection methods like Sobel and Prewitt operators relied on calculating directional (horizontal or vertical) intensity gradients using simple 3×3 convolution kernels. These methods were computationally efficient and easy to implement but suffered from noise sensitivity, especially in high-frequency areas. Laplacian and Laplacian of Gaussian (LoG) operators improved edge localization by highlighting regions of rapid intensity change; however, they were also noise-prone and often required additional smoothing to avoid spurious edges. The Canny Edge Detector, with its multi-step process (including Gaussian smoothing, gradient calculation, and edge tracking), set a new standard by improving edge continuity and reducing noise, though at a higher computational cost.

Figure 2-18: (a)(g) Original images and (b)(h) Edge detected from the original images, (c)(i) Edge detected after 5×5 Gaussian smoothing, (d)(j) Edge detected after 9×9 Gaussian smoothing, (e)(k) Edge detected after smoothing by the proposed technique using Canny operator, and (f)(l) Edge detected by the proposed technique with the proposed morphological gradient-based approach.

In this work, we propose a morphological gradient-based approach to address edge detection challenges. The morphological gradient offers advantages over traditional directional gradients, as it detects intensity changes in all directions. However, applying the morphological gradient directly for edge detection can result in sensitivity to noise and high frequencies, similar to the existing methods. To mitigate this, our approach explores both the local and global distribution of the morphological gradient, which reduces the noise and high frequency sensitivity while effectively identifying semantic edges. In the Figure 2-18 presents a comparative analysis: the edge detection results from the Canny detector applied to two original images, followed by results after Gaussian smoothing with masks of sizes

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5×5 and 9×9 , respectively. We then show the edges detected by the canny edge detector from the filtered images of the proposed technique, along with the results from our morphological gradient-based approach. These comparisons highlight the effectiveness of our technique in precisely detecting semantic edges.

2.4.5 Computational performance analysis

Table 2.4: The execution times (in seconds) of the developed method in contrast to the state-of-the-art methods.

<i>Images</i>	<i>BTF [32]</i>	<i>SATF [69]</i>	<i>RoG [22]</i>	<i>SATV [125]</i>	<i>FABF [55]</i>	<i>RILS [91]</i>	<i>Proposed</i>
Marine life (675×900)	56.04	77.95	9.96	5.57	7.47	3.21	56.67
Still life (600×450)	11.05	53.46	5.49	3.94	5.05	2.98	19.01
Graffiti (640×960)	46.42	101.58	10.08	7.50	7.76	3.51	88.20

The proposed technique has two important steps. First, it generates the edge-map, then based on the generated edge-map, adaptive median morpho-filtering produces the filtered image. The edge-map generation followed by median morpho-filtering is iteratively executed to obtain the final filtered image. The edge-map generation step has the complexity of $O(M \times N \times W)$, where $M \times N$ is the size of the image and W is the window for local gradient skewness calculation. The adaptive median morpho-filtering has the complexity of $O(M \times N \times W_s^a)$, where W_s^a is the adaptive window for filtering edge and non-edge pixels. So, the computational complexity of the developed algorithm is $O(M \times N \times W')$, where $W' = \max\{W, W_s^a\}$.

The proposed technique and the available Matlab codes of the 6 state-of-the-art techniques used for comparison are executed on a 3.70 GHz Xeon(R)-8 Core(s) processor with 128 GB RAM. Table 2.4 shows the execution time (in seconds) of different techniques. From this table, it is evident that although the developed technique takes lesser time than the existing SATF technique and comparable time with BTF technique, it takes significantly higher time than the RoG,

SATV, FABF, and ILS techniques. Note that our current Matlab implementation is worked on a CPU environment and is not heavily optimized. It takes some time for skewness, adaptive windows, and median computation, which can be significantly enhanced through parallel GPU implementation [60] and by employing more advanced sampling [64] and sorting algorithm (like counting sort [118]).

2.5 Conclusions

The main challenge for developing a robust structure preserving filtering technique lies in the fact of handling varying scale textural patterns. In order to better handle varying scale textural patterns, in this chapter we have proposed a semantic-aware structure preserving filtering technique. Our technique defines a novel method to obtain an edge-aware adaptive window of dynamic shape for filtering each pixel by excluding its neighbour pixels belonging to different textural or structural regions. To this end, at first, a novel approach is proposed to generate the edge-map by analysing the skewness of global and local histograms of the morphological gradient. Then, using the generated edge-map a semantic-aware structure preserving median morpho-filtering is designed by combining the output of median and morphological filters. The key advancements of this work are: i) proposes a texture structure decomposition technique analysing the global and local morphological gradient distribution, and ii) proposes a combined median morpho-filtering for better texture smoothing while preserving the significant structures. Our filtering method, unlike most existing techniques, can simultaneously achieve several conflicting goals, including identifying and removing texture, preserving structural edges, safeguarding subtle features such as corners, and preventing both over-sharpening and over-blurring artifacts or distortions.

Although the developed technique successfully works on a broad spectrum of images but our present implementation is not of real-time. Implementation of the proposed technique in real-time or near real-time and apply this technique to

different image/video processing applications like semantic segmentation, object detection and classification etc would be an interesting extension of this work.

List of publications from this chapter

Journals

1. Pradhan K., Patra S., “Semantic-aware structure-preserving median morpho-filtering”. *The Visual Computer*, 2023, March 5:1-7, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00371-023-02796-z>. (**IF-3.0**)

Chapter 3

Reduced parameter sensitive edge-aware semantic image filtering

3.1 Introduction

Although, the filtering technique presented in the previous chapter provides satisfactory results for a wide varieties of images, it has a critical parameter that needs to be define manually for incorporating appropriate semantic information of the pixels. To establish whether a pixel is an edge or non-edge, the technique used a fixed size square window to compute the skewness of local histogram of the gradient image for incorporating semantic information. So, the semantic edge-map generated by this technique is highly sensitive to the size of this window, which is varied from image to image. Moreover, for varying scale textural images, a fixed size window will not be capable of capturing appropriate semantic information. Thus, the technique may failed to provide good results for such images. Furthermore, to produce the appropriate edge-map for the input image, the technique presented in the previous chapter iterates some steps. The optimal number of iterations is varied from image to image and need to be fixed manually.

In order to mitigate above problems, in this chapter, we exploits Jensen

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Shannon Divergence (JSD) to incorporate semantic information for edge-map generation. Here we presented two approaches for generating the semantic edge-map by JSD. In the first approach the JSD is directly used to distinguish structural edge and non-edge pixels. In the second approach by exploiting JSD we proposed some novel features for discriminating structural edge and non-edge pixels. The first approach has one significant parameter that needs to be set manually for different images. On the other hand, the second approach reduced the parameter selection into four discrete options, which make it significantly less parameter dependent. Both the approaches generated the semantic edge-map in single iteration.

The key motivation of this approach is taken from the fact that if a line is passed through the different objects on a perfectly smoothed image as shown in Figure 3-1(a), the intensity distribution of the pixels on the image associated to the different portions of the line either follow step distribution or uniform distribution. The pixels associated to the portions of the line on the boundary regions of two objects follow 'Z' or reverse 'Z' type step distribution as displayed in Figures 3-1(b), and 3-1(d). The portions on a single object follow uniform distribution as displayed in Figure 3-1(c). In the proposed work this fact is incorporated as semantic information for determining whether the pixel is located on the structural edge or not. This chapter makes the following key contributions:

- It exploits JSD to propose novel features for better discriminating structural and textural edge pixels.
- It proposes a less parameter sensitive edge-aware filtering technique.

The next part of this chapter is organized as follows: Section 3.2 details the proposed technique. Section 3.3 discusses and analyzes the experimental findings. Finally, Section 3.4 concludes the chapter.

Figure 3-1: (a) A perfectly smooth image and a line passes through different objects on it, (b) (c) (d) intensity distribution of the pixels on the image associated to the different portions of the line.

3.2 Proposed filtering technique

In this section, a novel structure preserving semantic texture filtering technique is presented. The technique proposed two different approaches to generate the semantic edge-map of the input image by exploiting JS divergence. To remove impulse noises and enhance the discrimination between textural and structural edges on the input image I , first, our proposed technique applied morphological opening ($\delta_{SE}(\varepsilon_{SE}(I))$) and closing ($\varepsilon_{SE}(\delta_{SE}(I))$) operations on I by using a 3×3 structuring element (SE) and generate the pre-processed image J as follows:

$$J = (I + \delta_{SE}(\varepsilon_{SE}(I)) + \varepsilon_{SE}(\delta_{SE}(I)))/3 \quad (3.1)$$

Once the preprocessed image J is obtained, next our proposed technique generates semantic edge-map of the input image.

3.2.1 Generation of semantic edge-map

The success of edge-aware filtering techniques is dependent on the identification of appropriate structural edge pixels on the image. To this end, some recent research focuses on the generation of an edge-map that retains only the structural edges of the input image. Identification of appropriate structural edges of an image is a difficult task and still a challenging research topic. In this subsection, we propose

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two different approaches to generate semantic edge-map of the original image I by exploiting Jensen Shannon Divergence (JSD). In the first approach, JSD metric is directly used and in the second approach novel discriminating features are extracted by exploiting JSD to generate the semantic edge-map for the input image. The particulars of both the approaches are outlined in the following subsections.

3.2.2 Approach I: Generation of semantic edge-map by direct use of JSD metric [110]

In probability theory, the JSD is widely used to measure the dissimilarity between two probability distributions [86]. The lower the JSD score, the closer the two distributions are to one another. It is an extension of Kullback-Leibler Divergence (D_{KL}) to calculate a symmetrical score between two distributions. Let P and Q be the probability distribution of a discrete random variable, the Jensen Shannon-Divergence $JSD(P||Q)$ between the pair (P, Q) is calculated as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} JSD(P||Q) = \frac{1}{2}D_{KL}(P||M) + \frac{1}{2}D_{KL}(Q||M) \\ \text{where,} \\ M = \frac{1}{2}(P + Q) \\ D_{KL}(P||M) = - \sum P \log \frac{M}{P}, \\ D_{KL}(Q||M) = - \sum Q \log \frac{M}{Q} \end{array} \right. \quad (3.2)$$

Where $D_{KL}(P||M)$ computes the Kullback-Leibler Divergence between P and M . In the proposed work, to determine whether a pixel is on a structural edge or not, first, a fixed size square window is defined by considering it as a center pixel. Then within the window, several lines in different directions passing through the center pixel are considered (as shown in Figure 3-2). If spatial distributions of all such lines (i.e., the intensity values of the pixels on the line) are similar to a uniform distribution, then the center pixel is considered to be a non-edge pixel. On the

other hand, if the spatial distribution of any of the lines is more similar to a step distribution then it is considered to be a structural edge pixel. In the proposed work two discrete distributions viz; a step distribution and a uniform distribution are used as reference distributions (as shown in Figure 3-3). The JSD scores computed between the line inside the window and the reference distribution help us to determine whether the pixel is part of the structural edge or not.

Figure 3-2: Four lines horizontal H , vertical V , diagonal D_1 and D_2 passing through the center pixel p within a square window w .

Figure 3-3: Reference (a) step distribution function T_L and (b) uniform distribution function U_L

In greater detail, let J be the preprocessed input image and J_p stands for the intensity value of a pixel p in J . Considering p as the center pixel, a fixed-size square window w is defined. Then inside w four lines viz; horizontal H , vertical V , and two diagonal D_1 and D_2 passing through p are taken (see Figure 3-2). The probability distribution P_H , P_V , P_{D_1} and P_{D_2} associated to the line H , V , D_1 , and D_2 , respectively is computed as follow:

$$P_L(q) = \frac{|J_q - \min(\text{mean}(J_{L_1}), \text{mean}(J_{L_2}))|}{\sum |J_q - \min(\text{mean}(J_{L_1}), \text{mean}(J_{L_2}))|}, \quad \forall q \in L_1 \cup L_2 \quad (3.3)$$

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Where each line $L = H|V|D_1|D_2$ (i.e., $L = H$ or V or D_1 or D_2) is partitioned into two line segments L_1 and L_2 at center pixel p . From equation (3.3) it is seen that if pixel p is in structural edge, then the probability distribution of at least one line (i.e., P_H, P_V, P_{D_1} or P_{D_2}) is more similar to a discrete step distribution. On the other hand, if p is not in structural edge, then the probability distributions of all four lines are more similar to discrete uniform distributions. In the proposed work for each $P_L, (L = H|V|D_1|D_2)$ two discrete reference functions as shown in Figure 3-3 namely uniform function U_L and step function T_L are defined as follow:

$$\left\{ U_L = 1, \forall \text{ pixels} \in L \right. \quad (3.4)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{if } avg(P_{L_1}) > avg(P_{L_2}) \\ T_L = \begin{cases} 1, \forall \text{ pixels} \in L_1 \\ 0, \forall \text{ pixels} \in L_2 \end{cases} \\ \text{else} \\ T_L = \begin{cases} 0, \forall \text{ pixels} \in L_1 \\ 1, \forall \text{ pixels} \in L_2 \end{cases} \end{array} \right. \quad (3.5)$$

Where $avg(P_{L_1})$ and $avg(P_{L_2})$ are the average values of P_{L_1} and P_{L_2} respectively. Let for a line L (i.e., $L = H|V|D_1|D_2$), Q_L and R_L be the probability density function of the step function T_L and the uniform function U_L , respectively. If p is in structural edge then the spatial distribution of at least one line among four lines will be more similar to its step probability density function. Thus, in this work, an edge score S_p^w for the pixel p is computed by taking the minimum JSD between P_L and Q_L as follows:

$$S_p^w = \min_{L=H,V,D_1,D_2} \{JSD(P_L, Q_L)\} \quad (3.6)$$

If p is in structural edge then the edge score S_p^w computed in equation (3.6) will be smaller than the average JSD between P_L and R_L i.e., if $S_p^w <$

$avg_{L \in w} \{JSD(P_L, R_L)\}$ then the pixel p will be in structural edge. Note that one can generate the edge map that contains only the structural edges of the image by applying this criterion for every pixel in J . In that case, the width of structural edges in the edge map will be determined by the considered window size w . To make the width of structural edges invariant to the window w , we also compute the edge score $S_p^{w_5}$ considering a 5×5 window. Then the binary edge map E_b for the image J is generated as follows:

$$E_b(p) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } S_p^{w_5} < avg_{L \in w_5} \{JSD(P_L, R_L)\} \\ & \text{and } S_p^w < avg_{L \in w} \{JSD(P_L, R_L)\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3-4: Approach I: Overall framework of the developed technique

Figure 3-4 illustrates the overall framework of our developed filtering technique by generating the edge-map using approach I and algorithm 2 shows the precise steps of it.

3.2. Proposed filtering technique

Algorithm 2 Approach I: Proposed reduced parameter sensitive image filtering technique

- 1: **Input:** Original Image I
 - 2: **Output:** Filtered Image I_f
 - 3: Generate pre-processed image J using equation (3.1)
 - 4: For a selected window size w
 - 5: **for** each pixel $p \in J$
 - 6: **for** each pre-processed image band $J_c \in J$
 - 7: Compute the binary edge score $E_b^c(p)$ using equation 3.7
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: $E_b(p) = \text{Max}_c(E_b^c(p))$
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: Apply recursive adaptive median filtering using the edge-map E_b to obtain the filtered image I_f as described in Section 2.3.4.
-

3.2.3 Approach II: Generation of semantic edge-map by extracting discriminating features using JSD

In Approach I, the semantic edge-map generated by the developed technique is heavily determined by the window size w which is defined manually. Note that the optimal size of this window varied from image to image. Moreover, for the images with varying scale textures, a single window will not be capable of providing sufficient semantic information. In order to reduce the parameter dependency as well as to incorporate better semantic information for edge-map generation in the second approach we proposed to extract some novel features by exploiting JSD to discriminate structural edge and non-edge pixels. The overall frame work of our developed filtering technique using Approach II is shown in Figure 3-5.

In this approach, each pixel of the preprocessed image is expressed with a features set. These features are extracted in such a way so that they incorporate semantic information of the pixel. To incorporate appropriate semantic information associated to a pixel, first, considering it as a center pixel, multiple square windows of increasing sizes are taken. Then, within each window, four lines passing through the center pixel in different directions are considered (as shown in Figure 3-2). If the spatial distributions of the pixels on all the four lines are

Figure 3-5: Approach II: Overall framework of the developed technique

similar to a uniform distribution, then the center pixel will more probable to be a non-structural edge pixel (i.e., either a non-edge pixel or a textural edge pixel). On the contrary, if the spatial distribution of at least one of these lines is similar to a step distribution then the pixel will more probable to be a structural edge pixel. The JS Divergence between the spatial distributions of the lines passing through the center pixel and the reference distributions are considered as the features of the center pixel. Since features of the pixels are computed by incorporating semantic information of whether they belong to structural edges or not. When the pixels are projected into the feature space, they will form two groups, one for structural edge pixels and the other for non-edge pixels. Thus, a semantic edge-map of is easily obtained by applying a simple clustering technique.

Let the probability density function derived from the uniform function U and the step function T denotes as R_L and Q_L , respectively. If the center pixel p is on structural edge then for at least one $L, (L \in \{H|V|D_1|D_2\})$ (as shown in Figure 3-2) the value of $JSD(P_L, Q_L)$ will be low. Otherwise, for all four lines $JSD(P_L, R_L)$ will be low. To incorporate semantic edge information of pixel p , its features SS_L^p and US_L^p for $L \in \{H|V|D_1|D_2\}$ are computed as follows:

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$$SS_L^p = \{JSD(P_L, Q_L)\}, \quad L \in (H, V, D_1, D_2) \quad (3.8)$$

$$US_L^p = \{JSD(P_L, R_L)\}, \quad L \in (H, V, D_1, D_2) \quad (3.9)$$

Moreover, to define gradient feature of the center pixel p , the weighted Gaussian mean of the line segments L_1 and L_2 is computed as follows:

$$Gmean(L_i) = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{q \in L_i} J_q \times e^{-d^2}, \quad i = 1, 2. \quad (3.10)$$

where, the distance metric $d = \|p - q\|_1$ and $S = \sum e^{-d^2}$. Then the gradient feature MD_L^p for $L \in \{H|V|D_1|D_2\}$ is defined as:

$$MD_L^p = |(Gmean(J_{L_1}) - Gmean(J_{L_2}))|, \quad L \in (H, V, D_1, D_2) \quad (3.11)$$

Inside window w , considering each of the four lines (i.e., $L = H, L = V, L = D_1$, and $L = D_2$) equations (3.8), (3.9) and (3.10) computes the feature value SS_L^p , US_L^p and MD_L^p , respectively. If p is a structural edge pixel then at least one direction (i.e., for one line) the value of SS_L^p , US_L^p , and MD_L^p will be low, high, and high, respectively. If p is a non-structural edge pixel then all four directions (i.e., for all the four lines) value of US_L^p will be low. To discriminate the structural and non-structural edge pixels into the feature space, in this research we proposed two models by taking different combinations of the features SS_L^p , US_L^p and MD_L^p as follows:

Model I: This model is proposed for texture smoothing. In this model the feature set F_w^1 for the window w is generated by giving more emphasis on US_L^p and MD_L^p than SS_L^p by applying non linear stretching on SS_L^p using the sigmoid function (

$\frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$) as follows:

$$F_w^1(p) = \begin{cases} (US_L^p + MD_L^p) \times (1 + e^{-(SS_L^p)}) & \text{if } (SS_L^p \leq \text{avg}_{L \in w} \{US_L^p\}) \\ 0, & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.12)$$

The four components (features) of F_w^1 that represent a pixel p of the image are generated by considering the lines L as H, V, D_1 , and D_2 inside the window w .

Model II : This model is proposed for preserving structural small details. In this model the feature set F_w^2 for the window w is generated by giving more emphasis on SS_L^p than US_L^p and MD_L^p by applying non linear stretching on $(US_L^p + MD_L^p)$ using the sigmoid function ($\frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$) as follows:

$$F_w^2(p) = \begin{cases} SS_L^p \times (1 + e^{-(US_L^p + MD_L^p)}) & \text{if } (SS_L^p > \text{avg}_{L \in w} \{US_L^p\}) \\ 0, & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.13)$$

The four components (features) in F_w^2 that represent a pixel p on the image are generated by considering the lines L as H, V, D_1 , and D_2 inside the window w .

In both the models, the feature set generated from a single window will not provide enough semantic information. To capture better semantic information, in this work multiple windows of increasing sizes are taken, and for each window, four features are generated by using Eq. (3.11) or Eq. (3.12). Thus, for a gray scale image considering n number of windows, the developed technique generates $4 \times n$ features and for an image of c bands, it generates $4 \times n \times c$ features. Since features of the pixels are computed by incorporating semantic information of whether they belong to structural edges or not. When the pixels are projected into $R^{4 \times n \times c}$ dimensional feature space, they will be formed two clusters, one for structural edge pixels and the other for non-edge pixels. Thus, applying k-means

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clustering with $k = 2$, can easily produce a semantic-aware binary edge-map for the input image. Figure 3-6 displays the edge-maps produced by applying the developed Model I and Model II as well as the popular Sobel operator, Prewitt operator and Canny algorithm. From these figures one can see that the traditional edge detection models are completely failed to discriminate structural and textural edges. Whereas, both the proposed models are showed their robustness to discriminate structural and textural edges. Furthermore, from this figure one can see that Model I is better for texture smoothing, whereas Model II is suitable for preserving small structural details.

3.2.4 Generation of filtered image

Either using Approach I or Approach II once the semantic edge-map is obtained, the recursive edge-aware adaptive median filter developed in Chapter 2 is applied to produce the filtered image. Figure 3-7 shows the semantic edge-maps and the filtered images generated by the approach II of the proposed technique.

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To validate the proficiency of our developed technique, in this section the filtered images generated by considering the semantic edge-maps produced by Approach I and Approach II are analyzed. The particulars of the experimental findings for each of the Approach are given in the next subsections.

Figure 3-6: Input images (a)(b)(c)(d)(e)(f) and their corresponding edge-maps generated by Model I (a1)(b1)(c1)(d1)(e1)(f1), Model II (a2)(b2)(c2)(d2)(e2)(f2), Sobel operator (a3)(b3)(c3)(d3)(e3)(f3), Prewitt operator (a4)(b4)(c4)(d4)(e4)(f4), and Canny edge detection algorithm (a5)(b5)(c5)(d5)(e5)(f5).

Figure 3-7: Original image of Pompeii Marine Life mosaic, corresponding edge-maps, and filtered images produced by Model I and Model II of the proposed technique

Algorithm 3 Approach II: Proposed reduced parameter sensitive image filtering technique

- 1: **Input:** Original Image I
 - 2: **Output:** Filtered Image I_f
 - 3: Generate pre-processed image J using equation (3.1)
 - 4: Select $W_j, j = 1|2|3|4$
 - 5: **for** each pixel $p \in J$
 - 6: **for** each pre-processed image band $J_c \in J$
 - 7: **for** each window $w \in W_j$
 - 8: Compute feature set $F_w^1(p)$ for Model I and $F_w^2(p)$ for Model II by
 - 9: using equation (3.12) and equation (3.13), respectively.
 - 10: $F_c^1(p) = \sqcup_w F_w^1(p)$ and $F_c^2(p) = \sqcup_w F_w^2(p)$
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: $F^1(p) = \sqcup_c F_c^1(p)$ and $F^2(p) = \sqcup_c F_c^2(p)$
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: **end for**
 - 15: // \sqcup is vector concatenation operator //
 - 16: Project all the pixels into the feature space either using $F^1(p)$ or $F^2(p)$ or both $F^1(p) \sqcup F^2(p)$.
 - 17: Generate edge-map E_b by applying 2-means clustering in the feature space.
 - 18: Apply recursive adaptive median filtering using the edge-map E_b to obtain the filtered image I_f as illustrated in Section 2.3.4.
-

3.3.1 Results: Filtered image obtained from the edge-map produced by Approach I

Figure 3-8: Comparative results of a mosaic floor image: (a) Original image and zoomed portions of it. Filtered images with best possible parameters and its respective SSIM Values obtained by (b) Reg-Cov ($k = 15, ps = 6, \sigma = 0.2$) [SSIM = 0.36] [72] (c) BTF ($k = 9, n_{itr} = 7$) [SSIM = 0.37] [32], (d) SATF ($ss = 3, sr = 0.1, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$) [SSIM = 0.44] [69], (e) SATV ($\lambda = 1.25$) [SSIM = 0.32] [125], (f) RILS ($\lambda = 1.5, \gamma = 50/255, n_{itr} = 15$) [SSIM = 0.25] [91], (g) GISF ($\alpha = 0.75, \lambda = 1.25, n_{itr} = 10$) [SSIM = 0.45] [92], and (h) Proposed ($w = 11 \times 11, n_{itr} = 5$) [SSIM = 0.51] techniques.

To validate Approach I of the developed technique, the filtered image generated from the edge-map produced by it is compared with the filtered images provided by six structure preserving filtering techniques of state-of-the-art such as Reg-Cov [72], bilateral texture filtering (BTF) [32], scale-aware texture filtering (SATF

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) [69], structure adaptive total variation (SATV) [125], real-time iterative least square (RILS) [91], and generalized image smoothing framework (GISF) [92]. The first two (i.e., Reg-Cov [72] and BTF [32]) are textural feature based, next two (i.e., SATF [69] and SATV [125]) are structural edge based and last two (i.e., RILS [91] and GISF [92]) are learning based texture filtering techniques. Comparison with these techniques is carried out qualitatively on the basis of how much they are effective to differentiate texture and structure by smoothing out fine details of textures while preserving the significant structures. Structural Similarity (SSIM) [136] is calculated for a quantitative comparison.

Figure 3-9: (a)(c)(e)(g)(i) Original images with different types of textures and structures, (b)(d)(f)(h)(j) Corresponding filtered images generated by the proposed technique.

Figure 3-8 displays the filtering results attained by the developed as well as the state-of-the-art methods for the floor image. By examining the zoomed-in sections of the filtered images produced by all these methods, it is evident that our method surpasses the other compared methods in both respects: i) texture smoothing and ii) preserving the significant structures. From this figure, it is

apparent that the first two textural feature based methods i.e., Reg-Cov [72] and BTF [32] are performing overall smoothing well but from the zoomed part it is seen that they blurred the edges while preserving the smaller structure. The edge aware techniques, SATF [69] produce poor smoothing results. Whereas SATV [125] blurred the edges of the smaller structure. The RILS [91] and GSF [92] both blurring the smaller structural objects. In contrast, our developed method is equally effective in texture smoothing of varying scales as well as preserving the significant structure of different sizes. In contrast to the other considered methods, instead of blurring, the developed method sharpens the structural edges of the filtered image . It is capable of preserving the small structural details, like alphabets and light sources on the floor image more prominently than the others. The SSIM values are also proclaiming the better preservation of structural similarity by the developed technique. To further evaluate the effectiveness of it, we have applied to a wide variety of images across different categories and sizes of textural patterns and obtained satisfactory results. The filtering results obtained from a few of such images are shown in Figure 3-9. These results show the potentiality of our technique for filtering varieties of images.

Parameter analysis: The semantic edge-map generated by Approach I is heavily determined by the window size w (i.e., the fixed size square window for considering lines in different directions within it) which is defined manually. Note that the optimal size of this window varied from image to image. Moreover, for the images with varying scale textures, a single window will not be capable of providing sufficient semantic information. Thus the success of the technique is significantly dependent on the parameter w and finding its optimal value is difficult task. In Approach II we try to reduce the drawbacks of Approach I by extracting discriminating features using JSD.

3.3.2 Results: Filtered image obtained from the edge-map produced by Approach II

In this section, we first demonstrate our developed technique's robustness with respect to its parameters. Subsequently, we assess the efficiency of the developed technique through qualitative and quantitative outcomes contrasting with multiple state-of-the-art methods.

3.3.2.1 Parameters setting

In this approach for edge-map generation each pixel is expressed with a set of feature and these features are generated by considering multiple windows of increasing size. As the feature values rely on the window size, it is important to consider appropriate windows for generating the features of the pixels. In this work to consider appropriate windows, a subset $\{2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34\}$ from Fibonacci series is selected. Then by taking four consecutive elements of it, four subsets $W_1 = \{2, 3, 5, 8\}$, $W_2 = \{3, 5, 8, 13\}$, $W_3 = \{5, 8, 13, 21\}$ and $W_4 = \{8, 13, 21, 34\}$ are formed. And then looking into the kind of texture present on the input image one of these four subsets is chosen to define the windows for feature generation. For example, if the subset W_2 is chosen, the windows of sizes $(2 \times W_2 + 1)$ i.e 7×7 , 11×11 , 17×17 , and 27×27 are used to generate the features of each pixel. In this research, for the input images of having fine-scale textural details W_1 or W_2 and for the image of having large-scale textural details W_3 or W_4 is chosen for feature generation. As a result, in edge-map generation step of the proposed approach only the parameter w , where $w = \{W_1|W_2|W_3|W_4\}$ is needs to be selected manually. The radius of the windows are taken from The Fibonacci numbers as because the series grows exponentially with a non-uniform spacing, but their ratios converges to the golden ratio (approximately 1.618). This work well in generating semantic feature in variety of scales.

In the proposed filtering technique except the parameter w of edge-map generation step, all the other parameters are manually set with fixed values irrespective of the input images. Depending on the kind of input image only the w parameter is required to be set manually among four discrete options. This represents a significant advantage of the our technique over other state-of-the-art methods. It provides satisfactory results for varieties of images with minimal manual fine tune of its parameters. Note that the filtering results of most of the existing state-of-the-art methods are highly relied on one or multiple parameters which are required to fine tune manually within a continuous interval.

3.3.2.2 Qualitative Comparison

To evaluate the performance of our technique, it is contrasted with six state-of-the-art structure-preserving filtering techniques including Reg-Cov [72], BTF [32], SATF [69], SATV [125], RILS [91], and GISF [92]. Figure 3-10 shows the filtered images generated by applying various techniques for a floor image. By looking at the zoomed areas of the image one can observe that contrast to the state-of-the-art techniques the developed technique performed superior in terms of both, structure preserving and texture smoothing. The textural feature based techniques Reg-Cov [72] and BTF [32], and the structural edge-aware techniques SATF [69] and SATV [125], blurred the edges while smoothing smaller structures.

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Figure 3-10: Comparative results for Mosaic Floor I image: (a) Input image and some highlighted portions of it. Filtered images produced by applying (b) Reg-Cov ($k = 15, ps = 6, \sigma = 0.2$) [72] (c) BTF, $k = 9, n_{itr} = 7$ [32], (d) SATF $ss = 3, sr = 0.1, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$ [69], (e) SATV, $\lambda = 2.5$ [125], (f) RILS $\rho_{smooth} = 3, \rho_{sharp} = 5$ [91], (g) GISF, $\lambda = 50, \gamma = 20/255, n_{itr} = 15$ [92], (h) Proposed Model I, ($w = W_2$), and (i) Proposed Model II, ($w = W_3$) techniques.

Figure 3-11: Comparative results for Mosaic Floor II image: (a) Input image. Filtered images produced by applying (b) Reg-Cov ($k = 15, ps = 6, \sigma = 0.2$) [72] (c) BTF, ($k = 9, n_{itr} = 7$) [32], (d) SATF ($ss = 3, sr = 0.1, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$) [69], (e) SATV, ($\lambda = 2.5$) [125], (f) RILS ($\rho_{smooth} = 3, \rho_{sharp} = 5$) [91], (g) GISF, ($\lambda = 50, \gamma = 20/255, n_{itr} = 15$) [92], (h) Proposed Model I, ($w = W_2$), and (i) Proposed Model II, ($w = W_3$) techniques.

Figure 3-12: Comparative results for Mosaic Floor III image: (a) Input image. Filtered images produced by applying (b) Reg-Cov ($k = 15, ps = 6, \sigma = 0.2$) [72] (c) BTF, ($k = 9, n_{itr} = 7$) [32], (d) SATF ($ss = 3, sr = 0.1, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$) [69], (e) SATV, ($\lambda = 2.5$) [125], (f) RILS ($\rho_{smooth} = 3, \rho_{sharp} = 5$) [91], (g) GISF, ($\lambda = 50, \gamma = 20/255, n_{itr} = 15$) [92], (h) Proposed Model I, ($w = W_3$), and (i) Proposed Model II, ($w = W_3$) techniques.

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Figure 3-13: (a)(c)(e)(g)(i) Input images with a wide range of diverse textures and structures, and (b)(d)(f)(h)(j) Respective filtered images obtained by applying developed method.

Whereas, Model I and Model II of the proposed approach able to preserve the important structures of various sizes, as well as better smoothing the textures present at varying scales. Moreover, in contrast to the state-of-the-art techniques, both the models of the developed technique produced sharpen filtered images without distorting the structural edges. Small structural details such as alphabets and light sources as shown in Figure 3-11 are better preserved by the developed technique. To establish the robustness of the developed technique, we tested it with a wide varieties of images containing diverse types of regular and irregular textural patterns and always found satisfactory results. Figures 3-10, 3-11, 3-12, and 3-13 show some of the filtered images provided by the developed technique. By looking at these figures, it can be observed the robustness of our technique for smoothing varying scale regular and irregular textures, as well as for preserving significant structural details.

Table 3.1: The scores of the IQA metrics SSIM, MSSIM, MI and PIQE of the filtered images produced by the different techniques. The bold font are indicating the best scores of these IQA metrics.

<i>Images</i>	<i>Metrics</i>	<i>RegRov [72]</i>	<i>BTF [32]</i>	<i>SATF [69]</i>	<i>SATV [125]</i>	<i>RILS [91]</i>	<i>GISF [92]</i>	<i>(Model I, II)</i>
Mosaic Floor I PIQE=16.28	SSIM	0.62	0.68	0.68	0.69	0.60	0.72	0.76 , 0.71
	MSSIM	0.58	0.78	0.79	0.78	0.68	0.79	0.88 , 0.82
	MI	1.74	1.91	1.90	1.97	1.67	1.73	2.16, 2.26
	PIQE	91.62	89.57	88.70	81.28	100	81.41	69.14 , 75.10
Mosaic Floor II PIQE=37.27	SSIM	0.36	0.38	0.43	0.31	0.26	0.44	0.45, 0.46
	MSSIM	0.58	0.61	0.68	0.62	0.54	0.62	0.66, 0.68
	MI	2.30	2.27	2.08	2.00	1.91	2.31	2.46, 2.55
	PIQE	86.78	88.85	87.05	84.74	88.19	86.26	82.72 , 83.86
Mosaic Floor III PIQE=15.18	SSIM	0.49	0.44	0.57	0.51	0.47	0.53	0.64 , 0.59
	MSSIM	0.58	0.74	0.70	0.51	0.50	0.53	0.78 , 0.70
	MI	2.03	2.07	2.50	2.45	2.37	1.89	2.65, 2.75
	PIQE	86.74	88.86	89.96	86.47	100	87.91	78.34 , 80.00

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3.3.2.3 Quantitative Comparison

To demonstrate the robust performance of the developed technique, in this experiment a quantitative comparison between the filtered images produced by the developed and the state-of-the-art techniques is carried out. Here, for quantitative comparison three subjective IQA metrics like SSIM [136], MSSIM, MI [131] and a subjective no-reference metric PIQE [132] are used, where SSIM and MSSIM both range from $[0, 1]$, and MI ranges from $[0, \log(m \times n)]$, where $m \times n$ represents the image size, PIQE ranges from $[0, 100]$. For all the three SSIM, MSSIM, and MI, higher values indicate better performance, whereas for PIQE, a lower value indicates better quality. The scores of these IQA measures are reported in Table 3.1. From the table it can be observed that both the models of the developed technique yielded superior results contrast to the existing state-of-the art techniques. This once again confirms the robustness of the developed technique..

3.3.2.4 Applications

Structure-preserving filtering techniques find diverse numerous applications in image processing and analysis. These techniques can be employed as either pre-processing or post-processing steps for various tasks, including image denoising, image enhancement, tone mapping, image abstraction, image classification, image segmentation, and more. The following subsections describe some of the key applications of the proposed filtering technique.

Image denoising: In Figure 3-14 it is showing the noisy and corresponding denoised images produced the proposed filtering technique. The filtered images are showing that it preserving structures well while removing noises.

Figure 3-14: (a)(d)(g) Original images, (b)(e)(h) images with Gaussian noise ($\sigma = 0.03$) and their corresponding (c)(f)(i) denoised images obtained by applying proposed filtering technique.

Detail enhancement: Here the images in Figure 3-15 are showing the original images and their corresponding enhanced images using proposed filtering. The filtering technique first decompose the input image into two part- one is smoothed image and other is textural details. By adding the textural details to the origi-

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nal image we can get the final enhanced image. The enhanced images are more prominently showing the textural details.

Figure 3-15: (a)(c)(e) Original images and their corresponding (b)(d)(f) enhanced images obtained by the proposed technique.

Tone mapping: Figure 3-16(a)(c) showing LDR image (RGB) tone mapped

from two HDR image by Farbman techniques [47] and Figure. 3-16(b)(d) shows the corresponding tone mapped RGB version produced by using the proposed filtering technique. We have simply replaced the proposed filtering technique in place of bilateral filtering (BF) in Durand’s method [49] with $\gamma = 0.5$.

Figure 3-16: (a)(c) RGB tone mapped images generated by Farbman techniques [47] and (b)(d) RGB tone mapped images generated by integrating proposed filtering technique in [49].

All these above three results on different applications showing that the proposed technique providing satisfactory results. Also by comparing the results for these applications with the previous technique proposed in Chapter 2, it can be seen that for image denoising and image enhancement technique proposed technique in Chapter 2 perform better whereas in tone mapping application proposed technique in this chapter is doing better.

3.3.2.5 Computational analysis

The computational complexity of the developed technique is determined by the semantic-aware edge-map generation and the recursive median filter used to produce the filtered image. For an image of size $M \times N$, if S_1 is the size of the largest window used to extract the features of the pixels, the computational complexity of the generation of semantic-aware edge-map is $\theta(M \times N \times S_1)$. The recursive median filter used by the proposed technique define adaptive window L_w and w_s^a for filtering non-edge and edge pixels, respectively. The complexity of the recursive

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median filter is $\theta(M \times N \times S_2)$, where $S_2 = \max\{L_w, w_s^a\}$. Thus the computational complexity of our technique is $\theta(M \times N \times S)$, where $S = \max\{S_1, S_2\}$. table 3.2 is showing the comparative execution time taken by the developed and the state of the art techniques.

Table 3.2: The run time (in seconds) of the state-of-the-art and the technique we developed.

<i>Images</i>	<i>RegRov [72]</i>	<i>BTF [32]</i>	<i>SATF [69]</i>	<i>SATV [125]</i>	<i>RILS [91]</i>	<i>GISF [92]</i>	<i>Proposed</i>
Mosaic Floor I (675 × 900)	510.23	177.95	126.34	11.72	6.204	13.49	306.67
Mosaic Floor II (600 × 800)	415.74	153.46	113.65	11.440	6.01	49.99	216.93
Mosaic Floor III (450 × 600)	232.49	101.58	54.38	7.26	3.46	22.44	108.456

3.3.2.6 Selection of optimal model (Model I or Model II)

The proposed techniques have two main different approaches: the first one is the wise manual parameter (window size) selection, and that parameter needs to be selected depending on the texture sizes in the input image. That is for smaller textural pattern removal, window size may be chosen as smaller as 7×7 to 11×11 , and for the larger size textural images, it may be taken as 15×15 to 21×21 . The second approach is mainly focused on the reduction of this manual parameter selection. This approach has two different models (Model I, Model II) with two different types of feature generation methods. Model I and II have the same parameters set, that is W_1, W_2, W_3, W_4 . These parameters $W_1 = \{2, 3, 5, 8\}$, $W_2 = \{3, 5, 8, 13\}$, $W_3 = \{5, 8, 13, 21\}$ and $W_4 = \{8, 13, 21, 34\}$ basically represent a range of window sizes, where selecting W_1 or W_2 suitable for the images (like in Figure 3-11) having smaller objects to be preserved and selecting W_3 or W_4 is preferable for the images (like in Figure 3-7) having smaller insignificant objects to be removed. The basic differences between the two models are that Model I is preferable for maximal smoothing, whereas Model II is suitable for preserving most of the objects while smoothing less compared to Model I.

3.4 Conclusions

Structural edge-aware features are more robust than the textural features for filtering images of having varying scale irregular textures. However, the effectiveness of edge-aware filtering techniques dependent on their ability to identify the right structural edges.

In this chapter, we exploits JSD to incorporate semantic information for edge-map generation. We presented two approaches for generating the semantic edge-map. In Approach I, JSD is directly used to distinguish structural edge and non-edge pixels. In Approach II, by exploiting JSD we extracted some novel discriminative features for representing structural edge and non-edge pixels. Then by projecting the pixels into the feature space our approach applied k-means clustering to generate a semantic-aware edge-map. Once the edge-map is obtained either by applying Approach I or Approach II, an edge-aware adaptive recursive median filter is used to generate the filtered image. The first approach has one significant parameter that needs to be set manually for different images. On the other hand, the second approach reduced the parameter selection into four discrete options, which make it significantly less parameter dependent. However, both the approaches generated the semantic edge-map in single iteration.

The performance of the our developed technique is demonstrated by contrasting it with several state-of-the-art methods using a diverse set of images consisting of varying scale regular and irregular textures. The proposed technique can achieve several competing objectives that cannot be accomplished by using a single existing method, such as detecting and smoothing textures, protecting corners and other areas that are easy to overlook, avoiding over-blurring and/or over-sharpening artifacts, and maintaining structural edges.

List of publications from this chapter

Journals

1. Pradhan, K., Patra, S. Reduced parameter sensitive edge-aware semantic image filtering. (*Under review to ‘Pattern Analysis and Applications’*).

Conference

1. K. Pradhan and S. Patra, “ Structure Preserving Semantic Texture Filtering,” 2022 IEEE Calcutta Conference (CALCON), Kolkata, India, 2022, pp. 283-287, doi: 10.1109/CALCON56258.2022.10060620.

Chapter 4

A semantic edge-aware parameter efficient image filtering technique

4.1 Introduction

To incorporate semantic information for edge-map generation, the technique presented in Chapter 2 and the Approach I of Chapter 3, both considered a fixed size window which is manually defined by trial and error method. Although for the images of having regular texture it is possible to define a suitable window but it is impossible for varying scale irregular textures. Thus, for the images of having varying scale irregular textures, both the techniques may have failed to incorporate sufficient semantic information to generate the semantic edge-map. In order to mitigate the drawbacks of both the techniques in this chapter, we proposed another parameter efficient filtering technique by exploiting the properties of these two techniques.

To incorporate semantic information for better discriminating the structural and textural edges, in this chapter, we introduce a novel approach. Our method generates the edge-map of the input image by exploiting semantic information in two phases. In the first phase, a semantic gradient image (SGI) is generated by analyzing the local distribution of input image and morphological

gradient image. In the second phase, with the help of the generated SGI, the size of the windows are defined to exploit JS Divergence for generating the semantic edge-map. Once the edge-map is obtained, the edge-aware adaptive recursive median filter proposed in Chapter 2 is utilized to produce the filter image. Although the proposed filtering technique required to define multiple windows, the size and shape of most of these windows are either automatically defined or kept fixed, irrespective of the consider input images. There exists only a pair of windows that needed to be fixed manually by choosing one of the four options. Our technique provides satisfactory results for a diverse set of input images with minimal fine-tuning of its parameters, which is an important benefit of the proposed technique in contrast to the current state-of-the-art techniques. This chapter's key contributions are:

- Proposes a novel technique to incorporate semantic information for edge-map generation.
- Proposes an parameter efficient edge-aware texture filtering technique.

The rest of the Chapter is structured as follows: The proposed technique is described in Section 4.2. Section 4.3 analyses and analyzes the experimental findings. In Section 4.4, a conclusion is determined.

4.2 Proposed filtering technique [112]

To reduce the effects from the impulse noises and textural oscillations we used the equation 3.2 defined in Chapter 3 for generating the preprocessed image J from the input image I . Once the preprocessed image J is generated, our developed technique follows two steps to produce the filtered image. In the first step, it proposes a novel method that generates a semantic-aware edge-map of the input image. Then, in the second step, the adaptive recursive median filter proposed in Chapter 2 is used to produce the filter image.

4.2.1 Generation of semantic-aware edge-map

Figure 4-1: A fixed-size square window and the four lines H, V, D_1 , and D_2 passing through the center pixel p

We proposed a novel method that generates semantic-aware edge-map of the input image. Our method considers semantic information in two phases. In the first phase, for each pixel p , it computes mean gradient and average local skewness to generate the semantic gradient image (SGI). To this end, a set $W = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$ containing increasing size windows are considered. For each window $w_i \in W$, four lines H, V, D_1 , and D_2 passing through the center pixel p in four directions (as shown in Figure 4-1) are taken. To compute the mean gradient MD_W^p of the pixel p in the pre-processed image J , each line $L \in \{H, V, D_1, D_2\}$ inside the windows is partitioned into two equal halves L_1 and L_2 at p and then calculate their average intensity difference as follows:

$$MD_W^p = \frac{1}{|L| \times |W|} \times \sum_W \sum_L |mean(J_{L_1}) - mean(J_{L_2})| \quad (4.1)$$

where $mean(J_{L_1})$ and $mean(J_{L_2})$ represents the average intensity of the pixels on the line segments L_1 and L_2 , respectively. To compute the mean gradient of a pixel equation 4.1 incorporates semantic information by analyzing the local spatial distribution of its neighbor pixels in different directions. The high value of the mean gradient MD_W^p indicates that the pixel p is more probable to be a structural edge pixel, and the low value indicates that it is more probable to be a non-edge pixel.

4.2. Proposed filtering technique [112]

To compute the average local skewness of the pixel p , our technique generates the morphological gradient image J_{mg} as follows [111]:

$$J_{mg} = (\delta_{SE}(J) - \varepsilon_{SE}(J)) \quad (4.2)$$

Considering the pixel $p \in J_{mg}$ as center pixel of each window $w_i \in W$, a local histogram h_{w_i} is constructed by taking into account only the pixels inside the window w_i lie on the four lines $H, V, D1$, and $D2$. Then the average local skewness Sk_W^p of the pixel p is computed as:

$$Sk_W^p = \frac{1}{|W|} \sum_{w_i \in W} \frac{\max(h_{w_i}) - \text{median}(h_{w_i})}{\max(h_{w_i}) - \min(h_{w_i})}. \quad (4.3)$$

To compute the average local skewness of a pixel equation 4.3 incorporates semantic information by analyzing the distribution of its neighbor pixels in morphological gradient image J_{mg} and always provides positive value. High value of Sk_W^p indicates that the pixel p is more probable to be a structural edge pixel and low value indicates that it more probable to be a non-edge pixel. After compute the average gradient MD_W^p and the average local skewness Sk_W^p , the proposed semantic gradient image (SGI) associated to the input image I is generated by combining these two features as follows:

$$SGI(p) = MD_W^p \times Sk_W^p \quad (4.4)$$

MD_W^p and Sk_W^p considers semantic information of a pixel p by analyzing the local distribution of pre-processed image J and morphological gradient image J_{mg} , respectively. Both provided higher values for structural edge pixels and lower values for textural or non-edge pixels. Thus, equation 4.4 combines two different semantic information of the pixels for generating the semantic gradient

image (SGI). Hence, the proposed SGI image is capable of better differentiating the structural and textural edge pixels of the input image. Figures 4-2 (b) and (g) show the semantic gradient images generated by the proposed technique from the input images shown in Figures 4-2 (a) and (f). From these figures one can see that the higher intensity pixels of SGI are associated to the structural edge and the lower intensity pixels are associated to either non-edge or textural edge. Note that for the input image of irregular and varying scale textures, there is a possibility of having some pixels in SGI with high intensity values associated to textural edge pixels. In such situation even SGI provides little information to discriminate structural and textural edge pixels.

Figure 4-2: (a)(f) Original images and their corresponding generated (b)(g) semantic gradient images (SGIs), (c)(h) histograms of SGIs, (d)(i) edge-maps, and (e)(j) filter images.

In order to discriminate the structural edge and non-edge pixels of the input image more accurately, we proposed a novel method that exploits JS divergence to consider semantic information of the pixels by defining appropriate window. Since, the number of structural edge pixels in an image are much smaller than the number of non-edge pixels. The histogram of the SGI is likely to follow

a positive-skewed distribution as shown in Figures 4-2(c) and (h). Thus, the histogram of SGI can be approximated with lognormal distribution by defining its two parameters μ and σ as follows:

$$\begin{cases} f(x) = \frac{1}{x\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(\ln(x)-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \\ \mu = \ln\left(\frac{\nu}{\sqrt{1+\frac{\gamma^2}{\nu^2}}}\right) \\ \sigma = \sqrt{\ln\left(1+\frac{\gamma^2}{\nu^2}\right)} \end{cases} \quad \text{where } x > 0, \sigma > 0 \quad (4.5)$$

The red curves in Figures 4-2(c) and (h) are the lognormal distributions that approximated the histograms of SGIs by estimating μ and σ using the maximum likelihood estimator. The pixels in SGI associated to the left tail and the right tail of the approximated histogram are more certain to be non-edge pixels and structural edge pixels, respectively. The certainty level of the pixels between left and right tails are less. In our work to consider semantic information of a pixel, the size of the window is defined based on its certainty level. Pixels which are certain to be non-edge and structural edge are used in large and small window, respectively and the moderate size windows are used for uncertain pixels. The certainty level of the pixels are defined with help of the approximated histogram. After estimating μ and σ , the histogram of SGI is divided into four intervals $(0, e^{\mu-\sigma})$, $[e^{\mu-\sigma}, e^\mu)$, $[e^\mu, e^{\mu+\sigma})$ and $[e^{\mu+\sigma}, +\infty)$. The intensity values of the pixels in SGI within the first interval $(0, e^{\mu-\sigma})$ and the fourth interval $[e^{\mu+\sigma}, +\infty)$ are more certain to be non-edge pixels and structural edge pixels, respectively. So, the window w_{01}, w_{12}, w_{23} , and w_{34} (such that the size of $w_{01} > w_{12} > w_{23} > w_{34}$) is used to consider semantic information of the pixels associated to the intervals $(0, e^{\mu-\sigma})$, $[e^{\mu-\sigma}, e^\mu)$, $[e^\mu, e^{\mu+\sigma})$ and $[e^{\mu+\sigma}, +\infty)$, respectively. Once the window for each pixel of the input image is defined, the proposed technique exploits JS divergence to consider semantic information for determining whether it belongs to a structural edge or not.

In probability theory, JS divergence is a useful tool for measuring the similarity between two probability distributions. In this work JS divergence is exploited same way as presented in Subsection 3.3.2.3. Lower the value of $JSD(P, Q)$ indicates P and Q have similar distributions. For each pixel p of the pre-processed image J , its corresponding window $w \in \{w_{01}, w_{12}, w_{23}, w_{34}\}$ is used to incorporate semantic information. To this end, considering p as center pixel of w , four lines, namely horizontal H , vertical V , two diagonal $D1$ and $D2$ passes through p as shown in Figure 4-1 are taken. The probability density function of each line H , V , $D1$, and $D2$ is defined as follows:

$$\begin{cases} P_L(q) = \frac{|J_q - \min(\text{mean}(J_{L_1}), \text{mean}(J_{L_2}))|}{\sum |J_q - \min(\text{mean}(J_{L_1}), \text{mean}(J_{L_2}))|}, \\ q \in L_1 \cup L_2, \quad L \in \{H, V, D1, D2\} \end{cases} \quad (4.6)$$

where J_q represents the intensity value of the pixel $q \in L$. The probability density function of at least one of the four lines (i.e., P_H , P_V , P_{D1} or P_{D2}) will be similar to a discrete step distribution if the pixel p is in structural edge. Otherwise, the probability density functions of all four lines will be more akin to discrete uniform distributions. To incorporate such semantic information two reference functions, a uniform function U and a step function T are taken. Let Q_L and R_L denote the probability density functions for the step function T and the uniform function U , respectively. If the pixel p is a structural edge pixel then for at least one line $L \in \{H, V, D1, D2\}$, the distribution of P_L will be similar to the step distribution Q_L i.e., the value of $JSD(P_L, Q_L)$ will be low. If the pixel p is not a structural edge pixel then for all the four lines the distribution of P_L will be similar to the uniform distribution R_L i.e., the value of $JSD(P_L, R_L)$ will be low. In our work such semantic information is exploited to discriminate structural edge pixels and pixels of the input image that are non-edge and generate the binary edge-map E_b as follows:

$$E_b(p) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \min_L \{JSD(P_L, Q_L)\} \\ & \leq \frac{1}{|L|} \sum_L \{JSD(P_L, R_L)\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.7)$$

Figures 4-2 (d) and (i) show the semantic-aware edge-maps generated by the proposed technique.

4.2.2 Edge-aware adaptive median filter

Once the semantic edge-map of the input image is obtained, the filtered image is produced by applying the recursive edge-aware adaptive median filter developed in Chapter 2. Figure 4-2 shows the semantic edge-maps and the filtered images generated the proposed technique. The pseudo-code for this technique is provided in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Proposed parameter efficient image filtering technique

- 1: **Input:** Image I
 - 2: **Output:** Filtered Image I_f
 - 3: Generate pre-processed image J using equation (3.1)
 - 4: **for** each pixel $p \in J$
 - 5: **for** each pre-processed image band J_c
 - 6: **for** each window $w \in W$
 - 7: Compute feature $SGI(p)$ by
 - 8: using equation (4.4) .
 - 9: **end for**
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: SGI is divided into four regions by $(0, e^{\mu-\sigma})$, $[e^{\mu-\sigma}, e^\mu)$, $[e^\mu, e^{\mu+\sigma})$ and $[e^{\mu+\sigma}, +\infty)$, and a set of window sizes $F_1||F_2||F_3||F_4$ are determined for different region.
 - 13: Generate edge-map E_b by applying equation 4.7.
 - 14: Apply recursive adaptive median filtering using the edge-map E_b to obtain the filtered image I_f as described in Section 2.3.4.
-

4.2.3 Parameters of the proposed technique

Although the proposed technique considers several windows but most of them are of fixed-size. In pre-processing step, irrespective of input image, a fixed-size 3×3 square window is used as SE to generate the pre-processed image J . To generate SGI, the proposed technique computes the average gradient and the average local skewness of each pixel by considering semantic information. For the image of having varying scale irregular textures, it is not possible to capture sufficient semantic information by using a single window. To incorporate appropriate semantic information, a set of windows $W = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$ of increasing sizes are considered. The present work suggested to consider only four windows w_1, w_2, w_3 and w_4 to capture semantic information of variety of textures starting from smaller to moderate to larger and the size of these windows are defined by taking 3^{rd} , 5^{th} , 7^{th} , and 9^{th} numbers from the Fibonacci series $[1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34, \dots]$. In our work the window size is calculated using the formula $2x + 1$, where x is a number taken from Fibonacci series. So, irrespective of the considered input image, four windows of size $5 \times 5, 11 \times 11, 27 \times 27$, and 69×69 are used to generate the SGI.

After generating the SGI, to incorporate semantic information for each input image pixel for determining whether it belongs to a structural edge or not, our technique considers one of the four windows w_{01}, w_{12}, w_{23} , or w_{34} . In this research irrespective of the considered input image, the window size w_{01} and w_{34} is fixed to as $(w_{01} = 69 \times 69)$ and $(w_{34} = 5 \times 5)$, respectively. Moreover, depending upon the textures present in the input image, the size of the other two windows w_{12} and w_{23} are manually fixed from four discrete options F_1, F_2, F_3 and F_4 . Where, $F_1 = [w_{12} = 43 \times 43, w_{23} = 27 \times 27]$, $F_2 = [w_{12} = 27 \times 27, w_{23} = 17 \times 17]$, $F_3 = [w_{12} = 17 \times 17, w_{23} = 11 \times 11]$, and $F_4 = [w_{12} = 11 \times 11, w_{23} = 7 \times 7]$ is defined by considering four consecutive pairs of Fibonacci numbers $[21, 13], [13, 8], [8, 5]$ and $[5, 3]$, respectively. Note that the size of windows w_{12} and w_{23} are the only parameter of the proposed technique that needs to be fixed manually by choosing

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one of the four options F_1, F_2, F_3 or F_4 . Irrespective of the input images, the other parameters are either fixed or defined automatically. Conversely, the majority of existing state-of-the-art methods require multiple parameters, and their results are highly sensitive to their parameter values which need to be fine tuned manually within a wide interval. Figure 4-3 shows the filtered images produced by the proposed technique considering the options F_1, F_2, F_3 , and F_4 for a simple cartoon image. From this figure one can see that the options F_3 and F_4 are suitable for preserving smaller details, whereas the options F_1 and F_2 are suitable for smoothing.

Figure 4-3: (a) Original image and the filtered images produced by our developed technique by using the options (b) F_4 , (c) F_3 , (d) F_2 , and (e) F_1 .

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To assess the robustness of the proposed technique, the experiment includes both qualitative and quantitative comparisons with various state-of-the-art techniques.

Figure 4-4: Filtering results of a cross-stitch cartoon image having regular texture: (a) the original image and the filtered images produced by (b) Reg-Cov ($k = 15, ps = 6, \sigma = 0.2$) [72] (c) BTF, $k = 9, n_{itr} = 7$ [32], (d) SATF $ss = 3, sr = 0.1, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$ [69], (e) SATV, $\lambda = 2.5$ [125], (f) RILS $\rho_{smooth} = 3, \rho_{sharp} = 5$ [91], (g) GISF, $\lambda = 50, \gamma = 20/255, n_{itr} = 15$ [92], and (h) Proposed (F_4) techniques.

Figure 4-5: Filtering results of a mosaic image having complex textures and structures: (a) the original image and the filtered images produced by (b) Reg-Cov ($k = 15, ps = 6, \sigma = 0.2$) [72] (c) BTF, $k = 9, n_{itr} = 7$ [32], (d) SATF $ss = 3, sr = 0.1, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$ [69], (e) SATV, $\lambda = 2.5$ [125], (f) RILS $\rho_{smooth} = 3, \rho_{sharp} = 5$ [91], (g) GISF, $\lambda = 50, \gamma = 20/255, n_{itr} = 15$ [92], and (h) Proposed (F_3) techniques.

Figure 4-6: Filtering results of a floor image having irregular texture: (a) the original image and the filtered images generated by (b) Reg-Cov ($k = 15, ps = 6, \sigma = 0.2$) [72] (c) BTF, ($k = 9, n_{itr} = 7$) [32], (d) SATF ($ss = 3, sr = 0.1, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$) [69], (e) SATV, ($\lambda = 2.5$) [125], (f) RILS ($\rho_{smooth} = 3, \rho_{sharp} = 5$) [91], (g) GISF, ($\lambda = 50, \gamma = 20/255, n_{itr} = 15$) [92], and (h) Proposed (F_3) techniques.

Figure 4-7: Filtering results of a bee image having irregular varying scale textures: (a) the original image and the filtered images generated by (b) Reg-Cov ($k = 15, ps = 6, \sigma = 0.2$) [72] (c) BTF, ($k = 9, n_{itr} = 7$) [32], (d) SATF ($ss = 3, sr = 0.1, st = 0.1, n_{itr} = 7, div = 30$) [69], (e) SATV, ($\lambda = 2.5$) [125], (f) RILS ($\rho_{smooth} = 3, \rho_{sharp} = 5$) [91], (g) GISF, ($\lambda = 50, \gamma = 20/255, n_{itr} = 15$) [92], and (h) Proposed (F_2) techniques.

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Figure 4-8: (a)(d)(g)(j)(m)(p) Original images with various textures and structures and their corresponding (b)(e)(h)(k)(n)(q) edge-maps and (c)(f)(i)(l)(o)(r) filtered images generated by the proposed technique.

4.3.1 Qualitative comparison

In this experiment, the quality of the filtered images produced by our developed technique is compared with those generated by six well-known state-of-the-art structure-preserving filtering techniques: Reg-Cov [72], BTF [32], SATF [69], SATV [125], RILS [91], and GISF [92]. In qualitative comparison, the filter images produced by the different techniques are visually analyzed to find out how well the structures and textures present on the input images are discriminated for removing minute details of textures while retaining the key structures.

For varieties of input images, the filtered images obtained by the different techniques are shown in Figures 4-4, 4-5, 4-6, 4-7 and 4-8. Examining these figures reveals that the proposed technique excels in both texture smoothing and structure preservation. For example, the input image shown in Figure 4-4(a) is a simple cartoon image with regular textures and smaller structural details of different colors. The filtered images produced by the different techniques and some zoom portions of these filtered images are presented in Figure 4-4. From these figures, it can be seen that our developed technique better preserves the smaller color details while smoothing out the textural details. Figure 4-5(a) shows another input image with random textures and complex structural details. The corresponding filtered images and some zoomed portions of these filtered images are illustrated in Figure 4-5. Again, from these images, it is evident that, in contrast to the existing state-of-the-art methods, the proposed technique better preserves the smaller structures while smoothing out the textural details. Figures 4-6 and 4-7 show the filtering results for another two input images with varying scale textures. By visually analyzing these results, it can be observed that our developed technique is able to preserve the structures and smooth out the textures much better than most of the state-of-the-art techniques. Note that all the literature techniques considered here have multiple parameters, and their filtering results are heavily determined by these parameters. The measurements of these parameters are varied from im-

4.3. Experimental results and analysis

age to image and needed to be fixed manually within a wide range of continuous interval. To ensure a fair comparison, this experiment uses parameter values from the respective papers where the best results are reported, whenever feasible. Otherwise, the optimal values for these parameters are set manually through trial and error. Whereas, as presented in Section 4.2.3 the size of windows w_{12} and w_{23} are the only critical parameters of the proposed technique that needed to be fixed manually by choosing one of the four discrete options of F_1, F_2, F_3 or F_4 . This appears to be a significant advantage of our developed technique over existing state-of-the-art methods. Our proposed technique is tested on a substantial number of images with a variety of regular and irregular textural patterns and always gets satisfactory results. Figure 4-8 show few more filtering results from our developed technique for different types of input images. From these results, one can observe that our technique accomplishes numerous contradictory aims, such as locating and removing texture, maintaining structural boundaries, safeguarding subtle features like corners, and avoiding over-sharpening and/or over-blurring artifacts.

4.3.2 Quantitative comparison

In this experiment, a quantitative comparison between the filtered images produced by our developed and state-of-the-art techniques are carried out. Here we use three subjective reference IQA metrics: SSIM [136], MSSIM, and MI [131] and one subjective no-reference metric, PIQE [132] for quantitative comparisons, where both SSIM and MSSIM range from $[0, 1]$, MI ranges from $[0 - \log(m \times n)]$, where $m \times n$ is the image size, and PIQE ranges from $[0, 100]$. For the first three indices SSIM, MSSIM and MI, a higher value indicates better performance, whereas a lower value for PIQE indicates better. Table 4.1 reports the scores of different IQA measures computed from the filter images generated by different techniques. From these results, it is evident that the proposed technique consistently yields better IQA scores compared to the existing state-of-the-art techniques.

Table 4.1: The SSIM, MSSIM, and PIQE for the filtered images produced by different techniques. Bold type face indicates the best results.

<i>Images</i>	<i>Metrics</i>	<i>RegRov [72]</i>	<i>BTF [32]</i>	<i>SATF [69]</i>	<i>SATV [125]</i>	<i>RILS [91]</i>	<i>GISF [92]</i>	<i>Proposed</i>
Cartoon- Fig. 4-4 PIQE=44.5055	SSIM	0.5227	0.5772	0.6006	0.6091	0.5017	0.5424	0.6236
	MSSIM	0.5161	0.5401	0.5613	0.5704	0.4276	0.4348	0.5939
	MI	2.9846	2.8573	2.9095	2.5602	2.9771	1.8120	2.9857
	PIQE	66.5025	87.1371	87.1248	82.4621	100	85.5485	53.8407
Fish- Fig. 4-5 PIQE=31.6049	SSIM	0.4968	0.5527	0.6353	0.6759	0.4945	0.4544	0.6924
	MSSIM	0.6909	0.7431	0.8171	0.8284	0.6063	0.5238	0.8522
	MI	1.5275	1.6297	1.7915	1.8397	1.4633	1.6064	1.9401
	PIQE	69.88529	87.2677	84.6146	73.6599	83.8448	80.7166	64.4851
Imagine- Fig. 4-6 PIQE=37.2748	SSIM	0.36	0.38	0.43	0.31	0.26	0.44	0.4583
	MSSIM	0.58	0.61	0.68	0.62	0.54	0.62	0.6551
	MI	2.30	2.27	2.08	2.00	1.91	2.31	2.33
	PIQE	86.78	88.85	87.05	84.74	88.19	86.26	82.6128
Bee- Fig. 4-7 PIQE=16.2815	SSIM	0.49	0.44	0.57	0.51	0.47	0.53	0.5588
	MSSIM	0.58	0.74	0.70	0.51	0.50	0.53	0.76
	MI	2.03	2.07	2.50	2.45	2.37	1.89	2.5107
	PIQE	86.74	88.86	89.96	86.47	100	87.91	72.2437

4.3.3 Applications

As in previous chapter, also in this chapter our developed technique is validated across three different applications: image denoising, image enhancement, and tone mapping.

Figure 4-9: (a)(d)(g) Original images, (b)(e)(h) images with Gaussian noise ($\sigma = 0.03$) and their corresponding (c)(f)(i) denoised images obtained by applying proposed filtering technique.

4.3.3.1 Image denoising

In Figure 4-9, the presented results display both the noisy and the corresponding denoised images achieved through the proposed filtering technique. The filtered image clearly demonstrates its ability to preserve structures effectively while successfully eliminating noise.

Figure 4-10: (a)(c)(e) Original images and their corresponding (b)(d)(f) enhanced images obtained by the proposed technique.

4.3.3.2 Detail enhancement

In Fig. 4-9, the presented images showcase both the original images and their corresponding enhanced versions achieved through the proposed filtering method. The enhancement process begins by decomposing the input image into two components - one being a smoothed image and the other capturing textural details. The final enhanced image is produced by incorporating these textural details into the original image. The enhanced images prominently highlight the textural details, showcasing the performance of our developed filtering technique.

4.3.3.3 Tone mapping

In Figure 4-10(a)(c), two LDR image (RGB) tone-mapped from two HDR images using Farbman's technique [47] is presented. Figure 4-10(b)(d) illustrates the corresponding tone-mapped RGB version generated with the proposed filtering technique. Notably, the proposed filtering technique was seamlessly integrated in place of bilateral filtering (BF) within Durand's method [49] with $\gamma = 0.5$. This replacement demonstrates the impact of our developed technique in the context of tone mapping.

Figure 4-11: (a)(c) RGB tone mapped images by Farbman techniques [47] and (b)(d) RGB tone mapped images by proposed filtering, respectively, from two different HDR images.

4.3.4 Computational performance analysis

The computational complexity of our developed technique is dependent on the algorithm used to generate the semantic-aware edge-map and the recursive median filter. For an input image of size $(M \times N)$, the computational complexity of our algorithm that generates the semantic-aware edge-map is $\Theta(M \times N \times S_1 \log S_1)$, where S_1 represents the size of the largest window in W used to incorporate semantic information. Where skewness calculation for window S_1 takes $\Theta(S_1 \log S_1)$. The computational complexity of the adaptive median filter used in the proposed technique is $\Theta(M \times N \times S_2 \log S_2)$, where S_2 represents the size of the largest window among the adaptive windows L_w and w_s^a automatically define for filtering non-edge and edge pixels, respectively. The complexity of median calculation is $\Theta(S_2 \log S_2)$. Therefore, the overall computational complexity associated with our approach is $\Theta(M \times N \times (S_1 \log S_1 + S_2 \log S_2))$.

4.3.5 Limitations

The method begins with computing a morphological semantic gradient on input images using a series of increasing window sizes selected from alternate Fibonacci numbers (e.g., 2, 5, 13, 34), corresponding to square windows of sizes 5×5 , 11×11 , 27×27 , and 69×69 . This approach reduces sensitivity to parameter selection by capturing gradients for objects of varying scales, from small to large, making it effective for images with diverse object sizes and scales.

Subsequently, a Jensen-Shannon Divergence (JSD)-based gradient identification is performed in four directions. The window size for this operation is adaptively determined based on the gradient values computed in the initial phase, ensuring that the first layer of operation guides optimal window selection for the second phase. The accuracy of the final edge map depends on the sensitivity of the second phase to the initial semantic gradient computation.

As a two-layer technique, this method effectively handles multiscale edge detection but incurs higher runtime complexity due to its iterative and adaptive processes of two phases.

4.4 Conclusions

The most challenging task in structure preserving filtering is to discriminate important structures from textures, especially when irregular textural patterns with different scales are present. In many cases, spectral and spatial variations of the input image is not sufficient to discriminate structures and textures. In such cases, semantic information may provide additional useful insight. In this regard, the existing methods are very much parameter sensitive. Here, we introduced a novel approach for leveraging the semantic information of the image to enhance the discrimination of structural and textural edges. Our technique first generates a semantic-aware edge-map of the input image by exploiting semantic information. Then an edge-aware adaptive recursive median filter is utilized to generate the final filtered image. Although the developed filtering technique requires multiple windows, the size of most of these windows are either fixed or defined automatically, irrespective of the considered input image. There exists only a pair of windows that need to be fixed manually by choosing one of the four discrete options. The proposed technique provides satisfactory results for a wide selection of input images with minimal fine-tuning of its parameters, which is an important benefit in comparison to the current state-of-the-art techniques. Furthermore, in contrast to the majority of existing techniques, our technique accomplishes numerous contradictory aims, such as locating and removing texture, maintaining structural boundaries, safeguarding subtle features like corners, and avoiding over-sharpening and/or over-blurring artifacts. Furthermore, along with different computer graphics applications, the proposed technique also shows its robustness to incorporate spatial information for image classification.

List of publications from this chapter

Journals

1. Pradhan K, Patra S. A semantic edge-aware parameter efficient image filtering technique. Computers & Graphics. 2024 Nov 1;124:104068. (**IF-2.5**)

Chapter 5

Semantic-aware image filtering: Applications to classification of hyperspectral images and semantic segmentation of natural images

5.1 Introduction

Although the filtered images generated by the filtering techniques provided spatial information, they were seldom exploited for image classification. In this thesis, we proposed several semantic-aware filtering techniques to protect the significant structural elements in the image while removing noises or smoothing textural details. As a result, the filtered images generated by these techniques provided useful spatial information of the input image. In this chapter, we explore spatial information of hyperspectral images (HSIs) for spectral-spatial classification using the filtered images generated by our developed filtering techniques.

The recent development of hyperspectral imaging has enabled numerous applications across various sectors, including agriculture, mining, forestry, and ur-

ban area monitoring. Hyperspectral images (HSIs) contain spectral data spanning hundreds of tiny wavelengths. The curse of dimensionality may result from such high-dimensional data's potential for redundant information [12, 51, 102]. But when carefully investigated using the right methods, the rich spectral information is discovered to be significantly aiding in the precise classification of different land cover types.

It is already established that along with spectral knowledge, incorporating the spatial information of the pixels greatly enhances the classification results of HSIs. The HSI literature includes numerous spectral-spatial classification techniques. One of the fundamental goal of all such techniques is to build a robust model that can capable of considering better spatial information of the pixels. Markov random fields (MRFs) is a tool serves as the foundation for a variety of spectral-spatial HSI classification techniques. This offers a versatile framework for considering spatial information of the pixels on the image that has been widely used with HSI data [57]. Spectral-spatial classification techniques based on sparse representation (SR) constitute another important category. In [52], a shape adaptive fixed region based SR model is proposed to consider spatial information of the pixels. In [44], a multiscale adaptive sparse representation (MASR) model is proposed to incorporate improved spatial information. In [66], unmixing and SR are combined together to extract appropriate spatial information associated to the pixels on the HSIs. In [46], a multiple-feature-based adaptive sparse representation (MFASR) is introduced. In [45], superpixels are employed to incorporate spatial information. Mathematical morphology (MM) is another popular tool widely used for considering spatial information of the image [14]. A large number of morphological operations are available in the MM to include spatial information which are often designed with fixed shaped structuring element (SE) [123]. An extended morphological profile (EMP) for the spectral-spatial classification of (HSIs) is established in [105]. Through variations in the shape and size of the structuring element (SE), it generates multiple filtered images from the HSI. Then, EMP is

constructed by concatenating these filtered images along with the HSI. Attribute filter (AP) is another MM tool that capable of considering geometrical shape of the objects. Instead of EMP, subsequently, an extended attribute profile (EAP) [36] is developed by using attribute profiles (AP) with different thresholds for the HSIs classification. In [16] threshold free EAP is suggested for considering spatial information. In recent times, several models based on deep neural networks have been introduced for HSI classification [41, 57, 148]. Also, sparse representation, MM, and AP based feature sets are now combined in deep ANN and CNN models for HSI classification [31, 78, 144].

Structure preserving image filtering is a well known approach used to prevent integrity of the structures of the objects of images while removing the noises or smoothing the textures. The effectiveness of such filtering techniques is assessed by how efficiently they are capable of removing noise or smoothing the textures with the minimum distortion of the structures of objects present on the images. The recent research focuses on the development of semantic-aware filtering techniques that incorporate the semantic information of the images to better differentiate structures and textures. Although the filtered images of such advanced techniques provided better spatial information, they are seldom exploited for image classification. In this chapter, to show the impact of our developed filtering approaches for incorporating spatial information, an extended semantic filtered profile (ESFP) is created by combining the filtered images generated by our technique. Then the constructed profile ESEP is utilized for the spectral-spatial classification of HSI. To assess its effectiveness, we compared our proposed profile against several recent state-of-the-art techniques using three real hyperspectral datasets.

In addition to this, the proposed filtering techniques are also tested by applying them to the semantic segmentation of natural images. Semantic segmentation, a fundamental task in computer vision, assigns class labels to every pixel in an image, enabling critical applications in domains such as autonomous driving,

medical imaging, and satellite analysis [6, 11, 26, 68, 73, 77, 100, 151]. Achieving precise boundary delineation and minimizing noise in segmentation maps remain key challenges in this field. Image filtering techniques, particularly edge-aware filters like bilateral and guided filters, have proven essential in overcoming these obstacles. These filters are widely employed in preprocessing to smooth noisy inputs while preserving crucial edges and in postprocessing to refine segmentation outputs, ensuring that predicted boundaries align closely with actual object edges. Moreover, advanced approaches such as Conditional Random Fields (CRFs) and edge-preserving neural architectures have incorporated filtering principles to further enhance segmentation accuracy. By addressing noise suppression, boundary precision, and feature enhancement, image filtering significantly improves the robustness and quality of semantic segmentation in complex real-world scenarios. We compared our proposed techniques with three other different filtering techniques by exploiting two different recently developed semantic segmentation techniques: one is an unsupervised technique called MeanShift++ [68], and the other is a supervised technique named BiSeNet V2 [151]. As the test images, we have taken two simple RGB images that are already used in the previous chapters to show the filtering results, and the other two test images are taken from a well known data set, BSD500 [100] using which the BiSeNet V2 model is also trained.

The next part of the chapter is outlined as follows: Section 5.2 provides details on the construction of the extended semantic filtered profile (ESFP) for each of the filtering techniques presented in this thesis. Section 5.3 describes the HSI datasets used for the experiments. Section 5.4 presents the experimental results of it. Section 5.5 presents an application in semantic image segmentation, while Section 5.6 concludes the chapter.

5.2 Construction of Extended Semantic Filtered Profile (ESFP)

Chapters 2, 3, and 4 of this thesis present four different semantic-aware image filtering techniques. The filtered images generated by these techniques may provide better spatial information of the input image as they considered semantic information. To take into account spatial information for spectral-spatial classification of HSI, first, several filtered images of the considered HSI are generated by applying one of our proposed filtering technique. Then, an extended semantic filtered profile is constructed by concatenating these filtered images. Finally, the spectra-spatial features of the pixels on the profile are used for classification of HSI.

The structure preserving filtering techniques proposed in this thesis excel at filtering out insignificant details and noises while minimizing distortion of the underlying structures in the image. Consequently, the filtered images produced by these techniques offer improved spatial information. Note that to incorporate appropriate semantic information all the four filtering techniques proposed in this thesis used window. Since the optimal value of the window is unknown, to consider a maximum amount of spatial information, one can generate multiple filter images by varying the size of the window. However, when dealing with HSI with hundreds of spectral bands, generating multiple filtered images for each band is not feasible. To circumvent this problem, a reduced set of principal components (PCs) extracted from the HSI, which preserves the most crucial information, is considered. For each of the considered PC, multiple filtered images are produced by varying the size of window. Finally, all the filtered images derived from the considered PCs are combined together to construct an extended semantic filtering profile (ESFP) for the HSI classification.

In more detail, let I represent an HSI with dimensions $M \times N \times P$. To reduce the dimension of I with minimal information loss, Principal Component

Analysis (PCA) is applied to I . Subsequently, the first m principal components (PCs) are chosen to represent the HSI. Depending on the semantic-aware filtering technique applied to these PCs, the extended semantic filtering profiles ESFP I, ESFP II, ESFP III, and ESFP IV are generated as follows:

ESFP I: This profile is constructed by applying the semantic-aware filtering technique proposed in Chapter 2. In this technique a window w is used to consider semantic information from the morphological gradient image. Since the best value of w is unknown, to account for a maximum amount of spatial information, we generate multiple filtered images by varying the size of w . Let I^{pc_i} be the i^{th} PC of HSI I . The proposed filtering technique is applied to I^{pc_i} by considering increasing size window $w = w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$. As a result n filtered images denoted as $I_{w_1}^{pc_i}, I_{w_2}^{pc_i}, \dots, I_{w_n}^{pc_i}$ are generated. The steps is repeated for other PCs. Finally all the generated filtered images are concatenated together to form an ESFP I as follows:

$$I_{ESFP I} = [\{I_{w_1}^{pc_1}, I_{w_2}^{pc_1}, \dots, I_{w_n}^{pc_1}\}, \{I_{w_1}^{pc_2}, I_{w_2}^{pc_2}, \dots, I_{w_n}^{pc_2}\}, \dots, \{I_{w_1}^{pc_m}, I_{w_2}^{pc_m}, \dots, I_{w_n}^{pc_m}\}] \quad (5.1)$$

ESFP II: This profile is constructed by applying Approach I of the semantic-aware filtering technique proposed in Chapter 3. In this technique a window w is used to consider semantic information by exploiting JS divergence. Since the best value of w is unknown, to account for a maximum amount of spatial information, we generate multiple filtered images by varying the size of w . Let I^{pc_i} be the i^{th} PC of HSI I . The proposed filtering technique is applied to I^{pc_i} by considering increasing size window $w = w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$. As a result n filtered images denoted as $I_{w_1}^{pc_i}, I_{w_2}^{pc_i}, \dots, I_{w_n}^{pc_i}$ are generated. The steps is repeated for other PCs. Finally all the generated filtered images are concatenated together to form an ESFP II as follows:

5.2. Construction of Extended Semantic Filtered Profile (ESFP)

$$I_{ESFP II} = [\{I^{pc_1}, I_{w_1}^{pc_1}, \dots, I_{w_n}^{pc_1}\}, \{I^{pc_2}, I_{w_1}^{pc_2}, \dots, I_{w_n}^{pc_2}\}, \dots, \{I^{pc_m}, I_{w_1}^{pc_m}, \dots, I_{w_n}^{pc_m}\}] \quad (5.2)$$

ESFP III: This profile is constructed by considering Approach II of the semantic-aware filtering developed in Chapter 3. In this technique four windows W_1, W_2, W_3 and W_4 are used to consider semantic information. The proposed filtering technique is applied to I^{pc_i} by considering the four windows. As a result 4 filtered images denoted as $I_{W_1}^{pc_i}, I_{W_2}^{pc_i}, I_{W_3}^{pc_i}$, and $I_{W_4}^{pc_i}$ are generated. The steps is repeated for other PCs. Finally all the generated filtered images are concatenated together to form an ESFP III as follows:

$$I_{ESFP III} = [\{I^{pc_1}, I_{W_1}^{pc_1}, I_{W_2}^{pc_1}, I_{W_3}^{pc_1}, I_{W_4}^{pc_1}\}, \dots, \{I^{pc_m}, I_{W_1}^{pc_m}, I_{W_2}^{pc_m}, I_{W_3}^{pc_m}, I_{W_4}^{pc_m}\}] \quad (5.3)$$

ESFP IV: This profile is constructed by considering the semantic-aware filtering developed in Chapter 4. In this technique four options F_1, F_2, F_3 and F_4 are used to consider semantic information. The proposed filtering technique is applied to I^{pc_i} by considering the four options. As a result 4 filtered images denoted as $I_{F_1}^{pc_i}, I_{F_2}^{pc_i}, I_{F_3}^{pc_i}$, and $I_{F_4}^{pc_i}$ are generated. The steps is repeated for other PCs. Finally all the generated filtered images are concatenated together to form an ESFP IV as follows:

$$I_{ESFP IV} = [\{I^{pc_1}, I_{F_1}^{pc_1}, I_{F_2}^{pc_1}, I_{F_3}^{pc_1}, I_{F_4}^{pc_1}\}, \dots, \{I^{pc_m}, I_{F_1}^{pc_m}, I_{F_2}^{pc_m}, I_{F_3}^{pc_m}, I_{F_4}^{pc_m}\}] \quad (5.4)$$

The profiles ESFP I, ESFP II, ESFP III or ESFP IV constructed from HSI I contains rich spatial information. Figure 5-1 show the first PC of the

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Pavia University data set and the five filtered images generated by the filtering techniques presented in Chapter 2 and the Approach I presented in Chapter 3 for the window of sizes 7×7 , 11×11 , 17×17 , 27×27 , and 43×43 . Figure 5-2 show four filtered images generated from the first PC of Pavia University data set by applying the Approach II presented in Chapter 3 and the filtering techniques presented in Chapter 4. These figures, shows that the filtered images generated by the two of our developed technique well preserve the significant objects structures during the smoothing of textures and removing of noises. After constructing the profiles ESFP I, ESFP II, ESFP III, or ESFP IV, the derived spectral-spatial features of the pixels from these profiles are provided as input to a classifier for HSI classification.. The steps for the construction of profiles are summarized in Algorithm 5.

Figure 5-1: First PC of the Pavia University data set and the five filtered images generated from it by applying (a) the filtering technique presented in Chapter 2 and (b) the Approach I presented in Chapter 3, considering the size of windows 7×7 , 11×11 , 17×17 , 27×27 , and 43×43 .

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Figure 5-2: First PC of the Pavia University data set and the four filtered images generated from it by applying (a) the Approach II presented in Chapter 3 and (b) the filtering technique presented in Chapter 4 by using four discrete options.

Algorithm 5 Algorithm to generate the proposed profiles $I_{ESFP \text{ Ior IIor IIIor IV}}$

INPUT- First m PCs ($I^{pc_1}, I^{pc_2}, \dots, I^{pc_m}$) of the HSI I and n windows (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n) of increasing size or n parameter options

OUTPUT- Extended semantic filtering profile: $I_{ESFP \text{ Ior IIor IIIor IV}}$

$I_{ESFP \text{ Ior IIor IIIor IV}} = \Phi,$

For $i=1$ to m do

For $j=1$ to n do

Generate the filtered image $I_{w_j}^{pc_i}$ or $I_{W_j}^{pc_i}$ or $I_{F_j}^{pc_i}$ by applying presented filtering respectively

$I_{ESFP \text{ Ior IIor IIIor IV}} = \sqcup I_{w_j}^{pc_i}$ or $I_{W_j}^{pc_i}$ or $I_{F_j}^{pc_i}$

End For

End For

/* \sqcup is the vector concatenation operator */

5.3 Data sets description

Three widely recognized hyperspectral data sets: the Indian Pines data set, the University of Pavia data set, and the University of Houston data set are used to determine the efficacy of our proposed technique. Here are brief descriptions of each of these datasets:

5.3.1 Indian Pines data set

The benchmark data set utilized in this study comprises hyperspectral imagery acquired over the rural landscape in Indian Pines, in northwest Indiana, USA. The data collection employed the Infrared Imaging Spectrometer/Airborne Visible (AVIRIS) sensor, equipped with 220 channels covering a spectral range from 0.2 to 2.4 micrometers (μm). Through preprocessing, the dataset underwent a reduction to 200 spectral bands where 20 water absorption bands are excluded within the ranges of [104-108], [150-163], and band 220. The resultant image has a 20 meters spatial resolution of dimensions of 145 by 145 pixels. The classes, training samples, test samples, ground truth map all the details required for experimental validation are shown in Figure 5-3 and Table 5.1.

Figure 5-3: Indian Pines data set: (a) False color composition; (b) Classes with color code; (c) Training samples; (d) Test samples; and (e) Ground truth map.

5.3. Data sets description

Table 5.1: Class names, labels, as well as training and test samples selected by the IEEE GRSS Data Fusion Committee in 2013 [57], and available ground truths for Indian Pines dataset.

<i>Land Classes</i>	<i>Class labels</i>	<i>Training samples</i>	<i>Test samples</i>	<i>Labeled Samples</i>
Alfalfa	1	50	1384	1434
Corn (No till)	2	50	784	834
Corn (Min till)	3	50	184	234
Corn	4	50	447	497
Pasture/Grass	5	50	697	747
Trees/Grass	6	50	439	489
Pasture (Mowed)/Grass	7	50	918	968
Hay (Windrowed)	8	50	2418	2468
Oats	9	50	564	614
Soyabeans(No till)	10	50	162	212
Soyabeans (Min till)	11	50	1244	1294
Soyabeans (Clean till)	12	50	330	380
Wheat	13	50	45	95
Woods	14	15	39	54
Grass/Trees/Building	15	15	11	26
Steel/Towers/Stone	16	15	5	20

5.3.2 Pavia University data set

Figure 5-4: Pavia University data set: (a) False color composition; (b) Classes with color code; (c) Training samples; (d) Test samples; and (e) Ground truth map.

This hyperspectral dataset was obtained over the urban area of the University of Pavia in Pavia, Italy. It was taken by the Reflective Optics System Imaging Spectrometer (ROSIS-03) airborne optical sensor. This sensor, equipped with 115 channels, 0.43 to 0.86 micrometers (μm) spanned the spectral range.

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Following preprocessing, which entailed the removal of the 12 noisiest bands, the dataset was refined to consist spectral bands of 103. The resulting image possesses dimensions of 610 by 340 pixels showcases a spatial resolution of 1.3 meters. The details of the classes, training samples, test samples, ground truth map required for experimental validation are shown in Figure 5-4 and Table 5.2.

Table 5.2: Class names, labels, as well as training and test samples selected by the IEEE GRSS Data Fusion Committee in 2013 [57], and available ground truths for Pavia University dataset.

<i>Land Classes</i>	<i>Class Labels</i>	<i>Training Samples</i>	<i>Test Samples</i>	<i>Labeled Samples</i>
Asphalt	1	548	6304	6852
Meadow	2	540	18146	18686
Gravel	3	392	1815	2207
Tree	4	524	2912	3436
Metal sheet	5	265	1113	1378
Bare soil	6	532	4572	5104
Bitumen	7	375	981	1356
Brick	8	514	3364	3878
Shadow	9	231	795	1026

5.3.3 Houston University data set

The hyperspectral image of the University of Houston was captured through the Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (CASI) sensor, encompassing both the university grounds and the adjacent urban areas. The CASI sensor, with a 380 to 1050 nanometers (nm) ranged wavelength, equipped with 144 channels. This image features a spatial resolution of 2.5 meters and exhibits dimensions of 349 by 1905 pixels. The details of the classes, training samples, test samples, ground truth map required for experimental validation are shown in Figure 5-5 and Table 5.3.

5.4. Experimental results

Figure 5-5: University of Houston data set: (a) False color composition; (b) Classes with color code; (c) Training samples; (d) Test samples; and (e) Ground truth map.

5.4 Experimental results

5.4.1 Experimental setting

To reduce the curse of dimensionality problem, the first m PCs of the considered HSI which preserve more than 99% information are used to construct the ESFP. For each PC, if n filtered images are generated, then the size of the constructed ESFP will be $m \times n$. In the present experiment regardless of the considered data set first 10 PCs are used to construct the ESFP. Once the ESFP is obtained, for experimental validation random forest (RF) classifier is used. The $m \times n$ spectral-

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Table 5.3: Class names, labels, as well as training and test samples selected by the IEEE GRSS Data Fusion Committee in 2013 [57], and available ground truths for the University of Houston dataset.

<i>Land Classes</i>	<i>Class Labels</i>	<i>Training Samples</i>	<i>Test Samples</i>	<i>Labeled Samples</i>
Grass (Healthy)	1	198	1053	1251
Grass (Stresses)	2	190	1064	1254
Grass (Synthetic)	3	192	505	697
Tree	4	188	1056	1244
Soil	5	186	1056	1242
Water	6	182	143	325
Residential	7	196	1072	1268
Commercial	8	191	1053	1244
Road	9	193	1059	1252
Highway	10	191	1036	1227
Railway	11	181	1054	1235
Parking (Lot 1)	12	192	1041	1233
Parking (Lot 2)	13	184	285	469
Court (Tennis)	14	181	247	428
Track (Running)	15	187	473	660

spatial features of the profile are fed into the classifier for computing classification results. In our experiment, 200 trees are considered to construct the random forest classifier.

In the experiment the ESFP I and ESFP II are constructed by taking five windows of increasing size. The size of these windows is taken from the Fibonacci numbers [1 2 3 5 8 13 ...], which grow exponentially with a non-uniform spacing of numbers, but their ratios converge to the golden ratio (approximately 1.618). The formula used to determine the size of the windows is $2 \times f + 1$, where the value of f is taken from the Fibonacci series [1 2 3 5 8 13 21 ...]. Both the ESFP I and ESFP II are constructed by considering the window of sizes 5×5 , 7×7 , 11×11 , 17×17 , and 27×27 . So the size of both the profiles is $10 \times 5 = 50$. The ESFP III and ESFP IV is constructed by generating 4 filtered images from each PC using the options $W_1|W_2|W_3|W_4$ and $F_1|F_2|F_3|F_4$, respectively. As a results the size of these profiles is $10 \times 4 = 40$.

Figure 5-6: (a) Ground truth map and the classification maps provided by (b) ESFP I, (c) ESFP II (d) ESFP III and (e) ESFP IV for the Indian Pines data set.

5.4.2 Results analysis

In [57], a more challenging training and test samples for the above three described data sets are exercised to compare the overall performance of many state-of-the-art spectral-spatial HSI classification techniques that incorporate spatial information by using MRF, MM, segmentation, sparse representation, and deep neural networks. To show the potential of the proposed approaches, the ESFPs constructed by our four different method are also classified using the same training and test samples as used in [57]. This allows us to measure our developed techniques against the large number of state-of-the-art techniques reported in [57], which include other existing mathematical tools such as MRF, MM, segmentation, sparse representation, and deep neural networks for incorporating spatial information in

HSL.

Figure 5-7: (a) Ground truth map and the classification maps provided by (b) ESFP I, (c) ESFP II (d) ESFP III and (e) ESFP IV for the Pavia University data set.

The results for all three data sets, provided by the numerous spectral-spatial classification techniques are reported in [57]. By looking into these results, we found that three techniques, namely EMEP[56], MFASRC[46], and Gabor-CNN [30], provided significantly better results than the others. To gauge the adequacy of the proposed ESFPs, their classification results are contrasted with those of the three methods. Moreover, the threshold free attribute profile (TEAP) technique

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 5-8: (a) Ground truth map and the classification maps provided by (b) ESFP I, (c) ESFP II (d) ESFP III and (e) ESFP IV for the University of Houston data set.

presented in [16] and the PCA-based edge-preserving filtering (EPF) technique presented in [71] are used for comparison. The average class-wise accuracy (AA), the overall accuracy (OA), the kappa accuracy (κ) and the class-by-class accuracy metrics are used for comparison. where both OA and AA have a range of [0, 100], while κ ranges from [0, 1], with higher values in each metric indicating better performance. Table 5.4, Table 5.5, and Table 5.7 reports the classification results provided by the different techniques for Indian Pines, Pavia University and University of Houston data sets, respectively. Where for the proposed techniques, four different classification models are applied for classifications, *viz* Random forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Sparse Representation Classifier (SRC) and Convolution Neural Network (CNN). Among all these classifiers, RF provides the best results for the proposed approaches. Random Forest outperforms SVM, CNN, and SRC in HSI classification due to its robustness to high dimensionality, built-in feature selection, resilience to noise, and ability to handle limited training data (as the standard train test used here has limited and nonuniform training samples throughout the classes). It models complex non-linear relationships effectively without extensive hyperparameter tuning. While CNNs excel with large datasets and spectral-spatial patterns, RF's simplicity and ensemble learning make it ideal for HSI data with limited training samples. From these tables, it can be observed that for the Indian Pines data set, our proposed ESFP I, ESFP II, ESFP III and ESFP IV provide higher AA than the existing techniques, while ESFP II produces the highest AA of 98.23% and OA of 97.26%. Whereas the best literature method (i.e., MFASRC [46]) yields an AA of 97.25% and an OA of 95.22%. For Pavia University data set, the proposed ESFP II provides the highest AA (97.84%) and OA (95.73%) while the best literature method (i.e., EMEP [56]) results in an AA of 96.57% and an OA of 95.46%. Similar results also observed on University of Houston data set. For this data set, the proposed technique provides classification accuracy higher of 2% and 3% than those of the best TEAP [16] and second best MFASRC [46] literature methods, respectively.

5.4. Experimental results

Table 5.4: The classification results obtained from various techniques using the same training and test samples as those in [57] for the Indian Pines dataset.

$Cl_s./ Acc.$	EMEP [56]	MFASRC [46]	Gabor-CNN [30]	TEAP [16]	EPF [71]	Proposed ESFP I	Proposed ESFP II	Proposed ESFP III	Proposed ESFP IV
Indian Pines- Random Forest (RF) (Trees: 200)									
1	87.43	86.78	84.44	79.77	79.26	87.34	85.98	91.25	85.69
2	95.79	98.98	91.53	90.18	90.31	98.05	99.62	99.16	99.74
3	98.91	98.91	98.77	95.11	95.11	98.91	100	100	100
4	95.53	97.54	94.70	88.81	89.49	94.05	96.20	98.14	94.85
5	95.98	97.70	99.28	96.56	96.27	93.87	98.13	98.70	90.24
6	99.09	99.54	100	99.32	99.32	100	100	100	98.86
7	92.81	94.99	95.84	89.98	89.98	96.13	97.39	95.61	95.86
8	93.13	94.17	90.94	88.88	89.29	93.21	96.69	97.39	93.59
9	87.06	92.55	88.59	86.88	87.23	87.78	96.81	98.09	97.34
10	99.38	98.38	100	98.77	98.15	99.38	100	100	100
11	97.03	99.76	99.34	99.76	99.68	99.43	99.92	100	99.75
12	99.09	98.18	89.66	98.79	98.79	96.48	98.18	99.09	97.27
13	100	100	100	100	100	95.56	100	95.56	97.78
14	94.87	97.44	97.37	97.44	97.44	100	100	98.72	100
15	100	100	100	100	90.91	100	100	100	100
16	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
AA	96.00	97.25	95.24	93.86	93.84	98.01	98.01	98.23	97.09
OA	93.70	95.22	92.84	91.04	90.99	96.41	96.84	97.26	94.59
κ	0.9279	0.9452	0.9161	0.8975	0.8969	0.9588	0.9638	0.9686	0.9380
SVM (C: 1000, gamma: 1, kernel: rbf)									
AA						93.98	93.98	94.19	93.10
OA						87.76	88.15	88.53	86.10
κ						0.8607	0.8652	0.8695	0.8420
SRC (Alpha: 0.01, Cross-Validation Accuracy: 0.9237)									
AA						93.25	93.25	93.46	92.38
OA						88.15	88.55	88.93	86.49
κ						0.8651	0.8696	0.8739	0.8463
CNN (Filters Layer 1: 64, Layer 2: 128, Dense Units: 256, Dropout Rate 1: 0.3, Learning Rate: 0.0001)									
AA						88.32	88.32	88.52	87.49
OA						85.51	85.89	86.26	83.89
κ						0.8400	0.8444	0.8486	0.8218

Table 5.5: The classification results obtained from various techniques using the same training and test samples as those in [57] for the Pavia University dataset.

$Cl_s./ Acc.$	EMEP [56]	MFA SRC [46]	Gabor-CNN [30]	TEAP [16]	EPF [71]	Proposed ESFP I	Proposed ESFP II	Proposed ESFP III	Proposed ESFP IV
Pavia University- Random Forest (RF) (Trees: 200)									
1	96.05	82.95	87.75	93.73	86.29	90.91	96.27	93.58	91.62
2	93.45	56.79	97.25	87.14	80.98	78.62	92.60	96.12	98.89
3	81.37	91.07	70.92	79.12	80.94	58.55	98.02	66.33	89.03
4	99.87	96.36	97.09	98.83	94.88	95.80	98.59	98.12	96.98
5	99.93	97.75	98.83	99.91	100	99.43	100	100	99.64
6	99.26	81.87	64.62	75.15	80.93	97.15	99.91	98.58	86.43
7	99.85	99.39	76.66	99.49	90.42	89.25	97.35	95.31	93.86
8	99.43	95.87	99.05	99.14	90.69	94.99	99.29	93.11	94.96
9	100	92.33	98.36	99.62	94.59	97.86	98.62	98.65	99.12
AA	96.57	88.26	87.83	92.47	88.59	90.25	97.84	93.31	94.68
OA	95.46	74.39	91.62	89.17	85.30	88.88	95.73	94.68	93.33
κ	0.9407	0.6828	0.8914	0.8562	0.8072	0.8568	0.9429	0.9287	0.9300
SVM (C: 1000, gamma: 1, kernel: rbf)									
AA						86.54	93.82	89.47	90.79
OA						80.90	87.14	86.18	84.95
κ						0.7691	0.8464	0.8337	0.8348
SRC (Alpha: 0.01, Cross-Validation Accuracy: 0.9237)									
AA						85.87	93.09	88.78	90.09
OA						81.27	87.53	86.57	85.33
κ						0.7731	0.8508	0.8380	0.8391
CNN (Filters Layer 1: 64, Layer 2: 128, Dense Units: 256, Dropout Rate 1: 0.3, Learning Rate: 0.0001)									
AA						81.33	88.17	84.09	85.32
OA						78.83	84.90	83.97	82.78
κ						0.751	0.826	0.814	0.815

5.4. Experimental results

Table 5.6: The classification results obtained from various techniques using the same training and test samples as those used in [57] for the University of Houston dataset

<i>Cls./ Acc.</i>	<i>EMEP [56]</i>	<i>MEASRC [46]</i>	<i>Gabor-CNN [30]</i>	<i>TEAP [16]</i>	<i>EPF [71]</i>	<i>Proposed ESFP I</i>	<i>Proposed ESFP II</i>	<i>Proposed ESFP III</i>	<i>Proposed ESFP IV</i>
University of Houston- Random Forest (RF) (Trees: 200)									
1	77.78	80.82	87.47	82.03	54.04	82.03	81.67	81.20	81.67
2	76.88	82.52	86.01	85.10	82.24	85.15	83.46	85.06	85.15
3	100	100	78.22	99.90	100	99.98	100	100	100
4	82.77	82.77	85.02	92.10	44.41	92.17	90.06	86.27	91.00
5	96.02	100	99.89	99.80	100	99.89	99.81	99.91	99.91
6	95.80	99.30	89.44	94.60	95.80	99.30	99.30	95.80	95.80
7	72.95	86.29	90.19	85.70	63.53	85.70	73.60	71.55	84.61
8	82.05	68.66	74.44	77.19	45.68	77.19	78.06	79.49	79.11
9	63.17	78.75	84.42	82.40	51.37	82.47	88.86	78.47	82.81
10	67.57	66.60	63.61	57.25	48.55	57.29	68.53	68.24	68.53
11	82.83	81.50	80.06	77.84	90.89	77.84	97.72	95.92	73.34
12	84.53	74.35	87.30	80.90	78.77	80.99	79.06	86.26	76.85
13	73.68	63.86	85.06	70.05	71.57	70.07	69.47	64.91	65.26
14	99.60	100	100	99.50	100	99.59	99.60	100	99.59
15	98.94	100	56.95	99.65	98.94	99.70	99.79	100	99.79
AA	83.64	84.36	82.94	85.33	75.32	85.65	87.24	85.95	85.90
OA	80.83	82.09	84.12	82.82	70.21	83.76	85.47	83.36	83.16
κ	0.7920	0.8058	0.8251	0.8138	0.6773	0.8238	0.8423	0.8183	0.8173
SVM (C: 1000, gamma: 1, kernel: rbf)									
AA						82.13	83.65	82.41	82.37
OA						76.24	77.80	75.88	75.70
κ						0.739	0.756	0.735	0.734
SRC (Alpha: 0.01, Cross-Validation Accuracy: 0.9237)									
AA						81.49	83.01	81.78	81.73
OA						76.58	78.15	76.22	76.04
κ						0.743	0.760	0.738	0.737
CNN (Filters Layer 1: 64, Layer 2: 128, Dense Units: 256, Dropout Rate 1: 0.3, Learning Rate: 0.0001)									
AA						77.18	78.62	77.45	77.41
OA						74.29	75.80	73.93	73.76
κ						0.722	0.738	0.717	0.716

Thus, for all the three data sets the constructed ESFPs are not only provided best classification results, but it also showed better consistency of the results obtained through all the classes and the datasets than the literature methods. For visual analysis, the classification maps generated by our ESFPs are shown in Figures 5-6, 5-7, and 5-8. These results confirmed the superiority of our proposed filtering techniques for incorporating spatial information in HSI classification.

5.5 Semantic segmentation of natural images

Semantic segmentation is a valuable approach for testing the effectiveness of edge-aware filtering in real-time image processing. Edge-aware filters aim to suppress noise while preserving critical boundaries, which is essential for maintaining the visual and structural integrity of real images. By applying semantic segmentation algorithms to both the raw and edge-aware filtered images, the effectiveness of boundary preservation can be evaluated. Metrics like boundary accuracy and edge alignment, combined with visual inspection, help determine whether the filtering retains fine details and sharp edges without introducing over-smoothing or distortions. This ensures the filtered images are optimized for real-time applications where edge fidelity is crucial.

In this section, firstly we have evaluated the proposed filtering techniques on two simple RGB images (without ground truth edge maps), previously used to show the filtering results in the previous chapters, to demonstrate the basic functionality and effectiveness of the methods. Additionally, we tested the techniques on two real test images (with ground truth edge maps) selected from the BSD500 dataset [100], a widely used benchmark image set for image processing tasks like edge detection and segmentation. These real-world images provide a robust basis to analyze the performance of the filtering techniques under more complex and natural conditions, emphasizing their capability to preserve meaningful edges while reducing noise.

5.5. Semantic segmentation of natural images

For this analysis, we have selected two recently developed semantic segmentation techniques to evaluate the edge-aware filtering results. The first is MeanShift++ [68], an unsupervised method that clusters pixels based on spatial and color similarities, making it suitable for evaluating edge preservation without reliance on labeled data. The second is BiSeNet V2 [151], a supervised model trained on the BSD500 [100] training set, which leverages a real-time architecture to produce precise segmentation maps. By using these complementary approaches, we aim to comprehensively assess the performance of the filtering techniques in terms of edge retention and noise reduction across both simple RGB and real-world BSD500 test images [100].

In this evaluation, we used two types of metrics, one is reference based and the other is non-reference based, to quantitatively assess the quality of segmentation for the edge-aware filtered images. This distinction was applied because the first two simple RGB images have no ground truth edge map for reference, while the two test images from the BSD500 dataset [100] include annotated ground truth data. Hence, to evaluate the quality of segmentation for edge-aware filtered images comparatively, we utilized both reference-based and non-reference-based metrics, ensuring comprehensive analysis across images with and without ground truth.

The non-reference based metrics, applicable to all images, include the Edge Preserving Index (EPI) [6] (ranges from 0 to 1, where higher is better) to measure edge retention. Spatial Entropy [26] (ranges from 0 to $\log n$, where n is the number of spatial zones, which also lower is better) to assess the uniformity of segmented regions, Color Homogeneity [11] (ranges from 0 to 1, where higher is better) for evaluating consistency within segments, and Normalized Gradient Deviation (NGD) [77] (lower is better) to determine the preservation of gradient information. Together, these metrics provide a balanced framework to assess edge preservation, semantic coherence, and overall segmentation quality, with optimal

values indicating better performance for each respective criterion. The metrics Spatial Entropy, Color Homogeneity, Edge Precision Index (EPI), and Normalized Gradient Difference (NGD) provide complementary yet often contradictory perspectives on segmentation quality. Spatial Entropy assesses the balance of segment sizes, favoring evenly distributed regions, while Color Homogeneity emphasizes the uniformity within segments, prioritizing smoothness over boundary precision. EPI focuses on accurate edge detection, rewarding sharp and well-defined boundaries but potentially penalizing over-smoothing. In contrast, NGD evaluates the preservation of smooth transitions, often conflicting with EPI by penalizing sharp gradients. These metrics highlight the inherent trade-offs between uniformity, edge accuracy, and smoothness in evaluating segmentation results.

The first two rows of Table 5.7 show the quantitative values for these metrics for two simple RGB image taken from the previous chapters. Where the segmentation is done by the unsupervised MeanShift++ [68] semantic segmentation technique. Figure 5-9 is showing the corresponding images and their comparative segmented images, respectively.

The evaluation reveals distinct strengths across techniques, with the original image of Pompeii Marine Life 5-9(a) excelling in edge preservation ($EPI = 0.4543$) and GISF [92] leading in spatial entropy (1.7366) and color homogeneity (0.4701), highlighting their suitability for structural detail and region uniformity, respectively. The proposed three techniques, particularly the proposed III from Chapter 4, offer a balanced trade-off, excelling in gradient consistency ($NGD = 0.4820$) and achieving the best edge retention ($EPI = 0.2071$) among them while maintaining reasonable spatial entropy and color homogeneity. Proposed III stands out as the most versatile for general-purpose segmentation tasks. Similarly, for the image of the flower in Figure 5-9(i) the proposed I technique produces the overall best balanced semantic segmented map using MeanShift++ [68].

5.5. Semantic segmentation of natural images

The reference-based metrics, applicable to the BSD500 dataset with ground truth, include the F1 Score [6] for Edge (ranges from 0 to 1, where higher is better) for measuring overlap between predicted and true edges, Fragmentation Index (FI) [126] (ranges from 0 to 1, where lower is better) for assessing edge continuity, Normalized Mutual Information (NMI) [9] (ranges from 0 to 1, where higher is better) for quantifying agreement with ground truth, and Hausdorff Distance [73] (ranges from 0 to the diagonal length of input image, where lower is better) for evaluating the proximity of predicted and true boundaries. The metrics F1-Score for Edges, Fragmentation Index (FI), Normalized Mutual Information (NMI), and Hausdorff Distance offer diverse and sometimes conflicting evaluations of segmentation quality. The F1-Score for Edges assesses the overlap between predicted and ground truth edges, prioritizing precision and recall for boundary accuracy. Fragmentation Index (FI) evaluates the structural coherence within segments, penalizing excessive splitting of regions and favoring compactness. Normalized Mutual Information (NMI) measures the consistency between predicted and ground truth labels, emphasizing alignment in segmentation structure without focusing on spatial precision. Hausdorff Distance quantifies the maximum spatial deviation between segment boundaries, focusing on extreme mismatches but ignoring overall accuracy. Together, these metrics reflect trade-offs between edge precision, segment cohesion, label alignment, and boundary deviations, providing a comprehensive yet contrasting view of segmentation performance.

Figure 5-10 shows the semantic segmentation results of two different test images from the well-known dataset BSD500 [100] applying the real-time supervised technique BiSeNet V2 [151]. From the segmented images, it can be seen that the proposed techniques produce an overall balanced segmentation map for both images. The last two rows of Table 5.7 show the quantitative values for these metrics for two test images, respectively.

Table 5.7: The quantitative measure for the segmented image quality using no reference (without ground truth) metrics like Spatial Entropy, Color homogeneity, Edge preserving index (EPI), Normalized gradient deviation (NGD) and reference based (with ground truth) metrics F_1 score, Fragmentation Index (FI), Normalized mutual information (NMI), and Hausdorff distance (HD) of the original images and the filtered images produced by BTF [32], SATF [69], GISF [92] and three proposed techniques of the previous chapters. For semantic segmentation, two recently developed different methods: MeanShift++ [68] and BiSeNet V2 [151]. The bold fonts indicate the best scores of the respective metrics.

<i>Metrics</i>	<i>Original Images</i>	<i>BTF [32]</i>	<i>SATF [69]</i>	<i>GISF [92]</i>	<i>Proposed I [2]</i>	<i>II [3]</i>	<i>III [4]</i>
For two simple RGB images (see Figure: 5-9) without ground truth (By applying MeanShift++ [68])							
Spatial Entropy [26]	1.0357	1.4571	1.0691	1.7366	1.2668	1.1671	1.0770
Color Homogeneity [11]	0.1430	0.2725	0.1284	0.4701	0.2670	0.1687	0.2153
EPI [6]	0.4543	0.1907	0.0941	0.1175	0.2053	0.1909	0.2071
NGD [77]	0.6745	0.5030	0.3711	0.4043	0.4416	0.4989	0.4820
Spatial Entropy [26]	1.4506	1.5083	1.4701	1.6047	1.6758	1.5403	1.3776
Color Homogeneity [11]	0.2295	0.2483	0.2337	0.3390	0.5011	0.2451	0.1025
EPI [6]	0.202297	0.1275	0.1384	0.0994	0.2269	0.1644	0.1604
NGD [77]	0.5132	0.4215	0.437	0.3734	0.5394	0.4705	0.468
For two test images (see Figure: 5-10) with ground truth from the BSD500 dataset [100] (By applying BiSeNet V2 [151])							
F1-Score for Edges [6]	0.4811	0.4811	0.4710	0.4810	0.4381	0.4813	0.4801
Fragmentation Index (FI) [126]	0.8292	0.8323	0.6920	0.6834	0.7507	0.6833	0.6841
NMI [9]	0.0112	0.0110	0.0236	0.0129	0.0137	0.0135	0.0139
Hausdorff Distance [73]	71.45	70.72	72.24	78.24	72.48	70.48	70.72
F1-Score for Edges [6]	0.2677	0.1783	0.1482	0.1479	0.2692	0.2738	0.2739
Fragmentation Index (FI) [126]	0.8577	0.8780	0.9065	0.9099	0.8444	0.8804	0.8413
NMI [9]	0.0204	0.0193	0.0190	0.0226	0.0198	0.0185	0.0186
Hausdorff Distance [73]	121.79	117.44	116.66	111.83	115.52	116.18	118.01

5.5. Semantic segmentation of natural images

Figure 5-9: (a)(i) Original images (Two simple RGB images, those already used in the previous chapters to show the filtering results) and (b)(j) Segmented image from those original images, (c)(k) Segmented image from the filtered images of BTF [32], (d)(l) SATF [69], (e)(m) GISF [92], and (f-h)(n-p) proposed I, II, and III techniques from Chapters: 2, 3, and 4 respectively. Segmented using an unsupervised technique, MeanShift++ [68].

Figure 5-10: (a)(g) Two original test images from BSD500 dataset [100] and (b)(j) segmented images from those original images, (c)(k) segmented images from the filtered images of BTF [32], (d)(l) SATF [69], (e) GISF [92], and (f-h)(n-p) proposed I, II, and III techniques from the Chapters: 2, 3, and 4 respectively. Segmented by applying a supervised technique called BiSeNet V2 [151], (q)(r) Respective ground truth edges of the two test images.

The superiority of the last three segmentation maps is evident when analyzed across the four metrics: F1-Score, Fragmentation Index (FI), Normalized Mutual Information (NMI), and Hausdorff Distance (HD). While for the first butterfly image the proposed II technique excels in the three different metrics F_1 score (0.4813), FI (0.6833), and HD (70.48) indicating the highest agreement with ground truth, reflecting reduced fragmentation and minimal mismatch. Also, both techniques, the proposed I and III, demonstrate a balanced performance across all the metrics. These metrics collectively highlight the robustness of the last three techniques, with the proposed II standing out as the most consistent performer, demonstrating their overall superiority in handling the trade-offs between precision, fragmentation, agreement, and boundary alignment. Similarly for the second test image of the plunger, all three proposed techniques produce overall well-balanced results, where proposed III excels the most.

5.6 Conclusions

Semantic-aware structure preserving image filtering techniques play a pivotal role in preserving crucial structural information while reducing irrelevant textures and noises in the image. Even if the images produced by such an approach provide rich spatial information, they are seldom used for HSI classification. In this chapter, the semantic edge-aware structure preserving image filtering techniques proposed in this thesis are used to construct ESFPs for spectral-spatial classification of HSI. The performance of the proposed techniques have been validated by comparing it with that of many state-of-the-art spectral-spatial HSI classification techniques that incorporate spatial information by exploiting MRF, MM, segmentation, sparse representation, or deep neural networks. The results of the comparison pointed out the supremacy of the semantic filtering profile over the state-of-the-art techniques for incorporating spatial information. As a future development of this part of work, we plan to use the ESFP as an input to the deep

models for guiding the extraction of more effective features. To the end, in addition to this, the proposed filtering techniques are also validated through semantic segmentation of natural images by one unsupervised technique, MeanShift++, and another supervised technique, BiSeNet V2. The comparative results have shown the potential of the techniques in the overall balanced image segmentation. As a future task as an extension to this part, we plan to develop a new approach for semantic segmentation, incorporating our filtering techniques.

List of publications from this chapter:

Journals

1. Pradhan K., Patra S. and Bruzzone L., “Extended semantic edge-aware filtering profile for hyperspectral image classification,” in IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters, [https://doi: 10.1109/LGRS.2024.3387473](https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2024.3387473). (**IF-4.0**).

Conference

1. K. Pradhan and S. Patra, “ Semantic-Aware Image Filtering for Classification of Hyperspectral Images,” 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Vision and Computing (ICIVC 2023) (*Presented*).

Chapter 6

Conclusions and future scopes

6.1 Concluding remarks

Structure-preserving filters play an important role in many image processing applications. In the last two decades, the developments of filtering techniques has moved from gradient-based edge-preserving filtering to adaptive window-based edge-preserving filtering and region-statistics-based structure-preserving filtering. The concept of structure-preserving filtering is not only to preserve individual edges but also to preserve meaningful objects or structures as a whole while removing insignificant textures. In recent developments, the term semantic-aware structure preserving filtering [145] has been introduced. Defining the semantically meaningful structures of an image is one of the most challenging problems of such filtering. Most of the existing pixel-based or region-based state-of-the-art structure-preserving filtering methods use directional (horizontal and vertical) gradients (or partial derivatives) as structure descriptors, which often fail to preserve the corner edges (i.e., the edges other than horizontal or vertical orientations) properly or often create false edges for different images. They are also prone to removing similar structures (i.e., having similar patterns or statistical features) that are present consecutively. To get the best results from these methods, a huge amount of empirical study is needed by manually defining the neighbor window

size, the region window size, or the parameters of kernel functions. Morphological filters are able to preserve the structure of the objects without using statistical measures, but it heavily depends on the size and shape of the structuring element. In the literature, some recent methods have used adaptive structuring elements for structure-preserving filtering by taking a threshold in bilateral function. Connected component filtering is an advanced version of morphological filtering that can also be applied to preserve the structure of the objects in the image, but it depends on the component ordering and the considered threshold value. Thus, only morphological or connected component filters are not robust enough to develop semantic-aware structure-preserving filters. In the context of current literature, a lot of research is going on towards the development of robust semantic-aware structure-preserving filtering, but no standard generalized technique has yet been developed. In this thesis, we have exploited and combined the properties of both statistical region-based properties with morphological and adaptive median filtering to develop a few robust semantic-aware structure-preserving filters. Finally, we have applied and tested them for effective classification of remote sensing images.

The main challenge for developing a robust structure preserving filtering technique lies in the fact of handling varying scale textural patterns. In order to better handle varying scale textural patterns, in the first contribution we have proposed a semantic-aware structure preserving adaptive median morpho-filtering technique. Our technique defines a novel method to obtain an edge-aware adaptive window of dynamic shape for filtering each pixel by excluding its neighbour pixels belonging to different textural or structural regions. To this end, at first, a novel approach is proposed to generate the edge-map by analysing the skewness of global and local histograms of the morphological gradient. Then, using the generated edge-map a semantic-aware structure preserving adaptive median morpho-filtering is designed by combining the output of median and morphological filters. The major contributions of this research are: i) proposes a texture structure decomposition technique analysing the global and local morphological

6.1. Concluding remarks

gradient distribution, and ii) proposes a combined median morpho-filtering for better texture smoothing while preserving the significant structures. Unlike most of the existing techniques, our filtering can achieve multiple conflicting goals, like protecting structural edges, safeguarding easy-to-miss features such as corners, and Inhibiting over-sharpening and/or over-blurring artifacts/distortions while identifying and removing texture.

Structural edge-aware features are more resilient than textural features for filtering images with varying scales of irregular textures. However, the effectiveness of edge-aware filtering techniques is dependent on their ability to identify the right structural edges. In the second contribution to the thesis, we propose a novel and different approach for structural edge pattern detection than the previous one. It explores Jensen Shannon divergence (JSD) metric to identify the structural edge pattern of the image by considering the semantic information of the image. In this technique, structural edge pattern is defined by exploiting Jensen-Shannon (JS) divergence as a similarity /dissimilarity metric between the approximated real edge and ideal edge or non-edge pattern (step or uniform) in such a way that they incorporate semantic information of the pixel for determining whether it is a structural edge pixel or not. We proposed two different approaches to use this. In the first approach, we directly compared the metric for step and uniform pattern to get the edge-map. Whereas in the second approach, a set of novel features is proposed to represent the pixels of the input image. These features are generated by combining JSD metric and Gaussian mean difference using sigmoid function to generate semantic features of the pixels. By projecting the pixels into the feature space, our technique applied k-means clustering to generate a semantic-aware edge-map of the input image. Once the edge-map is obtained, an edge-aware adaptive recursive median filter is applied to generate the filtered image. Unlike the existing state-of-the-art techniques, the proposed technique reduced the parameter sensitivity and requires minimal manual fine-tuning of its parameters to get best possible results for different input images.

In the third contribution, we propose a novel method that leverages the semantic information of the image to enhance the discrimination between structural and textural edges by combining both the techniques introduced in first and second contribution. Our technique initiates by generating a semantic-aware edge-map through the exploitation of semantic information in two phases. In the first phase, it explores local morphological gradients skewness and mean difference gradient both as semantic feature for initial texture structure decomposition and generate a semantic gradient image (SGI). Then the second phase it uses this SGI to determine the window sizes of each pixels by categorizing pixels into four parts. The second and final layer of texture structure feature generation use JS divergence metric based structural edge pattern detection in the same way as in the first approach of second contribution. This final layer of feature decomposition generates the semantic-aware edge-map. Subsequently, an edge-aware adaptive recursive median filter is utilized to produce the filtered image using this edge map. Although our filtering technique requires defining multiple windows, the sizes and shapes of most of these windows are either automatically determined or remain fixed regardless of the input images under consideration. Only a pair of windows necessitate manual fixing by selecting one of four discrete options. This proposed parameter efficient technique yields satisfactory results across a diverse range of input images with minimal parameter fine-tuning, presenting a significant advantage over current state-of-the-art techniques.

To emphasize the validation of effectiveness through comparative analysis of all the proposed techniques with several state-of-the-art techniques employing a wide variety of images consisting of varying scales of regular and irregular textures. It also applied effectively to few computer graphics applications like image denoising, image enhancement, tone mapping *etc.* These proposed techniques can achieve several competing objectives that cannot be accomplished by using a single existing method, such as detecting and smoothing textures, protecting corners and other areas that are easy to overlook, avoiding over-blurring

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and/or over-sharpening artifacts, and maintaining structural edges. Although all our developed technique successfully works on a variety of images but our present implementation is not of real-time. Implementation of our technique in real-time or near real-time and apply this technique to different image/video processing applications like semantic segmentation, object detection and classification etc would represent an intriguing continuation of this research.

Hence, in the fourth and final contribution we have tested the above presented different semantic filtering based feature extraction in HSI classification. Semantic-aware image filtering techniques discussed in chapter 2, 3, 4 preserve the structures of the objects while removing insignificant textures and noises from the image by considering semantic information. Although filtered images generated by such advanced techniques provide better spatial information, they are seldom exploited for HSI classification. In the fourth and final contribution of this research, we have exploited all the above proposed semantic-aware filtering technique to generate the filtered images of HSI. Then an extended semantic filtering profile (ESFP) is constructed by concatenating the generated filtered images for spectral-spatial classification of HSI. Then the generated ESFP is fed to a random forest (RF) classifier for classifications of land covers of three well established HSI datasets. The effectiveness of the proposed technique has been validated by comparing it with that of many state-of-the-art spectral-spatial HSI classification techniques which incorporate spatial information by exploiting MRF, MM, segmentation, sparse representation, or deep neural networks. The results of the comparison pointed out the superiority of the semantic filtering technique. In the future, this research could explore to use ESFP as an input to the deep models for extracting better features.

Traditional image filtering approaches are usually faster in inference, as they lack the depth and iterative processes of deep learning or sparse optimization. This speed can be a significant advantage for real-time or near real-time applications, where rapid processing is essential. For deep learning architectures,

inference may be slower, especially on hardware without dedicated accelerators (e.g., GPUs or TPUs). Sparse approaches, with their iterative nature, may also have slower inference times due to the convergence checks in each step. While deep learning methods often have lengthy training times. Our developed filtering based approaches generally do not require training (or have very minimal requirements if used within a semi-supervised or unsupervised framework). Sparse methods may involve training but usually involve fewer iterations or layers than deep networks. So the proposed filtering techniques applied to hyperspectral image classifications are computationally much more effective than the existing deep learning or sparse representation based approaches.

6.2 Future scopes

We believe that such developments will have a great impact on other diverse image processing applications too. The future developments of the present work will be in three different directions: one is the real-time/faster implementation of the developed techniques; the second is to explore such techniques in other image and video processing (like real-time semantic segmentation, classification) applications like medical image analysis, text image analysis, *etc*, and the third is to model a robust deep neural network leveraging the proposed semantic features.

Chapter 7

Publication list

The thesis contributions led to the following publications.

Journals

1. Pradhan K., Patra S., “Semantic-aware structure-preserving median morpho-filtering”. *The Visual Computer*, 2023, March 5:1-7, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00371-023-02796-z>. (**IF-3.0**)
2. Pradhan, K., Patra, S. Reduced parameter sensitive edge-aware semantic image filtering. (*Under review to ‘Pattern Analysis and Applications*).
3. Pradhan K, Patra S. A semantic edge-aware parameter efficient image filtering technique. *Computers & Graphics*. 2024 Nov 1;124:104068. (**IF-2.5**)
4. Pradhan K., Patra S. and Bruzzone L., “Extended semantic edge-aware filtering profile for hyperspectral image classification,” in *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, [https://doi: 10.1109/LGRS.2024.3387473](https://doi:10.1109/LGRS.2024.3387473). (**IF-4.0**).

Conference

1. K. Pradhan and S. Patra, "Structure Preserving Semantic Texture Filtering," 2022 IEEE Calcutta Conference (CALCON), Kolkata, India, 2022, pp. 283-287, doi: 10.1109/CALCON56258.2022.10060620.
2. K. Pradhan and S. Patra, "Semantic-Aware Image Filtering for Classification of Hyperspectral Images," 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Vision and Computing (ICIVC 2023) (*Presented*).

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